

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

ALLINTERACT

Report 4

Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences

July 2022

UNIMIB Team

Project Number: 872396

Project Acronym: ALLINTERACT

Project title: Widening and diversifying citizen engagement in science

Executive Summary

1. Introduction

In this document we briefly report our piece of research focused on “*Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences*” (WP4). In particular, the aim of WP4 was to analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent in science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge. In fact, despite the efforts carried out to engage citizens during the last decades, we know that “vulnerable groups” still do not fully participate in science.

In the following paragraphs, we describe the methodology and the main results of our research. We conclude with a summary of the WP4 report’s contribution.

2. Methodology

As for the other WPs, a mixed-method approach to reach the research goal was adopted.

a) *Literature Review*

A systematic review of scientific and grey literature on the topics of “gender” and “education” was done. For “gender”, a subset of 53 particularly relevant articles was analysed; for “education”, a final sample of 43 articles. Each article was analysed accordingly to specific categories and dimensions to identify both factors facilitating or hindering the participation of citizens in science and actions to improve it.

b) *Social Media Analysis and Social Media Communicative Observation*

Starting from 191,233 messages published on Twitter, Facebook, Reddit and Instagram, a set of messages extracted from social media that refers to our topic was analysed. This included a total of 1,238 messages for gender and education. SMCO was conducted on Facebook and Reddit for 6 months and on the evidence-based platforms Sappho and Adhyayana for 15 months.

c) *Focus Groups*

An “intervention study” (composed by a “pre-test”, an “intervention” and a “post-test”) using the focus group technique, was designed with the aim to analyse the level of awareness and engagement of relevant audiences (i.e., students, teachers and parents for education, and members of women’s groups, members of LGBTQI+ groups, and young and vulnerable women, for gender). In particular, twelve focus groups (six for “gender” and six for “education”) were conducted for the “pre-test” phase in order to analyse how citizens’ engagement can be enhanced through awareness raising-actions (for the “intervention” and “post-test” phases see “Work Package 5”).

d) *Survey*

A survey on the European population (7507 cases) aimed at analysing which awareness-raising initiatives and actions are enhancing citizen participation in science as well as the recruitment of new talent for science was conducted.

3. Results

In this section, we present the main results for the WP4.

Barriers but also actions emerge to foster the recruitment of new talent in science

Existing literature review shows that organizational, social, technological and cultural barriers still emerge impeding the process of recruitment of new talent in science. At the same time, scholars identify actions for the recruitment in relation to the following areas: “education”, “organisations

and career”, “ICT/digital divide” and “inclusive communication”. SMA reinforce this finding, showing that messages express more frequently the “transformative” dimension than the “exclusionary” one. Actions mentioned concern: awareness-messages or campaigns, calls for action, corporate and academic initiatives, training, courses and other educational projects. Additionally, in FG participants proposed different actions to foster the participation but they also underlined barriers that hinder it. For instance, vulnerable women agreed that people who participated in science initiatives were often the “same type of people” (i.e., people with the same socio-cultural characteristics or the same biographical paths).

Most of the actions target women and young people

Quantitative results from the survey and SMA conclude that most actions are addressed to women and youth. On the one hand, the results from the survey point out that the best-known initiatives are those that target women in science (33.01%), while the least known are those that target LGBTQI+ individuals (20.70%). Only 9.7% of the total of respondents has participated in actions for the recruitment of new talent. In social networks messages, especially Twitter and Instagram, there are examples of initiatives targeting women and kids/young people, but also migrants and low-income students. On the other hand, FG participants acknowledged the importance of awareness-raising actions. Women were able to provide only a limited number of examples, while parents, teachers and students were more inclined to talk about them.

Interactions with science foster citizen participation in science

In focus groups, parents acknowledged that participating in “Scientific Dialogic Gathering” (see “Work Package 1” for details) increases the awareness and the interest about science results. It encouraged them to attend and to promote other scientific events (talks or conferences) in associations or schools. Teachers valued interactions with role models (e.g., women scientists, young scientists *etc.*) and diverse science contents as important ways to recruit new talent. Survey shows that interactions with science increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who participate in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science. Women and people from low SES are the two groups that benefit more.

People from vulnerable groups value scientific research and recognize its benefits

Survey indicates that in most vulnerable groups the proportion of participants who think that scientific research benefits citizens’ lives ranges from 74.50% (young people) to 76.90% (religious minorities). The only exception is the LGBTQI+ individuals (with 58.82%). Interactions with science improves the perception of the benefits of science in vulnerable groups. The impact is more remarkable when participants follow a scientific person on social networks. People with low SES are the group with a higher increase in their perception of the benefits of science. In focus groups, students expressed the importance of organizing different activities to improve scientific literacy and satisfy aspirations. They expressed the need for further communication campaigns, the inclusion of science-related topics in curricula and equal opportunities for all students.

If science is linked to real life issues (e.g. related to the daily life), people show more involvement, interest and curiosity in science

Literature review shows that there is clearly a strong interest for engagement-events and learning activation when these events are related to daily life issues. In FG participants expressed that their relationship with science derive from both their daily life experiences and their curiosity towards science. Participation in the discussion of everyday topics with scientific evidence increases self-confidence in people who are not used to getting involved in science. This result has gained much

relevance during the pandemic, during which individual and public health concerns have affected all citizens, but in particular women because of their familiar responsibilities (children, parents, people with disabilities etc.) or their professional roles (e.g., they work more in the public or social sectors and so on). In this new context, science has become unexpectedly part of their daily lives. Finally, quantitative results from the international survey show that changing their mind because something happened to them or their families promotes knowledge of and participation in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science.

Social media provides opportunities to interact with science that foster initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science

Across vulnerable groups, following a person who publishes about science on social media is associated with higher knowledge and with participation in these initiatives. In this line, SMA shows that diverse awareness-raising initiatives emerge across social networks. One of the initiatives found in the literature review is the creation of a digital learning resource for citizens to learn how they can participate in the creation of smart cities. The literature review concludes that initiatives should take advantage of ICT to bridge the digital divide and facilitate new ways of learning, especially for young people.

Initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science are promoted by diverse agents

SMA points out that initiatives designed with a top-down approach prevail because of the presence of representatives of institutional actors (NGO, government, enterprises, universities). Bottom-up initiatives are less frequent, but more emotionally involved. In the literature review and in the FG, schools, universities and national institutions emerged as the main promoters of the initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science.

4. Conclusion

The Report WP4 contributes to understand more deeply the factors that hinder or facilitate the participation of new talent in science. It highlights the type of actions and their multiple targets, the level of awareness and engagement, the citizens' perception of the benefits of science, the role of social media in fostering the recruitment of vulnerable groups. Furthermore, the analysis shows that vulnerable groups value scientific research and recognize its benefits in their daily lives. However, their participation to targeted-actions is still limited, as their level of access to scientific evidence. Literature review, focus groups and survey suggest that interaction with science fosters the participation; furthermore, if science is linked to real life issues (e.g., related to the daily life), people show more interest and curiosity. Participation in the discussion of everyday topics with scientific evidence increases self-confidence in people who are not used to getting involved in science, as well as communicating its social impact can help their engagement and their participation in the scientific enterprise.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Literature review.....	7
2.1. Overview.....	7
2.2. Gender	7
2.2.1. Overview	7
2.2.2. Methodology.....	7
2.2.3. Analysis.....	12
2.2.4. Results.....	44
2.3. Education.....	49
2.3.1. Overview	49
2.3.2. Methodology.....	49
2.3.3. Analysis.....	52
2.3.4. Results.....	85
2.4. Conclusion.....	89
2.5. References	90
3. Social Media Analytics.....	97
3.1. Overview.....	97
3.2. Methodology.....	97
3.2.1. Social Media Analysis (SMA)	97
3.2.2. Social Media Communicative Observation (SMCO).....	101
3.3. Results for SMA	110
3.3.1. Gender	110
3.3.2. Education	119
3.4. Conclusion.....	128
3.5. Results for SMCO.....	129
3.6. Conclusion.....	130
4. Focus Groups.....	131
4.1. Overview.....	131
4.2. Methodology.....	131
4.2.1. Gender	132
4.2.2. Education	138
4.3. Analysis.....	142
4.4. Results	142
4.4.1. Gender	142

4.4.2. Education	149
4.5. Conclusion.....	159
5. Survey.....	162
5.1. Overview.....	162
5.2. Sociodemographic questions.....	163
5.3. Actions for the recruiting of vulnerable groups in science	171
Knowledge of actions for the recruitment in science	171
Responses by vulnerable groups	173
The impact of interactions	174
Participation in actions for the recruitment in science	177
Responses by vulnerable groups	177
The impact of interactions	180
5.4. The importance of scientific research.....	187
Benefits of scientific research.....	187
Responses by vulnerable groups	187
The impact of interactions	190
Investment in scientific research.....	196
Responses by vulnerable groups	198
The impact of interactions	204
5.5. Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence	217
Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education.....	218
Responses by vulnerable groups	220
The impact of interactions	223
Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender	233
Responses by vulnerable groups	235
The impact of interactions	238
5.6. Interpretation of the data	248
5.7. Conclusion.....	466
6. <i>Online workshop with KAPIs members.....</i>	<i>469</i>
7. <i>Conclusion.....</i>	<i>470</i>

1. Introduction

The overall task of WP4 of the ALLINTERACT project is to explore the awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences considering two topics: gender and education.

In order to respond to this objective, a series of tasks have been conducted, namely a Literature Review, a Social Media Analytics, Focus Groups and a Survey. Different Consortium partners have been involved in the aforementioned tasks and analyses that integrate this report coordinated by the University of Milano-Bicocca.

2. Literature review

2.1. Overview

In response to O4, the literature review on “awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences” was conducted. In the following section we present the methodology and the results for gender and education.

Findings of this literature review informed the other parts of the research: the design and development of the social media communicative intervention, the focus groups, the survey, as well as of the interventions and policy recommendations which will be presented in other deliverables of the project.

2.2. Gender

2.2.1. Overview

This section provides information regarding the literature review of on awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences (O4). With this aim, a systematic literature review has been conducted in Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases. In addition, grey literature has been searched to complete the task. This part includes the methodology followed in this literature review, with a focus on gender, the analysis, the results obtained and the main conclusions.

2.2.2. Methodology

In the first phase, a literature review was conducted following the guidelines concerning the selection of the sources, the collection of the information and the analysis.

In the second phase, a categorization of the literature review was conducted following a specific grid to highlight the contribution of each study on the awareness-raising actions.

1) FIRST PHASE

Sources selection and keywords

The research team carried out the literature review starting from the selection of articles in two ways: to ensure that articles from top journals in the field are considered in first place, the research team focused on the most important journals in the field “Science and Technology Studies” using the list provided by the Society for Social Studies of Science: (<https://www.4sonline.org>). These journals are:

- “Science, Technology and Human Values”.
- “Social Studies of Science”.
- “Public Understanding of Science”.
- “Minerva”.
- “Engaging Science Technology and Society”.
- “Science and Technology Studies”.
- “Catalyst: Feminism, Theory and Technoscience”.
- “East Asian Technology and Society”.
- “Tapuya: Latin American Science, Technology and Society”.

We added to the above list “Science Communication” and “Journal of Science Communication” to enlarge the range of opportunities to discover articles on public engagement and science-citizens dialogue topics.

Second, the research team used Google scholar and Scopus to have a wider host of articles from journals in different research areas, in particular Gender and Women Studies.

In both steps the team used the list of keywords that was previously validated by the Unimib group (the list was shared in the All Interact workspace). The keywords are:

- Gender equality/equal opportunity and science
- Women/girls and science
- Gender, career and science
- Inclusion and science
- Gender stereotypes/prejudices/bias and science
- Sexism/discrimination and science
- Gender training and science
- Science citizenship and gender
- Public engagement of science and gender
- Science communication and gender
- Science, attitudes, gender/women
- Science, media, gender

When a new keyword emerged after the article’s analysis, it was added together with the others.

1. Criteria for article selection:

We collected all articles from 2010 to 2021 showing one or more keywords inside the title or the abstract. For each article in the collection, the research team checked:

1) The journal quartile (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4) as indexed in “Journal Citations Reports”; “Scimago” was used when JCR was not found. 2) The article impact, measured by the total number of citations resulting from Scopus.

We kept for literature review only articles in the first two quartiles (Q1 and Q2) with a relevant number of citations. We avoided selecting only USA articles and tried to cover non-Anglo-Saxon research too. We include some international reports (e.g. Unesco, European Commission).

Selected articles and literature review

In this way the research team selected 120 articles and analysed a subset of 53 particularly relevant articles excluding:

- redundant topics articles.
- marginal topics articles.
- short papers without empirical research.

In the literature review the articles were partitioned in three main areas:

- *Public perception, public engagement/participation in Science and Technology (S&T) and gender (13 articles)*
- *Under-representation of women in STEM curricula (13 articles)*
- *Under-representation of women in STEM careers (25 articles)*
- *Gender, innovation and the feminist perspective (4 articles)*

The “Lit review grid” (see Table 2.1.) provides an overview of these articles organized along the following categories: main area, full reference, journal title, JCR classification impact (quartile), article impact (number of citations):

Table 2.1 - Literature review grid

N.	Main area	Full Reference	Journal title	JCR Class	Article number Citations (Scopus)
1	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Johnson KM, Simon RM. Women's Attitudes Toward Biomedical Technology for Infertility: The Case for Technological Salience. <i>Gender & Society</i> . 2012;26(2):261-289.	<i>Gender & Society</i>	Q1	9
2	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Cornelia Fraune. Gender matters: Women, renewable energy, and citizen participation in Germany. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i> , 7, 2015, Pages 55-65, ISSN 2214-6296, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.02.005 .	<i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>	Q1	32
3	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Haynes RD. Whatever happened to the 'mad, bad' scientist? Overturning the stereotype. <i>Public Understanding of Science</i> . 2016;25(1):31-44.	<i>Public Understanding of Science</i>	Q1	20
4	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	The gender gap on public opinion towards genetically modified foods, <i>The Social Science Journal</i> , Volume 55, Issue 4, 2018, Pages 500-509, ISSN 0362-3319, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscj.2018.02.015 .	<i>The Social Science Journal</i>	Q2/Q3	6
5	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Bren S, Seel, Rebecca L, Warner and Denise Lach, Gender Differences in Support for Scientific Involvement in U.S. Environmental, in <i>Science, Technology, & Human Values</i> , March 2010, Vol. 35, No. 2 (March 2010), pp. 147-173	<i>Science, Technology and Human Values</i>	Q1	10
6	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Losh SC. Stereotypes about scientists over time among US adults: 1983 and 2001. <i>Public Understanding of Science</i> . 2010;19(3):372-382. doi:10.1177/0963662509098576	<i>Public Understanding of Science</i>	Q1	37
7	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Helzlsouer A and Lowenstein H (2014) Is She an Expert or Just a Woman? Gender Differences in the Presentation of Experts in TV Talk Shows. <i>Sex Roles</i> 70(9): 376–386. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-014-0370-z	<i>Sex Roles</i>	Q1/Q2	5
8	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Anzolino, M., Ceravolo, F.A. & Rostan, M. The two dimensions of Italian academics' public engagement. <i>High Educ</i> (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-020-00624-0	<i>Higher Education</i>	Q1	0
9	Public perception, public engagement/participation in S&T and gender	Simon RM. Gendered contexts: masculinity, knowledge, and attitudes toward biotechnology. <i>Public Underst Sci</i> . 2011 May;20(3):334-46. doi: 10.1177/0963662509344272. PMID: 21796882.	<i>Public Understanding of Science</i>	Q1	7

Each article was analysed as the follow (see the document “Literature review” uploaded in the ALLINTERACT workspace by UNIMIB):

Key word search	Gender, STEM, stereotypes
Reference	<i>Louise Archer, Jennifer DeWitt, Jonathan Osborne, Justin Dillon, Beatrice Willis & Billy Wong (2013) 'Not girly, not sexy, not glamorous': primary school girls' and parents' constructions of science aspirations, Pedagogy, Culture & Society, 21:1, 171-194, DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748676</i>
Aim	Understanding children’s science aspirations and career choice to explore the reasons why, even from a young age, many girls may see science aspirations as ‘not for me’.
Participants/target	10–14-year-old children
Geography	USA
Methodology	five-year longitudinal study
Findings	Science aspirations are largely ‘unthinkable’ for girls because they do not fit with either their constructions of desirable/intelligible femininity nor with their sense of themselves as learners/students. We argue that an underpinning construction of science careers as ‘clever’/‘brainy’, ‘not nurturing’ and ‘geeky’ sits in opposition to the girls’ self-identifications as ‘normal’, ‘girly’, ‘caring’ and ‘active’. This lack of fit is exacerbated by social inequalities, which render science aspirations potentially less thinkable for working-class girls in particular.
Conclusions	Work might usefully be undertaken to open up popular perceptions of the sciences, and the cultures that operate within the sciences, to render them more accessible for ‘non-traditional’ groups. In particular, careful attention might be paid to how the sciences might encourage and value broader forms of participation and engagement, such that children can see that careers in/from science welcome and embrace a wide range of identity performances (e.g. not just being ‘clever’ and geeky). It would also appear valuable to increase the potential for (and/or families’ awareness of) more diverse forms of participation in post-compulsory science. The children and parents largely saw science jobs only in terms of becoming a scientist (or doctor or science teacher), suggesting little public awareness of either the diversity contained within ‘being a scientist’, nor of the immense diversity of jobs from science.

2) SECOND PHASE

In this phase the findings for O4 (literature review) were organised following the table below. It classifies every action presented in the article analysing it on the basis of:

- a) the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the implementation of the targeted actions);
- b) the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the implementation of the targeted actions).

Table 2.2 - Exclusionary and transformative dimensions grid

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
	Transformative								
	Exclusionary								

2.2.3. Analysis

Cornelia Fraune (2015) *Gender matters: Women, renewable energy, and citizen participation in Germany*, “Energy Research & Social Science”, 7, 55-65.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding how the larger social, cultural, and political context fosters and constrains people's agency to take part in citizen participation schemes in renewable electricity production (RES-E).	Public	National/ Germany	Energy	Citizens (Women and men) that own energy plants	Citizens were interviewed to gather data	Interviews and survey data to collect information. The results give an indication of the existence of cultural, social and political factors affecting gender differences in participation in RES-E operated by citizens' associations.	Increase the participation in renewable electricity production
	Exclusionary Dimension	Two structural outcomes of the gendered distribution of labor are of special importance in terms of citizen participation schemes in RES-E: the gender wealth gap and gendered occupational segregation.							

Bren S. Seel, Rebecca L. Warner and Denise Lach (2010) *Gender Differences in Support for Scientific Involvement in U.S. Environmental*, in “Science, Technology, & Human Values”, Vol. 35, No. 2, 147-173.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	To study the relationship of gender to attitudes toward science and preferred roles of scientists in environmental policy among various environmental policy participants	Public	National /USA	Environment	Different groups involved in environmental policy	Respondents	Questionnaire to people involved in environmental policies. Women were less supportive of positivistic view of science than men; there was no significant gender difference in the expressed preferences for scientist role in policy making; Women are more likely than men to support a post-normal integrative role of the scientist	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	Education, training, and occupation are critical variables that can exclude women.							

Taragin-Zeller L, Rozenblum Y, Baram-Tsabari (2020) *A Public Engagement with Science Among Religious Minorities: Lessons From COVID-19*, in “Science Communication”, 42(5):643-678.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Drawing on the disproportionate magnitude of COVID-19-related morbidity on Israel's Ultra-Orthodox Jews, the article examines their processes of COVID-19 health decision making. More inclusive communications should thus promote more culturally specific science communication by considering specific communal sensibilities, “local moral worlds” and state-minority power relations	University	National/Israeli	Health	Haredi community -- Israel's Ultra-Orthodox Jews (women and men)	Respondents/Questionnaire	Compliance with health recommendations for personal decisions (where health and religious norms conflicted) was associated with using more health-related justifications and sources of information than religious ones.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	A critical point is the disparity between the ways public health guidelines are perceived in the context of general education as compared with the ways guidelines should be applied in a religious context.							

Anzivino, M., Ceravolo, F.A. & Rostan, M. (2020) *The two dimensions of Italian academics' public engagement*, in "Higher Education", 82, 107-125.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The article studies the Italian academics' Public Engagement "Local Community Engagement" (LCE)* and "General Political Engagement" ** (GPE). Being female favoured participation in LCE activities compared to being male, while no gender difference was recorded for involvement in GPE activities	University	National/Italy	Science	academics	Respondents/Survey	Analysis of national survey on academics' third mission. When PE activities are aimed at personal development or have a broad educational purpose and are addressing the local community, academic women are more likely to be strongly involved in them than academic men. No differences between men and women were found for PE activities aimed at solving societally relevant problems, that have a possible range of application settings from local to global.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Pamela R. Aschbacher, Erika Li, Ellen J. Roth (2010) *Is science me? High school students' identities, participation and aspirations in science, engineering, and medicine*, in “Journal of Research in Science Teaching”, Volume 47, Issue 5, 564-582.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim: private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding why some who were once very interested in science, engineering, or medicine (SEM) majors or careers decided to leave the pipeline in high school while others persisted.	University	National/USA	STEM	Students (33 high schools)	Respondents	Longitudinal interviews and survey. Results underscore the key role communities of practice play in career and identity development and suggest a need for interventions to encourage students to appreciate science, be aware of possible career options in science and enjoy learning and doing science	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Gender interacting with ethnicity and socio-economic categories seemed to play a role in under-represented minority students' aspirations and pipeline participation.							

Kurtz-Costes, B., Copping, K.E., Rowley, S.J. *et al.* (2014) *Gender and age differences in awareness and endorsement of gender stereotypes about academic abilities*, in “Eur J Psychol Educ” 29, 603–618.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Analysing gender stereotypes on academic abilities in children of different school grades	University	National/USA	STEM	Children	Respondents/questionnaire.	Children's reports of their own gender stereotypes were correlated with their perceptions of adults' gender stereotypes.	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	Children's tendency to favour girls in verbal domains may contribute to gender differences in educational and career choices by pulling girls toward the humanities and social sciences and discouraging boys from pursuing those domains.							

Louise Archer, Jennifer DeWitt, Jonathan Osborne, Justin Dillon, Beatrice Willis & Billy Wong (2013) *'Not girly, not sexy, not glamorous': primary school girls' and parents' constructions of science aspirations*, in "Pedagogy, Culture & Society", 21:1, 171-194.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding children's science aspirations and career choice to explore the reasons why, even from a young age, many girls may see science aspirations as 'not for me'. Work might usefully be undertaken to open up popular perceptions of the sciences, and the cultures that operate within the sciences, to render them more accessible for 'non-traditional' groups.	University	National	STEM	10–14-year-old children	They were interviewed.	Longitudinal study. Science aspirations are largely 'unthinkable' for girls because they do not fit with either their constructions of desirable/intelligible femininity nor with their sense of themselves as learners/students.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	The children and parents largely saw science jobs only in terms of becoming a scientist (or doctor or science teacher), suggesting little public awareness of either the diversity contained within 'being a scientist', nor of the immense diversity of jobs from science.							

Rainey, K., Dancy, M., Mickelson, R. et al. (2018) *Race and gender differences in how sense of belonging influences decisions to major in STEM*, in “International Journal of STEM Education” 5, 10.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding the causes of the under-representation of science (gender and ethnicity)	University	National	STEM	Women/students who either majored in STEM or started but dropped a STEM major.	They were interviewed.	Students from underrepresented groups are less likely to feel they belong (lack of social and personal connections with peers, lack of interest, poor grade, low performance).	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Structural and cultural features of universities, as well as STEM curricula and pedagogy, continue to privilege white males							

Moss-Racusin, C., Sanzari, C., Caluori, N., & Rabasco, H. (2018) *Gender bias produces gender gaps in STEM engagement*, in “Sex Roles”, 79(11-12), 651-670.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding whether the existence of gender bias causes gender gaps in STEM engagement. Evidence-based interventions targeting gender bias are needed to boost women's representation.	University	International	STEM	Participants (women/men) were recruited through Amazon's Mechanical Turk (MTurk)/Participants recruited in the Chemical Dep.	They participated to an experiment	When explicitly exposed to the reality of bias in the gender bias condition, women expected to experience less sense of belonging, positive attitudes, and aspirations to participate in STEM than did men.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Results were largely unaffected by whether departments completed a diversity training, suggesting that knowledge of diversity initiatives alone cannot close STEM gender gaps.							

Leaper C, Starr CR. (2019) *Helping and Hindering Undergraduate Women's STEM Motivation: Experiences with STEM Encouragement, STEM-Related Gender Bias, and Sexual Harassment*, in "Psychology of Women Quarterly", 43(2):165-183.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim: private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding whether women's experiences of sexual harassment and STEM-related gender bias negatively predicted their STEM motivation and STEM career aspirations; whether STEM encouragement from friends and family positively predicted motivation and aspirations.	University	National	STEM	Undergraduate Women	Respondents to a survey	Perceived encouragement and experiences with discrimination may strengthen or weaken women's motivation and aspirations in STEM. By identifying sources that impede or help, policy makers and administrators can develop and implement interventions aimed to foster the STEM motivation of all children and adults	
	Exclusionary Dimension	STEM-related gender bias from classmates and sexual harassment from instructors (faculty, teaching assistants, or graduate students) were negatively related to STEM motivation and career aspirations.							

Legewie J, DiPrete TA. (2014) *The High School Environment and the Gender Gap in Science and Engineering*, in “Sociology of Education” 87(4): 259-280.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Studying the role of the high school context for plans to major in STEM field.	University	National/USA	STEM	High school students	Respondents- National Education Longitudinal Study/sensitive analysis	Going to a school that supports girls' STEM orientations reduces the gender gap by 25 percent more, and the school's impact durable. High school context influence choices and preferences, so policy intervention can promote a change on high school CV.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Two characteristics influence the gender gap in plans: high school curriculum in STEM and gender segregation of extracurricular activities.							

Brittany Bloodhart, Meena M. Balgopal, Anne Marie A. Casper, Laura B. Sample McMeeking, Emily V. Fischer (2020) *Outperforming yet undervalued: Undergraduate women in STEM*, in PLOSone.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The article examines 1) whether college STEM students continue to hold gender biases about the abilities of their peers, particularly compared to women's and men's actual performance and 2) student views about the ability of their peers in life sciences versus physical sciences, where the general representation of women typically differs substantially	University	National/USA	STEM	Students enrolled in STEM courses	Respondents to a survey.	Undergraduate women may not be able to escape gender-ability stereotypes even when they are outperforming men, which has important implications for 1) the recognition of women's achievements among their peers in undergraduate education and 2) retention of women in STEM disciplines and careers.	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	The persistence of gender stereotypes.							

Starr CR. (2018) *‘I’m Not a Science Nerd!’: STEM Stereotypes, Identity, and Motivation Among Undergraduate Women*, in “Psychology of Women Quarterly” 42(4): 489-503.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		Aim of the enhancing/ participation action	Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)	Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)	Field of intervention	Participants (targeted and real)	Type of participation (role of the participants)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social Impact
Article	Transformative Dimension	Would stereotyping STEM as a domain for nerdy geniuses negatively relate to women’s STEM identity? Would STEM identity mediate the relation between stereotypes and STEM motivation? Interventions might incorporate growth-mindset (to counteract the genius stereotype), employ STEM role models that vary in both gender and behaviour and traits, and directly address nerd-genius stereotypes.	University	National/USA	STEM	Undergraduate	Respondents to a survey	This study points to the negative effect a variety of stereotypes have on STEM identity among a diverse group of undergraduate women. Implicitly associating science with men was negatively related to STEM identity.	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	Endorsing stereotypes that people who work in STEM are nerdy geniuses who are tech obsessed, have no social lives, and are not successful romantically was negatively related to STEM identity and, in turn, to motivation							

Ernesto Reuben, Paola Sapienza, Luigi Zingales (2014) *How stereotypes impair women's careers in science*, in “Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences”, 111 (12) 4403-4408.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim: private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The authors studied the effect of gender stereotypes in an experimental market, where subjects were hired to perform an arithmetic task that, on average, both genders perform equally well.	Public	National/USA	Math	Adults	Participation to a laboratory experiment	There is a strong bias to hire women. Objective information about past performance (how subjects actually performed on the task) attenuated sex-biased decision-making in this context but failed to eliminate it, especially in employers who showed a stronger implicit sex bias.	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	Implicit stereotypes predict gender-related expectations.							

Wynn AT, Correll SJ. (2018) *Puncturing the pipeline: Do technology companies alienate women in recruiting sessions?* in “Social Studies of Science” 48(1):149-164.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The authors study if technology companies create environments that may dampen women's interest at the juncture when they are launching their careers. Recruiters may puncture the pipeline, lessening the interest of women at the point of recruitment into technology careers. Particularly in male-dominated fields, companies have an opportunity to increase the representation of women by being more mindful of the images they project in recruitment sessions, interviews, and the workplace more generally.	Public	National/USA	Technology	Women	Analysis of observational data from 84 recruiting sessions	In a process that lacks clear guidelines or regulations, recruiters strive to be personable, relatable, and interesting to their student audiences.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	In a process that lacks clear guidelines or regulations, recruiters strive to be personable, relatable, and interesting to their student audiences. Through their presentations, interactional styles, and the images they project, companies convey a gendered sense of who will fit best in their company culture. Company representatives often engage in behaviours that are known to create a chilly environment for women. By emphasizing geeky masculinity, they risk appealing only to a narrow range of men and virtually no women							

Liza Howe-Walsh & Sarah Turnbull (2016) *Barriers to women leaders in academia: tales from science and technology*, in “Studies in Higher Education”, 41:3, 415-428.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The article examines women’s experiences regarding the perceived barriers to leadership in ST faculties in UK universities.	Public	National/UK	Research/University	Women leader in ST faculties	Women interviewed	were	The authors highlight the gendered nature of ST faculties and how women struggle to navigate their careers. The investigation illustrates the effect of organisational influences such as temporary work arrangements, male-dominated networks, intimidation and harassment, as well as individual influences such as lack of confidence.
	Exclusionary Dimension	The male-dominated culture influences daily working practices, and the evidence suggests that exclusion from networks limits opportunities for career advancement. Male-dominated culture led women to feel intimidated and consider leaving the organisation.							

Tarja Tiainen & Eleni Berki (2019) *The re-production process of gender bias: a case of ICT professors through recruitment in a gender-neutral country*, in “Studies in Higher Education”, 44: 1, 170-184.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding the recruiting/selection process and the possible bias, starting from the under-representation of women in ICT issue. The authors analyse the discrepancy between the formalized policy and the recruiting selection process.	Public	National/Finland	Technology	Women	Secondary analysis data (webpages/CV/university documents); Case study of the School.	The analysis of the case study shows that the process is not gender-neutral; it is necessary to implement equal opportunity organisational practices (as mentoring) to avoid discrimination	//
	Exclusionary Dimension	When the evaluators know the gender of the applicants, male applicants might be valued higher than female one with similar CVs. This bias is based on the predisposition which connects masculinity to technology and professionalism, and that strengthens the evaluators' impression of male candidates' competence.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Eaton, A.A., Saunders, J.F., Jacobson, R.K. *et al.* (2020) *How Gender and Race Stereotypes Impact the Advancement of Scholars in STEM: Professors' Biased Evaluations of Physics and Biology Post-Doctoral Candidates*, in "Sex Roles" 82, 127-141.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Studying how intersecting stereotypes about gender and race influence faculty perceptions of post-doctoral candidates in STEM fields in the United States. To have STEM job candidates submit materials that do not include their full names, but only surnames, which are inevitably present in citations of publications and presentations. This may reduce the operation of gender biases in the evaluation of candidates' materials; change post-doctoral hiring protocol to include additional checks and balances. Including additional faculty members in the evaluation of post-doctorates, from colleagues to administrators, may help to expose and/or undermine the operation of biases that an individual PI might have.	Public	National/USA	Science/University	Post-docs	Experimental design: Eight large, public, U.S. research universities were asked to read one of eight identical curriculum vitae (CVs) depicting a hypothetical doctoral graduate applying for a post-doctoral position in their field, and rate them for competence, hire-ability, and likeability. The candidate's name on the CV was used to manipulate race (Asian, Black, Latinx, and White) and gender (female or male), with all other aspects of the CV held constant across conditions	Faculty in physics exhibited a gender bias favouring the male candidates as more competent and more hireable than the otherwise identical female candidates. An interaction between candidate gender and race emerged for those in physics, whereby Black women and Latin women and men candidates were rated the lowest.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Faculty in physics exhibited a gender bias favouring the male candidates as more competent and more hireable than the otherwise identical female candidates.							

Hardcastle, V.G., Furst-Holloway, S., Kallen, R. and Jacquez, F. (2019), *It's complicated: a multi-method approach to broadening participation in STEM*, in "Equality, Diversity and Inclusion", Vol. 38 No. 3, pp. 349-361.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The authors describe several examples of research, programming activities and program evaluation (with particular attention to NSF ADVANCE-IT) in order to help others to avoid common mistakes by articulating very broad and generalizable "lessons learned" about the inclusion of minorities in STEM career.	Public	National/USA	Research/Science	Women	A Case study designed by an iterative methodology (a social network analysis, an exit survey of departed faculty, a longitudinal analysis of career trajectories and research productivity, and a survey on the interaction between values and climate).	The pay-off for using more complex research approach to triangulate onto specific challenges is that the interventions are more likely to be successful, with a longer-lasting impact. The analysis suggests the following strategies: improve professional networks realign policy documents and departmental practices to better reflect faculty's values improve departmental climates.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Corinne A. Moss-Racusin, John F. Dovidio, Victoria L. Brescoll, Mark J. Graham, Jo Handelsman (2012) *Faculty's subtle gender biases favour male students*, in "Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences", 109 (41) 16474-16479.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	<p>The authors analyse whether science faculty exhibit a bias against female students that could contribute to the gender disparity in academic science.</p> <p>Interventions addressing faculty gender bias might advance the goal of increasing the participation of women in science.</p>	Public	National/USA	Different disciplines	Students/Faculty	Randomized double blind study: science faculty from research-intensive universities rated the application materials of a student—who was randomly assigned either a male or female name—for a laboratory manager position.	Faculty participants rated the male applicant as significantly more competent and hireable than the (identical) female applicant. These participants also selected a higher starting salary and offered more career mentoring to the male applicant. The gender of the faculty participants did not affect responses.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Negin Sattari, Rebecca Sandefur (2019) *Gender in academic STEM: A focus on men faculty*, in “Gender, Work and Organisation”, 26: 158-179.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The authors analyse how men faculty understand the role of gender in shaping faculty experiences in academic science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) and how they position themselves in relation to inequalities disfavouring women. Findings show the important implications of men's sensitivity to gender in the ways they perform their professional roles as, for example, mentors, colleagues, and teachers in relation to women in STEM. They further call for attention to men's perceptions of gender issues when designing institutional interventions for improving women's conditions in STEM.	Public	National/USA	STEM	Faculty	Semi-structured in-depth interviews	The data reveal diversity among men in their understandings regarding challenges facing women in STEM. Most participants revealed gender blind perspectives and argued that the egalitarian structure of academia does not allow gender to impact attainments in STEM in any significant way.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Hirsu, L., Quezada-Reyes, Z. & Hashemi, L. (2021) *Moving SDG5 forward: women's public engagement activities in higher education*, in "High Education" 81, 51-67.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Universities play a critical role in the delivery of the Sustainable Development Goals through the third mission, i.e. public engagement activities. However, female academics miss opportunities to be part of this mission because they are caught in many roles that prevent them from getting involved in the SDGs. In light of SDG5, the authors investigate women aspirations, opportunities and experiences with public engagement activities.	Public	National/Iran and Philippines	Science	20 Women academics	Women were interviewed.	While recent gender policies have enabled female academics to develop robust careers, their contributions beyond the walls of the university remain limited because of longstanding patriarchal structures, distrust in women's professional expertise and unchanged systemic constraints.	HE institutions may enhance their third mission and better achieve the targets of SDGs by valuing women's work and facilitating their engagement activities that may lead to significant societal impact. The authors propose: a) Flexibility of work and more fluid working spaces b) Increased access to international professional organisations c) Training women in skills and capacities that enable them to fully engage in the TM; d) Parity in professional support e) Inequalities among LGBTQI staff should be addressed explicitly and fully
	Exclusionary Dimension								

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Laura Fogg-Rogers and Laura Hobbs (2019) *Catch 22 — improving visibility of women in science and engineering for both recruitment and retention*, in “Journal of Science Communication”.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Understanding how enhancing women engagement in science.	Public	National/UK	STEM	Women	They answered to a questionnaire	Enhancing self-efficacy for female scientists and engineers to mentor others will generate more supportive workplaces. Similarly, enhancing self-efficacy for public engagement improves the visibility of diverse female role models for young girls.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Clem Herman Suzan Lewis Anne Laure Humbert (2013) *Women Scientists and Engineers in European Companies: Putting Motherhood under the Microscope*, in “Gender, Work and Organization”, Volume 20, Issue 5, 467-478.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Examining the experiences of women SET professionals in three European companies, with particular attention to how motherhood rather than gender alone influences the path.	Public	France, The Netherlands and Italy	SET	Women	They were interviewed	Authors propose a set of strategies that women adopt in doing motherhood and SET. Furthermore, the careers of SET professionals in industry are shaped not only by corporate cultures and practices but also by the specific national contexts in which they live and work.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	While all three companies had policies that were aimed at addressing the work–life balance and supporting employees who were mothers, these appear to have been implemented differently in different circumstances and their success or lack of success often depended on the attitudes and actions of their immediate line managers.							

Bevan V, Learmonth M. '(2013) *I wouldn't say it's sexism, except that ... It's all these little subtle things*': Healthcare scientists' accounts of gender in healthcare science laboratories, in "Social Studies of Science" 43(1), 136-158.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The authors explore healthcare scientists' accounts of men in healthcare science laboratories.	Public	National/USA	Health	Men and women health scientists (public and private laboratories)	42 in-depth interviews	While women act and behave within healthcare science, the discourses constituting masculinity and femininity typically reinforce interpretations that men are more suited to high-level posts than women. Men were thought subtly to treat women as though they were inferior to men; however, it is apparent from the interviews that women rarely challenge male behaviour they see as problematic, finding ways to cope that typically reinforce their subordination.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	The authors indicate continuing subtle forms of discrimination that largely go unnoticed – by both women and men alike in healthcare science.							

Valentina Tartari, Ammon Salter (2015) *The engagement gap: Exploring gender differences in University – Industry collaboration activities*, in Research Policy, Volume 44, Issue 6, 1176-1191.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Exploring gender differences in University – Industry collaboration activities.	Public	National7UK	Industry and Engineering	Physical and engineering scientists	Respondents.	Secondary data analysis and survey questionnaire for testing hypotheses. The study suggests that women engage in less with industry than their male counterparts with industry. The difference between men and women in engagement efforts was present only in organizations with no significant formal commitment to supporting women in science and engineering academic careers. Moreover, the stark differences between younger women and male academics in industry engagement are attenuated in universities that are committed to promoting women in science and engineering. Policies designed to help women in science may be an effective means to enable women to engage with industry as a critical element in their academic careers.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Universities without policies to improve the participation of women in science							

McKinnon, M., O'Connell, C. (2020) *Perceptions of stereotypes applied to women who publicly communicate their STEM work*, in “Humanities Social Sciences Communication” 7, 160.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	This study explores the perceptions of the stereotypes applied to female STEM professionals who publicly speak about their work in both academic and non-academic settings.	Public	Australia, New Zealand, USA and Japan	STEM	300 researchers (STEM professionals)	300 researchers (STEM professionals) participating to specific workshops on gender during conferences	Focus Groups and Qualitative analysis to analyse stereotypes. The results show different stereotype categories for women in science who publicly communicate their work.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	Women may be in a more vulnerable position when communicating publicly about their work. Systematic cultural and institutional change is needed in STEM fields to address the underlying bias and negative stereotypes facing women. However, it should be ensured that the intended solutions to facilitate this change are not compounding the problem.							

Xu, Y.J., Martin, C.L. (2011) *Gender Differences in STEM Disciplines: From the Aspects of Informal Professional Networking and Faculty Career Development*, in “Gender Issues” 28, 134.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	This study examines informal professional networks (IPNs) and their role in the underrepresentation of women faculty in traditionally male-dominated science. Open communication between genders is needed for women to even have access to some established networks in STEM fields. Administrators can help women faculty with their professional networking is to design programs that help women faculty initiate contact with established colleagues in their discipline. For instance, following the example of the Kansas State University ADVANCE Institutional Transformation project, university administrators may assist and support women faculty to invite elite scholars in their fields for a campus visit and presentation. A second approach is for the university to organize regular informal gatherings within a department or college to give faculty members opportunities to have more interactions. Better communication would lead to increased chances for collaboration. Finally, the STEM departments should encourage senior faculty to serve as mentors for entry-level faculty members.	Public	National	Technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines.	Women/men in STEM dep.	They were interviewed and responded to a questionnaire	Mixed-method approach (interview and on-line survey). The authors show the different perspectives on IPN that influences the participation of women to science.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Miller, D. I., Eagly, A. H., & Linn, M. C. (2015) *Women's representation in science predicts national gender-science stereotypes: Evidence from 66 nations*, in "Journal of Educational Psychology", 107(3), 631–644.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	<p>The article studies how national differences in women's science participation related to gender-science stereotypes that associate science with men more than women.</p> <p>Science educators could help weaken stereotypes by highlighting diverse examples of female scientists. Presenting single or infrequent examples of female scientists will likely not substantially change gender-STEM stereotypes.</p>	Public	66 nations	Science	Women/Men of different nations	Respondents	Statistical analysis. The results indicated that participants across 66 nations strongly associated science with men more than women, including in nations where women were approximately half of the nation's science majors and employed researchers. Results indicated robust relationships between women's representation in science and national gender-science stereotypes.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Wendy M. Williams, Stephen J. Ceci (2015) *STEM faculty prefer hiring women professors 2:1*, in “Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences”, 112, 17, 5360-5365.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Analysing gender preferences in hiring decision making. It is a propitious time for women launching careers in academic science. Messages to the contrary may discourage women from applying for STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) tenure-track assistant professorships.		National/USA	Biology, engineering, economics, and psychology	Women and men tenure-track faculty (assistant professor)	They participate to some experiments	The author report five hiring experiments in which faculty evaluated hypothetical female and male applicants, using systematically varied profiles disguising identical scholarship, for assistant professorships in biology, engineering, economics, and psychology. Contrary to prevailing assumptions, men and women faculty members from all four fields preferred female applicants.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

Carli LL, Alawa L, Lee Y, Zhao B, Kim E. (2016) *Stereotypes About Gender and Science: Women ≠ Scientists*, in “Psychology of Women Quarterly”, 40(2), 244-260.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	To examine the effect of stereotypes as potential obstacles to women in science and to assess the similarity between stereotypes about women and men and stereotypes about successful scientists.	Public	National/US A		Volunteers (women and men) recruited online through Mechanical Turk (MTurk) and undergraduates.	They answered to a questionnaire	A pre-test plus two studies with questionnaire. Women may be at a disadvantage in science because people hold different stereotypes about women than they do about men and successful scientists, particularly in scientific fields where women are less prevalent.	
	Exclusionary Dimension	The perceived relative lack of fit between the female gender role and the role of scientist may undermine people's evaluation of female scientists, who may be seen as overly communal, insufficiently agentic, or too passive to succeed in science. People should be aware of these potential biases and attempt to compensate for them in evaluating women and girls in STEM.							

Eric V. Patridge, Ramon Barthelemy, Susan R. Rankin (2013) *Factors Impacting the Academic Climate for Lgbq Stem Faculty*, in “Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering”, 75-98.

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	To assess the experiences of LGBQ faculty from science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines. The efforts to improve the retention of LGBT faculty need to address the climate; furthermore, reducing exclusionary behaviour could enhance retention and comfort. Authors propose some institutional/community strategies, as revising non-discrimination statement and the other policies; institutionalising diversity councils/centres.	Public	National/USA	STEM	279 LGBQ faculty members across multi-departments	Respondents	National survey. Findings show that several factors influence the academic climate and the careers in STEM departments: identity, climate and experiences have career consequences for LGBT faculty.	
	Exclusionary Dimension								

2.2.4. Results

We divided the articles in four categories: “Public perception, public engagement and participation in S&T and gender”; “the under-representation of women in STEM curricula”, “the under-representation of women in STEM careers” and “Gender, innovation and the feminist perspective”. In all these areas the articles treated the topic of “awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences” from different perspectives.

“Public perception, public engagement and participation in S&T and gender”

Some articles analyse the gender differences in the perception of science and technology, because women and men truly approach them in different ways, in particular health and biotechnology. Women have greater concerns about their safety while men are more comfortable with biotechnology, like genetically modified foods (Elder *et al.* 2018). Experiences, beliefs, and values – including the religious one (Taragin-Zeller *et al.* 2020) – impact women (and men) attitudes, especially when technologies concern the women’s body (Johnson and Simon 2012). Furthermore, the experiences of individuals in their everyday lives have the power to affect these attitudes toward science (Simon 2011).

Together with the public perception of science and technology another important topic is the public engagement and the participation in science by women and men. Studies show that cultural, social and political factors affect gender differences in participation. For instance, the gendered social distribution of both paid and unpaid labor shapes women’s and men’s agency and their capabilities to participate (Fraune 2015). Persistent gender differences and inequalities in science image and in scientific careers still emerge (Losh 2010) as a smaller women’s participation in science, even if this participation varies in relation to different aspects. In some specific contexts/professions (as the academic one), being female favours the participation in local community engagement activities compared to being male, while no gender difference was recorded for the involvement in other engagement activities (Anzivino *et al.* 2020). Furthermore, women are more oriented to promote a different role of the scientist and are less supportive of a positivistic view of science than men (Bren *et al.* 2010). In general, women and men share a positive vision of public outreach and engagement with no significant gender difference, but the practices can strongly differ, because of the intervention of other actors like (traditional and social) media. In fact, media contact women scientists less often than men scientists — and this independently of position, age, and faculty (Crettaz and von Roten 2011). In talk shows men experts outnumber women experts and the topics that the experts commented reflect familiar gender stereotypes with men more likely to talk about security and self-defence, politics and economy and women more often talk about body grooming and childcare (Hetstroni and Lowenstein 2014).

In this area, another topic concerns the image of the scientist in the collective imaginary. Scientists are now rarely objects of fear or mockery. Mathematicians, both real-life and fictional, are now depicted empathically (Haynes 2016) with “female characteristics”. However, in the last years, while women in science appear to be more accurately represented, there is still room for improvement in the representation of the scientist from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds (Mitchell 2019), especially in those countries in which some people still consider STEM fields suited to men. In this context, egalitarian attitudes toward gender roles can have a strong effect on the perceptions of women’s gender suitability for scientific roles (Ikkatai 2020).

“The under-representation of women in STEM curricula”

Studies show that different social factors affect STEM education attainment. Cognitive and social-psychological characteristics matter, as do structural influences at the family, neighbourhood, school, and broader cultural levels. Disparities by family income, race, and gender persist in STEM education (Xie *et al.* 2015; Wang *et al.* 2017). Privileges such as parental education and books at home are positively correlated with STEM aspirations (Liu 2020). High school curriculum in STEM and gender segregation of extracurricular activities influence the gender gap in STEM (Legewie 2014), as the role of media models of STEM professionals on adolescents (Steike 2017). As we underlined, the under-representation of women in STEM curricula is analysed starting from the process of socialization and the formation of gender stereotypes on academic abilities: children’s tendency to favor girls in verbal domains may contribute to gender differences in educational and career choices by pulling girls toward the humanities and social sciences and discouraging boys from pursuing those domains (Kurtz-Costes *et al.* 2014). The existence of gender bias produces STEM gender gaps (Starr 2018). When explicitly exposed to the reality of bias in the gender bias condition, women expected to experience less sense of belonging, positive attitudes, and aspirations to participate in STEM than did men. These gender differences were fully eliminated when participants were exposed to the idea of gender equality (Moss-Racusin *et al.* 2018). Furthermore, science aspirations are largely ‘unthinkable’ for girls when they do not fit with either their constructions of desirable/intelligible femininity nor with their sense of themselves as learners/students. This lack of fit is exacerbated by social inequalities (Archer *et al.* 2013). Studies show that not only are they discouraged in choosing science careers, but those were very interested in science, engineering, or medicine majors or careers decided to leave the pipeline in high school while others persisted. Different microclimates framed students’ perceptions of their study, abilities, career options, and expected success, thereby shaping their science identities and consequent STEM trajectories. In specific countries, gender interacting with ethnicity and socio-economic categories seemed to play a role in under-represented minority students’ aspirations and pipeline participation (Aschbacher *et al.* 2010). Furthermore, students from underrepresented groups are less likely to feel they belong (lack of social and personal connections with peers, lack of interest, poor grade, low performance), while students who remain in STEM majors report a greater sense of belonging than those who leave STEM. These findings highlight structural and cultural features of universities, as well as STEM curricula and pedagogy, that continue to privilege specific categories (men, white *etc.*). Furthermore, gender gaps in self-efficacy and masculine cultures influence the relationship between women and STEM (Cherian *et al.* 2017). STEM-related gender bias from classmates and sexual harassment from instructors (faculty, teaching assistants, or graduate students) were negatively related to STEM motivation and career aspirations. Perceived STEM encouragement from friends was positively related to motivation, and STEM encouragement from friends and family predicted STEM career aspirations (Leaper *et al.* 2019). Stereotypes affect women scientists too: for instance, a piece of research shows that women are outperforming men in both physical and life science courses at the same institution, while simultaneously continuing to be perceived as less-able students. So women may not be able to escape gender-ability stereotypes even when they are outperforming men (Bloodhart *et al.* 2020). Science educators could help weaken stereotypes by highlighting diverse examples of female scientists (Miller, Eagly and Linn 2015).

Overall, significant progress has been made with respect to girls’ participation in education in recent decades. There is a positive trend in terms of closing the gender gap in STEM-

related learning achievement in girls' favour, but significant regional variations exist. As with the data on participation, national and regional variations in data on learning achievement suggest the presence of contextual factors affecting girls' and women's engagement in these fields. The degree of gender equality in wider society influences girls' participation and performance in STEM. Gender stereotypes that communicate the idea that STEM studies and careers are male domains can negatively affect girls' interest, engagement and achievement in STEM and discourage them from pursuing STEM careers. Girls who assimilate such stereotypes have lower levels of self-efficacy and confidence in their ability than boys. Self-efficacy affects both STEM education outcomes and aspirations for STEM careers to a considerable extent. In countries with greater gender equality, girls tend to have more positive attitudes and confidence about mathematics and the gender gap in achievement in the subject is smaller (Unesco 2017).

"The under-representation of women in STEM careers"

This area is strictly linked to the previous one. Family formation and childrearing, gendered expectations, lifestyle choices, and career preferences have an impact on gender and STEM careers (Ceci and Williams 2011). First, different studies analyse the effect of stereotypes as potential obstacles to women in science (Carli *et al.* 2016) and their specific influence in the workplace and in the human resources management process. Bias against female researchers is particularly strong at the very early stage of a scientific career, potentially leading to an under-representation of women in research centres in the later stages of a scientific career (Checchi *et al.* 2019). Existing practices can produce gender gaps in recruitment, retention, and career progression and preclude gender parity (Thomas *et al.* 2015), with some exceptions (e.g. Williams, Ceci 2015). In the evaluation process when the evaluators know the gender of the applicants, male applicants might be valued higher than female one with a similar CV. This bias is based on the predisposition which connects masculinity to technology/science and professionalism, and that strengthens the evaluators' impression of male candidates' competence as superior (Tiainen and Berki 2019). This problem concerns also other fields like physics where gender biases favour male candidates considered as more competent and more hireable than the otherwise identical female ones (Eaton *et al.* 2020; Moss-Racusin *et al.* 2012). Objective information about past performance can attenuate sex-biased decision-making but failed to eliminate it, especially in employers who showed a stronger implicit sex bias (Reuben, Sapienza and Zingales 2014).

Stereotypes and discrimination are amplified in a context that lacks clear guidelines or regulations. Through their presentations, interactional styles, and the images they project, organisations convey a gendered sense of who will best fit in their culture. Their representatives often engage in behaviours that are known to create a chilly environment for women (Wynn *et al.* 2018). Furthermore, the male-dominated culture in STEM influences daily working practices and evidence suggests that exclusion from networks limits opportunities for women's career advancement (Xu and Martin 2011). A male-dominated culture, the presence of stereotypes applied to female STEM professionals in both academic and non-academic settings (McKinnon, O'Connell 2020) and the subtle forms of discrimination led women to feel discouraged or intimidated and push them to find ways to cope that typically reinforce their subordination (Bevan and Learmonth 2013); in this context they can consider the possibility to leave the organisation (Howe-Walsh and Turball 2016). In some countries, while recent gender policies have enabled female academics to develop robust careers, their contributions beyond the walls of the university remain limited because

of longstanding patriarchal structures, distrust in women's professional expertise and unchanged systemic constraints (Hirsu et al. 2021).

Studies highlight different strategies to better retain and promote women and LGBT+ community in STEM, as opening professional networks, realigning policy documents and departmental practices to better reflect faculty's values, improving departmental climates (Hardcastle *et al.* 2019; Patridge 2013), implementing mentorship programs to generate more supportive workplaces. Similarly, enhancing self-efficacy for public engagement improves the visibility of diverse female role models for young girls (Fogg-Rogers and Hobbs 2019); finally, sensibilizing men could help to reduce stereotypes and discrimination practices. Studies reveal diversity among men in their understandings about obstacles and challenges facing women in STEM. Most participants show gender blind perspectives and argue that the egalitarian structure of academia does not allow gender to impact attainments in STEM in any significant way. However, a considerable number of them felt privileged compared to women and described subtle ways in which gender shapes opportunities (Sattari and Sandefur 2018).

“Gender, innovation and the feminist perspective”

The articles of this thematic area analyse the relationship between gender/diversity and innovation. A recent study shows that the novel contributions of unrepresented groups are still devalued and discounted (Hofstra *et al.* 2020) and more profound mechanisms are necessary to generate institutional change beyond the confines of stereotyping: diversity paradoxically both crystallizes as a sign of an increasingly neoliberal academy, and signals as marker of social progress toward the inclusion of differently positioned actors (Jablonek *et al.* 2020). In this direction it is important to introduce gender analysis in research and education (European Union 2020) and to implement practices to promote the introduction of gender perspective in CV curricula (Miller *et al.* 2013).

We analysed the literature considering the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions (see paragraph 2.2.3). We sum-up the results in the table 2.3. In the first column we enumerate the general goals of the “awareness-raising actions”; in the second, we report the factors that still obstacle the process of inclusion of the disadvantage categories; in the third, we enumerate the different techniques used to carry out the research or the action-research.

Table 2.3 - Summary of the main awareness actions

Transformative	Exclusionary	Research techniques/ ways to engage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enhancing the participation and the engagement in science. ○ Designing an inclusive communication. ○ Supporting aspirations and interests of children/young people. ○ Designing a more inclusive teaching, showing different examples and models. ○ Strengthening the pipeline in academic careers and avoiding abandons. ○ Enhancing self-efficacy, role-models, self-confidence of girl/women. ○ Implementing organizational practices to avoid discrimination. ○ Implementing diversity initiatives and mentorship programs. ○ Defining clear procedures/guidelines to recruit and to evaluate candidates. ○ Training recruiters to avoid stereotypes and bias. ○ Implementing awareness campaign gender, LGBTQ+ and diversity. ○ Working on culture and gender/STEM fit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wealth and occupational gaps, ethnicity and education are variables that can obstacle the participation of women and other disadvantage categories to science. ○ Parents’ stereotypes and socialization can preclude the participation. ○ Curriculum and pedagogy activities can implicitly favor men. ○ Sexual harassment and micro-aggressive practices can inhibit the professional lives of disadvantages groups, together with a chilly environment, a patriarchal system and a gendered culture in the academy and organizations. ○ Less sense of belonging and unfit between gender and science identity can push away women. ○ Absence of policies and practices that monitor bias and discrimination in human resources management process exacerbate social exclusion. ○ Women exclusion from networks can slow down women’s careers. ○ The image of scientist as far from gender identity and other groups can increase stereotypes. ○ Low attention to other communities increases the gap between disadvantage groups and participation in science. 	<p>Surveys, interviews, focus groups, hiring experiments/lab experiments, longitudinal studies, statistical analysis, literature review.</p> <p>In these studies, prevail the use of interviews and surveys.</p>

2.3. Education

2.3.1. Overview

This section provides information regarding the literature review of on awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences (O4). With this aim, a systematic literature review has been conducted in Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases. In addition, grey literature has been searched to complete the task. This part includes the methodology followed in this literature review, with a focus on education, the analysis, the results obtained and the main conclusions.

2.3.2. Methodology

In the first phase, a literature review was conducted following the guidelines concerning the selection of the sources, the collection of the information and the analysis.

In the second phase, a categorization of the literature review was conducted following a specific grid to highlight the contribution of each study on the awareness-raising actions.

1) FIRST PHASE

The research team was advised and supported by the University of Helsinki's information and library service. Based on these discussions, the research team undertook its research using Scopus. Accordingly, the following keyword searches were employed for this topic:

- Science or technology and education and under-representation and recruitment
- Science or technology and education and “vulnerable groups” and recruitment
- Science or technology and under-representation and recruitment
- Science or technology and "vulnerable groups" and recruitment
- Science or technology and education and diversity and "business case"
- Science or technology and education and careers and success
- Science or technology and education and teaching and diversity
- Science or technology and education and “smart cities”

Based on these key words the following was undertaken:

- The literature review was conducted in English.
- The search involved both primary (abstract and title) and secondary (title) word search fields to limit the number of results.
- To refine the search research articles published over the 2010-2020 period and in the subject area of ‘social sciences’ were examined.
- The articles were prioritised according to the number of citations.
- All the abstracts for the keyword searches were assessed and if considered relevant the entire article was assessed and summarised.
- A total of 147 articles were reviewed of which 43 were considered relevant and summarised in the report.

It is important to note that this literature review list of evidence does not involve an analysis of the findings; instead, the focus is on ensuring the literature review list of evidence supports the deliverables and milestones in subsequent work packages.

Each article was analysed as the follow (see the document “Literature review” uploaded in the ALLINTERACT workspace by Helsinki):

Key word search	Science or technology and under-representation and recruitment
Reference	Gender in Science and Engineering Faculties: Demographic Inertia Revisited Thomas, Nicole R; Poole, Daniel J; Herbers, Joan M; Amaral, Luís A Nunes. ISSN: 1932-6203, 1932-6203; DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0139767 PloS one, 2015, Vol.10(10), p.e0139767
Aim	The under-representation of women on faculties of science and engineering is ascribed in part to demographic inertia, which is the lag between retirement of current faculty and future hires. The assumption of demographic inertia implies that, given enough time, gender parity will be achieved.
Participants/target	Women in science
Geography	US
Methodology	Examine that assumption via a semi-Markov model to predict the future faculty, with simulations that predict the convergence demographic state. Model shows that existing practices that produce gender gaps in recruitment, retention, and career progression preclude eventual gender parity. Further examine sensitivity of the convergence state to current gender gaps to show that all sources of disparity across the entire faculty career must be erased to produce parity: cannot blame demographic inertia.
Findings	Together, the gender gaps in recruitment, retention, and promotion suggested that demographic inertia was not solely responsible for the under-representation of women on the STEM faculty
Conclusions	Demographic inertia predicts that despite vigorous hiring, many years will be needed to allow for retiring men to be replaced by women. The assumption of inertia has placed a spotlight on recruitment of women into junior positions. Demographic inertia may partially explain women’s under-representation in the short term, but over the long term achieving

	<p>the goal of gender parity will require substantial changes also to existing patterns of retention, and career progression. This particular institution has put many policies in place to address root causes of disparity, and enriching the applicant pool is a key strategy to achieving a faculty with equal representation of women. Yet retention and post-tenure promotion to Professor remain problematic; changing those patterns will require structural and/or cultural change to provide environments that allow everyone to succeed. Achieving gender parity among STEM faculty, which requires equalizing career progression for men and women across their entire careers, depends on addressing all the environmental factors that impede career progression.</p>
--	---

2) SECOND PHASE

In this phase the findings for O4 (literature review) were organised following the table 2.4. It classifies every action presented in the article analysing it on the basis of:

- a) the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the implementation of the targeted actions);
- b) the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the implementation of the targeted actions).

Table 2.4 - Exclusionary and transformative dimensions grid

O4) Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge								
Article	<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Transformative Dimension								
Exclusionary Dimension								

2.3.3. Analysis

INCREASING ACHIEVEMENT AND HIGHER-EDUCATION REPRESENTATION OF UNDER-REPRESENTED GROUPS IN SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, AND MATHEMATICS FIELDS: A REVIEW OF CURRENT K-12 INTERVENTION PROGRAMS Valla, Jeffrey M; Williams, Wendy M									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Increasing the representation of women and ethnic minorities in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education and careers has been a goal of education researchers for nearly half a century.	Public/Private	International	Review of STEM programmes	Programme delivery with particular focus on teachers	Review prototypical designs of these programs, highlighting specific programs in the literature as examples of program structures and components currently in use.	Future STEM program designers can use this organizational scheme to tailor a program to the unique developmental needs of a given target population and resources available, based on an analysis of component combination effectiveness reported by past programs.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	The most important improvements that can be made are in the evaluation of programs.							

[Which are my Future Career Priorities and What Influenced my Choice of Studying Science, Technology, Engineering or Mathematics? Some Insights on Educational Choice—Case of Slovenia](#) Cerinsek, Gregor; Hribar, Tina; Glodez, Natasa; Dolinsek, Slavko

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Present to young people a range of different possibilities available in science careers, especially, in order to attract more females, those careers that are more people/health/society oriented. Furthermore, to achieve better gender balance, STEM subjects and courses should be more closely focused to real world/contextual and social relevance, e.g. demonstrating how science can contribute to society and environment, since females are attracted to these issues significantly more than their male counterparts.	Public	National (Slovenia)	Teacher training	STEM students	Focus on main objectives: (1) to identify which priorities male and female STEM students in Slovenia seek in their future careers, and (2) to identify different important factors (i.e. key persons, previous school and out-of-school experiences) that influenced their choice of studying STEM.	The main data collection method was a questionnaire developed within the Interests and Recruitment in Science project group. The sample consisted of 861 males and 420 female undergraduate STEM students towards the end of their first year of higher education and this represented 60.8% of the whole target population. For data analysis, basic descriptive statistics with one-way analysis of variance was used.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Gender-role socialization with commonly held stereotypes about gender differences lead females and males to develop different hierarchies of their core personal values, interests and priorities that ultimately form their identities. The cultural milieu suggests which subjects/activities/careers go with which identity.							

The re-production process of gender bias: a case of ICT professors through recruitment in a gender-neutral country Tiainen, Tarja; Berki, Eleni									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Focus on the discrepancy in the recruitment policy and subsequent recruitment process.	University	Local (Finland)	University recruitment	University staff	Analysis of the case School outlines that there is no gender equality; for example, the statistics of PhDs and staff members in different kind of posts state the obvious biases.	The framework's context captures occupational retention for women in ICT workforce. It includes four contexts: individual, organisational, professional and environmental.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Besides getting access to the scientific community and feel included, there are also problems for female scientists to get admission to their home universities. In University research centres, women are younger, less likely to be tenured, and at a remarkably lower rank than their male colleagues.							

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Women have made significant progress in developing their interest and capabilities in STEM education. Women are still under-represented in science, applied science, medicine and more so in the technical stream. In 1995, women earned only 16.3% of the engineering undergraduate degrees, while the proportion of degrees conferred to women in soft sciences – science, mathematics and computer majors, was slightly more than half.	Public	National (Malaysia)	STEM	Women students at university	Focus on measuring the magnitude of gender disparity in tertiary education consider the percentage of total degrees awarded to women for a specific major.	Using data provided by the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education, our results suggest that under-representation of women in engineering was attributed to low recruitment at the point of entry.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	The challenge is that when STEM education is left to be segregated according to one's sex, the segregation is likely to cause a societal challenge at the subsequent workplace.							

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promotin & organiza tion (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The role of health practitioners and health-care services and systems are important, given the differential levels of care and interventions that Indigenous people receive when they attend for health-care advice.	Public	Regional (Australia)	Healthcare training	Indigenous Australians	Developing recruitment and retention strategies that meaningfully address the significant under-representation of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people in the medical and broader health professions.	Overview of the long-term strategies that have been in place at the University of Western Australia, which aim to build the capacity and preparedness of the health-care workforce in Aboriginal health. In 1996, the Centre for Aboriginal Medical and Dental Health was established within the Faculty of Medicine, Dentistry and Health Sciences to implement a comprehensive approach to Aboriginal health.	Having a Centre that is Aboriginal led with the majority of the staff being Aboriginal health practitioners has been essential in the growth and relevance of the teaching content as well as ensuring the cultural context and safety of the student support provided.
	Exclusionary Dimension	Racism, both overt and institutional, is traumatic, and both tiring and emotionally draining for staff and students, highlighting the importance of comprehensive across institution anti-racism strategies. Added to this is having to regularly deal with new staff, which often leads to revisiting old stories/arguments. Comprehensive Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander culture and health orientation programmes for new and existing staff would help overcome the issues here.							

Computing and STEM in Greece: Gender representation of students and teachers during the decade 2002/2012 Kordaki, Maria; Berdousis, Ioannis									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The results of this study may be the starting point for Greek Computing teachers to rethink their beliefs and practices concerning classroom teaching approaches so that they might cater for both boys and girls.	Public/Private	National (Greece)	IT	HE students in IT and computing	This study focuses on the investigation of gender representation of tertiary-level education students (freshmen, graduates, master's degree graduates and PhD's) and of secondarylevel education teachers in Computing and STEM education during the decade 2002– 2012 in Greece.	A quantitative study was conducted taking into account appropriate data that emerged from the Hellenic Statistical Authority which is the national statistical service of Greece	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	It seems that the main problem is recruitment and not retention in Computing and STEM, despite female under-representation in most of these disciplines.							

[Responses to a Theoretically Adapted Clinical Trial Education Session: Faith-Based Sites Versus Rural Work Site Dissemination](#) Aumiller, Betsy B; Parrott, Roxanne; Lengerich, Eugene J; Dominic, Oralia; Camacho, Fabian; Lehman, Eric; Gallant, Nancy R; Loughran, Thomas P

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Need to be aware of including adults' self-directed learning style, use of life experience as a resource for learning, linking social role and emotional needs to learning, immediate application of knowledge to solve problems, and internal rather than external motivation.	Public/Private	Local (US)	Healthcare	Cancer patients	The process for advancing biomedical knowledge depends upon recruiting an adequate and representative sample of individuals to voluntarily participate in research studies.	From eight focus groups with 90 participants, church leaders, congregants, and community members were receptive to education on cancer research, increased their short-term knowledge about it, and intent to participate in cancer studies, decreased their current anxiety about clinical trials participation, and provided specific suggestions for further adapting the educational session to be even more culturally relevant.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	A consistent personal barrier to cancer clinical trial participation is the lack of awareness and understanding related to trial availability, and the prevention and treatment roles participation represents. In particular, comprehensive community-based approaches to recruit and educate rural residents are needed.							

Analysis of instruments focused on gender gap in STEM education Verdugo-Castro, Sonia; García-Holgado, Alicia; Sánchez-Gómez, M ^a Cruz									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Deepen the motivations of people to choose their studies. Knowing this is important because of its relationship with the objectives established when it comes to studying. In order to identify this, instruments such as those addressed are constructed.	Public/private	National (Spain)	Public interest in science	Women and minority ethnic	Review	An instrument search was carried out using the databases Scopus, Web of Science, Dialnet and Google Scholar. The review was developed using different search terms and formulas, both in English and Spanish. The terms used and combined were: "questionnaire", "survey" and "gender gap", "segregation", "minorities", "women" and "STEM", "science", "technology", "engineering", "mathematics", "tertiary education", "higher education".	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	This under-representation becomes evident as the academic and professional scale progresses, making representation figures smaller at higher levels. This is due to the existence of stereotypes about the presence in the technological and scientific sector.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

[Gender in Science and Engineering Faculties: Demographic Inertia Revisited](#) Thomas, Nicole R; Poole, Daniel J; Herbers, Joan M; Amaral, Luís A Nunes

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Achieving gender parity among STEM faculty, which requires equalizing career progression for men and women across their entire careers, depends on addressing all the environmental factors that impede career progression.	University	Local (US)	STEM recruitment	Gender gaps in recruitment, retention, and	Examine sensitivity of the convergence state to current gender gaps to show that all sources of disparity across the entire faculty career must be erased to produce parity: cannot blame demographic inertia.	Examine that assumption via a semi-Markov model to predict the future faculty, with simulations that predict the convergence demographic state.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	The under-representation of women on faculties of science and engineering is ascribed in part to demographic inertia, which is the lag between retirement of current faculty and future hires.							

[Gendered Interests in Electrical, Computer, and Biomedical Engineering: Intersections With Career Outcome Expectations](#)

Potvin, Geoff; McGough, Catherine; Benson, Lisa; Boone, Hank J; Doyle, Jacqueline; Godwin, Allison; Kirn, Adam; Ma, Beverly; Rohde, Jacqueline; Ross, Monique; Verdin, Dina

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	These results suggest that a potential path to improved participation of women in electrical and computer engineering may be to recruit participants through an emphasis on the communal or relational importance of these domains.	Public/Private	National (US)	Engineering	Computer engineering students	Recruit participants through an emphasis on the communal or relational importance of these domains.	Regression analyses were conducted on multiply-imputed data of introductory engineering students at four public universities in the U.S.	Female identified students report stronger associations between “helping others” and interest in bioengineering/biomedical engineering than non-females.
	Exclusionary Dimension	The results provide evidence that incoming engineering students have particular associations between their expectations for their career (interests in achieving certain outcomes) and their interests in electrical, computer, and bioengineering/biomedical engineering, and that gender plays a significant but distinct role in each case.							

[Catch 22 — improving visibility of women in science and engineering for both recruitment and retention](#) Fogg-Rogers, Laura; Hobbs, Laura

	<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>	
Article	Transformative Dimension	There is a significant under-representation of women in STEM which is damaging societal progress for democratic, utilitarian, and equity reasons. However, changing stereotypes in STEM requires a solution denied by the problem — more visible female role models.	University	Local (UK)	STEM	Women and students	Providing training for women scientists and engineers in education outreach, along with supported opportunities for public engagement, is essential to improve self-efficacy for education outreach.	In total, 52 professional female engineers working in industry or research in the West of England region were trained in public engagement and outreach ('junior' engineers with ≤5 years' experience, N=26) and mentoring ('senior' engineers with 5–32 years' experience, N=26). Junior engineers carried out a target of three education outreach activities each, with senior engineers providing at least two mentoring sessions to the junior engineer with whom they were paired through the scheme.	Science communication can present a different perspective on the culture of science and identity traits of scientists, and is therefore a critical profession for making a difference to the employment of women in STEM and a more equitable society.
	Exclusionary Dimension	The social value placed on STEM subjects being competitive, logical, and individualistic (which are not necessarily true) are perceived to be contradictory to the feminine gender identity traits of communality, nurturing, and sociality.							

Rethinking religious under-representation in science R.L. Bertrand									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Hypothesize that several sociopsychological mechanisms of social bias potentiate discrimination within the scientific institution, favouring non-religious candidates in recruitment into the scientific role as well as during subsequent career advancement.	Public/Private	International	Recruitment	Scientists	Review	Need data on a broad set of individuals within the scientific role, including graduate students, post-doctoral fellows, researchers, and academic faculty, ideally collected throughout their developing scientific careers.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	It has been traditionally assumed that low religious turnout in science is a consequence of epistemological conflicts between religion and science dissuading religious affiliates from pursuing scientific careers. The potential contribution of the scientific institution itself (and its social practices), however, has been seldom questioned as a contributing factor.							

[Reaching the hard-to-reach: a systematic review of strategies for improving health and medical research with socially disadvantaged groups](#) Bonevski, Billie; Randell, Madeleine; Paul, Chris; Chapman, Kathy; Twyman, Laura; Bryant, Jamie; Brozek, Irena; Hughes, Clare

	<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>	
Article	Transformative Dimension	To tackle the challenges of research with socially disadvantaged groups, and increase their representation in health and medical research, researchers and research institutions need to acknowledge extended timeframes, plan for higher resourcing costs and operate via community partnerships.	Public/Private	International	Medical/health	Researchers	A systematic review with narrative synthesis was conducted. Searches of electronic databases Medline, PsychInfo, EMBASE, Social Science Index via Web of Knowledge and CINHAL were conducted for English language articles published up to May 2013.	review the literature regarding the barriers to sampling, recruitment, participation, and retention of members of socioeconomically disadvantaged groups in health research and strategies for increasing the amount of health research conducted with socially disadvantaged groups.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Most studies of strategies to address the barriers were of a descriptive nature and only nine studies reported the results of randomised trials.							

Agentic Pathways Toward Fulfillment in Work									
Keller, Anita C; Samuel, Robin; Bergman, Manfred Max; Semmer, Norbert K; Mortimer, Jeylan T; Vuolo, Mike; Staff, Jeremy									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The three dimensions of agentic striving of interest in this study (i.e., educational aspirations, career goal certainty, and job search behavior), while often studied singly, are clearly intertwined.	Public	Local (US)	Vocational	Young people	From 1989 to 2005, respondents completed up to 15 follow-up surveys tapping educational and occupational plans and attainments, behavioral and psychosocial adjustment, relationship formation, civic engagement, and experiences in work, school, and family. By 2005 (the 16th wave of data collection), when most respondents were 31 and 32 years old, 71 % of the initial participants had been retained.	The ongoing Youth Development Study is a prospective longitudinal study of 1,010 individuals randomly drawn in 1988 from of all ninth graders enrolled in the St. Paul Public School District in Minnesota.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Agentic striving in the post-high school period matters both for long-term occupational attainment and for contemporary youth's capacity to obtain high quality adult work experiences.							

Carrots or Sticks? A Study on Incentives to Attract and Retain Women in Science, Engineering and Technology in South Africa Thege, Britta; Popescu-Willigmann, Silvester; Pioch, Roswitha; Badri-Höher, Sabah; Salo, Elaine R; Liersch, Felix; Mohlakoana-Motopi, Lieketseng; Maree, Marinda									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Incentives can be used to attract and retain women and, subsequently, enable them to re-enter the diverse fields of Science, Engineering and Technology (SET) in South Africa.	Public	National (South Africa)	SET/STEM	Women	This recruitment process has to be well planned over the short and long term using multiple strategies. In the short term, women who possess already suite of requisite skills are targeted while junior women who are recruited or employed within the company are mentored to acquire these skills.	This study interviewed 45 interviewees located within corporate institutions, government ministries in SET as well as in SET fields in tertiary institutions. The study contributes to a small but growing body of research in the field of women and gender in SET in South Africa and sheds some light on the gendered features of education and the workplace that enable or alienate women in this field.	Those respondents who said that they saw an improvement in the representation of women in their particular sectors were from parastatals or public universities.
	Exclusionary Dimension	The recruitment of women and particularly of black women is only one part of the solution to gendering the workplace – new recruits especially from excluded groups would continue to experience a qualitative sense of exclusion.							

Theoretically and Practically Speaking, What is Needed in Diversity and Equity in Science Teaching and Learning? Mensah, Felicia Moore									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Multicultural education “represents a way of rethinking school reform because it responds to many of the problematic factors leading to school underachievement and failure” for diverse learners.	Public/Private	National (US)	Science teachers	Diverse students	Experiential approach adopted by case study teacher	Highlighting examples from my own teaching and research and other studies in education, Frame in terms of a broad application of theory in science teacher preparation to classroom practices in order to address science achievement and equity for diverse students. Also discuss the relevance of my argument for in-service professional development.	Efforts to transform one’s minds and challenge one’s thinking about what it means to teach more effectively students who are being underserved in their education.
	Exclusionary Dimension	The ability of preservice and in-service teachers to draw upon various theories and principles of equitable teaching, not just in science but also in other subject areas, entails understanding student culture and learning how to balance the when, how, what, and why of putting into practice theoretical perspectives that promote student learning.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Diversity and credibility in young People's news feeds: A foundation for teaching and learning citizenship in a digital era T. Nygren									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	In education, students' news feeds can be used to scrutinize credibility and help students navigate towards credible news domains to support democratic engagement.	Public	National (Sweden)	Student social media	School students	The students' news feeds primarily contain hard news from established news media.	Using citizen science and a mixed methods approach we review 2617 news from authentic news feeds.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Education can stimulate democratic discussions starting in credible information. But students also need to pay attention to biases.							

Actors and act-ers: Enhancing inclusion and diversity in teaching and teacher education through the validation of quiet teaching Collins, Steve; Ting, Hermia

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Encouraging individual student teachers to identify their strengths and to reflect on how these can best be incorporated into their teaching will lead to an optimal and effective teaching style.	Public/Private	National (Canada)	Teacher training	Training involved in teacher training were engaged with to maximize the potential in their student teachers by focusing on and developing their strengths rather than risking frustration and discouragement by over stressing areas of weakness.	Gain insights from those with “quiet voices”, that is, the student teachers, teachers, administrators, and teacher educators themselves who have addressed their own issues of quietness within the context of teaching.	Examine the pertinent literature to provide a perspective in which we can frame our revision of the conception of the "introverted" student teacher and the responsibilities of Teacher Education to them.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Changes in the environment outside of us makes changes to our internal feelings and thoughts that adjust our interaction strategies in particular situations.							

Teaching and Learning About Sexual Diversity Within Medical Education: the Promises and Pitfalls of the Informal Curriculum Murphy, Marie									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Beyond adding to our understanding of how marginalization of sexual minorities occurs within the informal cultural milieu of medical education, this research also demonstrates that the informal curriculum is a site where much learning about sexual diversity is possible.	Public/private	Local (US)	Medicine	LGBT medical students	Engage with students to understand aspect of medical education has the potential to be a very powerful form of curriculum concerning sexual diversity.	Ethnographic study of the processes by which teaching and learning about sexuality were accomplished at Buena Vista Medical School, a top 20 medical school in the USA	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Even where robust non discrimination policies are in place, they alone may not be enough to foster an environment in which sexual minority persons feel that it is safe to disclose their identities.							

Race, multiculturalisms and the role of science in teaching diversity: towards a critical post-modern science pedagogy Ash, Anthony; Wiggan, Greg									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Recognizing the need for an interpretive and inclusive approach for teaching about diversity issues in teacher education, the article attempts to reposition science as being central to diversity education.	Public/Private	International	STEM fields	Potential teachers	Work towards preparing a scientifically literate workforce, a growing body of literature on science education and student diversity is emerging.	Substantive critical theories emancipate the individual by explaining shortcomings of the present; locating areas for social transformation; and advising practical means for doing so.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Increasingly diverse student populations must contend with a demographically homogenous teacher force that is largely unprepared to teach them. Moreover, research on using science to teach about diversity in educational settings is sparse.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

[Teaching Diversity, Becoming Inclusive: Perspectives and Possibilities in ASEAN Library and Information Science Schools](#)

Maestro, Roselle S; Ramos-Eclevia, Marian; Eclevia, Carlos L; Fredeluces, John Christopherson LT

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Results indicate that cultural competence is relevant to the practice of librarianship.	Public	National (ASEAN countries)	Libraries	Library studies students	LIS students may develop their cultural competence through personal experience by engaging in library internship with all library types, community immersion and collaborative group work with diverse members.	This study used a mix of qualitative survey research and content analysis of LIS course offerings.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	ASEAN LIS education is inadequate in terms of integration of diversity and inclusion in core courses.							

Panel ACM SIGCSE Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education Seattle, Wash.) 2017 :									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Several aspects of the TIDES Initiative could be replicated by faculty interested in institutional change: an interdisciplinary team with administrative support, a supportive community beyond the institution to exchange ideas as the projects ran into resistance, and expert advice on cultural competence, effective evaluation measures, and institutional change.	Public	National (US)	Computing	three-year initiative in 2014 to support and mentor faculty teams at twenty institutions as they developed new curriculum and/or adopted culturally sensitive pedagogies to better support the learning and retention of all students, especially female students and students traditionally ally underrepresented in computing.	The four panelists will each speak about their TIDES projects, which all involved educating faculty about cultural competency.	TIDES (Teaching to Increase Diversity and Equity in STEM) is a three-year initiative to transform colleges and universities by changing what STEM faculty, especially CS instructors, are doing in the classroom to encourage the success of their students, particularly those that have been traditionally underrepresented in computer science.	Experts in cultural competence and institutional change served as coaches to each project, providing individualized guidance on how to overcome challenges and how to assess the projects so they might serve as models for other institutions.
	Exclusionary Dimension	Mindsets, and meaningful ways of measuring change.							

Smart cities and attracting knowledge workers: Which cities attract highly-educated workers in the 21st century? Betz, Michael R; Partridge, Mark D; Fallah, Belal									
		Aim of the enhancing/ participation action	Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)	Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)	Field of intervention	Participants (targeted and real)	Type of participation (role of the participants)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social Impact
Article	Transformative Dimension	Highly-educated workers are a strongly sought after commodity and are often the focus of policy interventions to enhance local economic development.	Public	National (US)	Economic development	Planners	Regional policy-makers have long sought to attract highly-educated workers with a view to stimulating economic growth and vibrancy.	Use detailed 4-digit NAICS industry employment data combined with public micro-data to construct measures of industry skill upgrading and changes in industry composition to control for their effects on human capital growth.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Important changes in industry education levels and overall industry composition that may influence city-level college graduate growth.							

Educating the smart city: Schooling smart citizens through computational urbanism Williamson, Ben

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	School as a 'data platform' where the realtime 'datafication' of the individual is becoming the 'cornerstone of a big-data ecosystem' and in which 'educational materials will be algorithmically customized' and 'constantly improved'.	Public	National (UK)	School infrastructure	Planners and policy-makers	two interrelated dimensions of an emerging smart schools imaginary: (1) the constant flows of digital data that smart schools depend on and the mobilization of analytics that enable student data to be used to anticipate and shape their behaviours; and (2) the ways that young people are educated to become 'computational operatives' who must 'learn to code' in order to become 'smart citizens' in the governance of the smart city.	Current and emerging developments around schooling in smart cities as a particular social and technical instantiation of the contemporary fascination with big data that might itself play a role in 'the formation of other social, political and cultural developments of different types'.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Aspirations of technical experts to govern the city at a distance through both monitoring young people as 'data objects' and schooling them as active 'computational citizens' with the responsibility to compute the future of the city.							

		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Attitude is an individuals' psychological evaluation about an object and is widely considered to consist of three key components; the cognitive component comprised of belief or knowledge about the object, the affective component comprised of feeling about the object and the behavioural component comprised of actions taken towards the object.	Public	National (UK)	ICT/Mooc	Learners	A high proportion of the learners (89%) reported they were participating in at least one smart city activity after studying the course.	A mixed methods research design was employed, collecting data via an online survey that was completed by 202 learners and through in-depth interviews with 8 of those learners.	The results show that learners' perceived high levels of attitudinal learning on the topic of smart cities across four categories of learning outcomes (general, cognitive, affective and behavioural).
	Exclusionary Dimension	The aim of the Smart Cities MOOC is to support citizens to engage in smart city initiatives, a critical perspective is that such initiatives try to make people fit with technological requirements of smart cities rather than empowering them to participate.							

Editorial: Smart cities of the future: Creating tomorrow's education toward effective skills and career development today F. Klett									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Cities are growing and increasingly suffering from rapid urbanization quickly taking pace with approximately 60% of the world population residing in urban and sub-urban regions, and demographic change. In addition, governments progressively experience pressure toward a need for a sustainable economy, which results in a need for a qualified and retaining competitive workforce.	Public/Private	International	Planning and ICT	Students	The important role of Multiple choice questions (MCQs) in educational assessment and active learning toward enhancing the conceptual understanding of the students.	Literature review	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Some researchers identify the level of human capital that the city's inhabitants possess as a smartness rank criterion for cities							

Building a typology of the 100 smart cities in India									
Praharaj, Sarbeswar; Han, Hoon									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom- up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The KPIs around education, health and social services emerged from the analysis as the most significant drivers in the urban typology building process.	Public	National (India)	Planning/ICT	Policy-makers	Five projects for education and health sector have found a place in the proposals by the 33 cities that received funding at the initial stages of the SCM.	A two-stage statistical process is employed in this typology building exercise – first, a cluster analysis is conducted to classify the selected cities, then a multiple discriminant analysis is used to characterise each classified city.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	The lack of basic community infrastructure, especially in the small-to-medium-sized cities in India, exposes the shortcomings of a one-size-fits-all technocratic smart city development strategy that assumes foundational infrastructure is already in place for technology to take effect.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

An Exploration of “Hyper-Local” Community-University Engagement in the Development of Smart Cities Leigh, Elaine W									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Situate higher education anchor engagement practices into a broader debate on data, technology, and metropolitan social policies to honor complexity in community engagement and identify relevant actors and ideas necessary to rethink equity and representation in such partnerships as the urban landscape continues to change.	University	National (US)	Planning/ICT	Planners	Since 2010, IBM has run the Smarter Cities Challenge, providing technical expertise to over 132 cities globally on using their data analytics tools to drive data-driven solutions for urban governance	Critical geography and participatory GIS studies, urban planning, science and technology studies, computer science and engineering, higher education, and public policy circles need to be in more complete conversation to fully incorporate community-university engagement in this ecosystem and better understand the levers available inside and outside the university to more intentionally engage in local areas.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Tensions in the narratives of civic engagement and democratic practice for community well-being are juxtaposed with tensions in the smart citizen narrative implied by the idealized smart city design.							

Validation of the Smart City as a Sustainable Development Knowledge Tool: The Challenge of Using Technologies in Education during COVID-19 Olmos-Gómez, María del Carmen; Luque-Suárez, Mónica; Mohamed-Mohamed, Soraya; Cuevas-Rincón, Jesús Manuel									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, which is an unprecedented situation for all sectors of society and for education in particular (the subject addressed in this study), face-to-face classes have been urgently adapted to a remote format.	Public	National (Spain)	Teacher training	Teachers	Teachers creating a Smart Learning Environment where the subjects evaluated consider that they make good use of online video portals.	The questionnaire were analyzed through structural equation modeling (SEM), and the model was adjusted through a multivariate regression analysis to relate response patterns to a set of latent factors that cannot be directly observed, but exist in continuous dimensions of the people evaluated, and to create a valid and reliable instrument as a measurement tool using a sample of n = 973 subjects. The sample distribution consisted of 22.36% primary school teachers, 59.01% high school teachers, and 18.56% university teachers.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	The use of new technologies requires that teachers have knowledge, skills, and attitudes that empower them to take advantage of and apply information and communication technologies in the educational process.							

Gamification and citizen motivation and vitality in smart cities: a qualitative meta-analysis study Latifi, Gholam Reza; Monfared, Masoumeh Poor; Khojasteh, Hasan Abdi									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Results showed that gamification has implications in education, e-learning, commerce management, citizen participation, and motivation. The findings can be used by urban planners to provide citizens with playgrounds to play different games.	Public/Private	International	Gaming/ICT/e-learning	Gamers	74 papers which were relevant to the impact of gamification were analyzed.	Different electrical database sources, including Google Scholar, Academia, Linked-in, Research gate, etc. were searched for the keywords: gamification, gamification implication, gamified* participation, etc. The data of the study were synthesized thorough qualitative meta-analysis.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Gratitude and reward systems, which are parts of gamification, make people engage with what they are doing and increase their communication with others.							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Building a Workforce for Smart City Governance: Challenges and Opportunities for the Planning and Administrative Professions David; McNutt									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The growth of smart cities and collateral movements offer new and exciting possibilities for the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) for service delivery, civic engagement, and governance.	Public	National (US)	Planning	Teachers of urban planning	While engineers and scientists will create the technology, there are skills that go beyond what these disciplines can accomplish.	Planners would have to understand how technology impacts the built environment.	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Challenge for professional education to provide a supporting infrastructure that trains urban planners and public administrators for smart city governance in the 21st century.							

Smart education in smart city and student model									
M. Dumancic									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local / national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	The development of Smart Cities demands special attention directed towards the education of each individual by offering him lifelong learning, development of abilities and smart skills.	Public	National (Romania)	Teaching of ICT	Teachers	Quality implementation of all of these elements will not be possible within the existing models if there is no active student model.	Literature review	N/A
	Exclusionary Dimension	Today's education and its organization and implementation are not sufficient for the future of smart cities.							

Promoting Sustainability: The Role of Smart Cities Venkatesan, Madhavi; Azeiteiro, UM; AKERMAN, M; Leal Filho, W; Setti, AFF; Brandli, LL									
		<i>Aim of the enhancing/ participation action</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local /national/ international; bottom-up/ top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Type of participation (role of the participants)</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension	Smart cities provide infrastructure to support both conscious and unconscious sustainable consumption.	Public	National (India)	Planning/ICT	Planners	Smart city would employ available means to promote both holistic efficiency and risk management, thereby implicitly incorporating sustainability as the cultural paradigm of its inhabitants.	The assessment provided differs from other research and evaluation in this area, as it does not view the standard consumer model as the basis for smart city economic development (smart economic development).	Members of a society have to be both empowered and cognizant of the need for this type of evaluation in order for efficiency and ultimately sustainability to be a realized inter- and intra-generational attribute.
	Exclusionary Dimension	Like progress, smart city does not have a universal or standard definition							

2.3.4. Results

The articles were divided in the following categories: “Science or technology and education and under-representation and recruitment”; “Science or technology and vulnerable groups and recruitment”; “Science or technology and education and careers and success”; “Science or technology and education and teaching and diversity”; “Science or technology and education and smart cities”.

“Science or technology and education and under-representation and recruitment, careers and success

Research shows that early socialization and achievement experiences of women, girls, and ethnic minorities can have a substantial impact, positive or negative, on students’ decisions to pursue and persist in science careers (Valla and Williams 2012). Gender-role socialization with commonly held stereotypes about gender differences lead females and males to develop different hierarchies of their core personal values, interests and priorities that ultimately form their identities (Keller *et al.* 2014). Gender stereotypes, stereotyped roles and biases are internalized as they grow up and reach adolescences. This leads to decreasing numbers for minority groups and women in STEM courses and in the academic careers (Verdugo-Castro *et al.* 2019).

The under-representation of women on faculties of science and engineering is ascribed in part to demographic inertia, which is the lag between retirement of current faculty and future hires. The assumption of demographic inertia implies that, given enough time, gender parity will be achieved. Demographic inertia may partially explain women’s under-representation in the short term, but over the long-term achieving the goal of gender parity will require substantial changes to existing patterns of retention and career progression practices (Thomas *et al.* 2015), also using incentives (Thege *et al.* 2015). In fact, women continue to be under-represented in STEM faculty/professions, in particular in Engineering and Computer Science (Goy *et al.* 2018; Tiainen and Berki 2019). Even in the era of “internet and social media” -- where more women than men are online and use these media every day -- they are still under-represented (Kordaki, Berdousis, 2017). This situation concerns not only women but other minorities, as the religious one (Bertrand 2013). In this context, science communication can present different perspectives on the culture of science and on the identity traits of the scientists; it is therefore a critical profession for making a difference to the recruiting of minorities in STEM (Fogg-Rogers and Hobbs 2019).

Educators have recognized the potential benefits of providing early, positive STEM socialization, even if key persons in the socialization were not considered by STEM students as having an important direct influence on their educational choices. Present to young people a range of different possibilities available in science careers, especially, in order to attract more females, is considered central to recruit young people for STEM careers. Furthermore, to achieve better gender balance, STEM subjects and courses should be more closely focused to real world and social relevant, e.g. demonstrating how science can contribute to society

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

and environment, since females are attracted to these issues significantly more than their male counterparts (Cerinsek *et al.* 2013; Potvin *et al.* 2018). Furthermore, it is important to connect education and research to different types of communities (rural, religious *etc.*) in order to fill the gap between science and minorities (Aumiller *et al.* 2013, Paul 2013) and to know all the factors that obstacle the involvement of socioeconomically disadvantaged groups in specific domains (Bonevski *et al.* 2014).

“Science or technology and education and teaching and diversity”

Different authors reflected about teaching diversity at school and university, in particular in multicultural contexts. This means knowing the pedagogy in teaching subject matter to students with different backgrounds; working on the awareness of students' identities and their cultures; including multiple perspectives in the classroom to enhance student learning; implementing diverse assessments and tools to capture students' understandings of the content (Mensah 2013). Teaching cultural competences and diversity is a lifelong learning process of understanding and appreciating cultural similarities and differences (Maestro *et al.* 2018). It is important also to prepare students to recognise different information and sources presented with different perspectives and to understand the potential bias of the different types of news/contents (Nigren 2019). Teaching diversity and inclusion means also to increase students' capacity to interact respectfully and effectively with different people in specific contexts (for instance, in the medical context between medical students and different patients): indeed, robust non-discrimination policies alone may not be enough to foster an environment in which minorities feel that it is safe to disclose their identities (Murphy 2019). Research suggests that teachers' pedagogical contents knowledge and cultural understandings are central to effective teaching and high levels of students' achievement. Virtually absent among these debates are the implications for the role of science in promoting meaningful discussions about human diversity (Ash and Wiggan 2018).

“Science or technology and education and smart cities”

There is a diverse literature focused on “smart cities” (e.g. Klett 2014; Sarbeswar and Hoon 2019), because of the new challenges that technology brings in terms of educational system, human capital and labor market (Betz *et al.* 2016), citizen participation and sustainability (e.g. McNutt 2019; Venkatesan 2018). In the “smart city” contexts, education is being positioned as an urban laboratory in which imaginaries of the smart city are being made attainable in experimental forms. School is viewed as a “data platform” where the real time “datafication” of the individual is becoming the cornerstone of a big-data ecosystem and in which educational materials will be algorithmically customized and constantly improved (Williamson 2015). There are different experiments on how to improve the participation in smart cities engaging the education system: for instance, MOOCs could provide an effective tool for facilitating citizen learning and participation with a wider access to education as they are open, have no prerequisites or commitment, and attract a large global audience with diverse backgrounds and attitudes (Lorraine *et al.* 2019). Universities can ameliorate and improve their educational propositions using technologies as during the COVID-pandemic.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The use of new technologies requires that teachers have knowledge, skills, and attitudes that empower them to take advantage of and apply information and communication technologies in the educational process (Olmos-Gómez *et al.* 2020). Furthermore, the use of gamification has implications in education, e-learning, commerce management, citizen participation, and motivation. Gamification is being used in e-learning systems to motivate and engage learners. Smartification of life and use of new approaches such as gamification would modify and reduce environmental, economic, cultural and social problems and make life in the cities more vibrant and motivated (Latifi et al. 2020). Together with gamification other learning experiences are emerging in the “smart cities” contexts as the “smart learning environments” (SLE) that are physical and virtual environments enriched by a contextual surrounding and adaptive digital device. SLE encourages “smart learning” through situations, events, interventions, and observations necessary for learning, for making problem solving activities, for socializing, communicating, practicing and thinking (Dumančić 2019). Universities have the financial and human capital as well as technical expertise to facilitate this change, promoting also hyper-local engagement activities, acting as an intermediary responsive to citizen needs while expressing those interests to local governments (Leigh 2017).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

We analysed the literature considering the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions of the actions analysed. We sum-up the results in the following table: in the first column we enumerate the general goal of these actions; in the second column, we report the factors that still obstacle the process of inclusion of the disadvantage categories; in the third column, we enumerate the different research techniques.

Table 2.5 - Summary of the main awareness actions

Transformative	Exclusionary	Research techniques and ways to engage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supporting the aspiration and the interests of children/young people. ○ Presenting different programs and opportunities to students. ○ Designing a more inclusive teaching, showing different examples and models. ○ Developing a multicultural education. ○ Strengthening the pipeline in STEM careers and avoiding abandons. ○ Enhancing self-efficacy, role-models, self-confidence. ○ Implementing organizational practices to avoid discrimination. ○ Training recruiters to avoid stereotypes and bias. ○ Developing remote education, gamification and new learning environment to favor the inclusion of disadvantage groups and to promote citizen participation. ○ Fulfilling the digital gap to promote people engagement in smart cities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Parents' stereotypes and socialization that generates a different hierarchy of values. ○ Homogenous teachers' identity. ○ Curriculum and pedagogy activities that implicitly favor men and amplify stereotypes. ○ Less sense of belonging and mismatch between gender and science identity. ○ Absence of policies and practices that monitor bias and discrimination in human resources management process. ○ Low attention to other communities. ○ Conflict between science and religion. ○ High standards technological requests and digital divide. ○ Tension between democratic stances and smart cities opportunities. 	<p>Statistics analysis, surveys, focus groups, longitudinal studies, intervention research (programs and experiments), ethnographic studies, mixed methods.</p> <p>In this section prevail action research techniques.</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

2.4. Conclusion

In the literature review different kind of initiatives promoted by different actors were presented with the aim to analyse the main findings and highlight the transformative and exclusionary dimensions of each one.

Our analysis shows that organizational, cultural, social, and urban barriers still emerge impeding the process of inclusion in science/STEM careers; at the same time, most of the studies we have analysed (e.g. Sue *et al.*, 2013, Unesco 2017, Starr, 2018, Marphy 2019, Fogg-Rogers and Hobbs 2019, Nygren, 2019, Eaton *et al.* 2020, Latifi *et al.* 2020) propose some contributions in terms of actions to favour the recruiting and the participation of vulnerable groups to science (e.g. citizen engagement activities, awareness-raising initiatives and cultural dissemination, training courses, role models activities, inclusive teaching, horizontal learning with smart technologies etc.).

In terms of research techniques adopted, in the literature review on “gender”, surveys, focus groups and interviews are prevalent; in some cases, we noticed experiments, longitudinal studies and the adoption of a mixed method approach too; in the literature review on “education” we noticed more participatory-research interventions as focus groups, training programs, ethnographic studies; these studies use also meta-analysis, statistical data analysis and mixed method approaches.

The literature review on gender and education gives some suggestions about the type of initiatives for recruiting and activating minorities, disadvantages groups and people who do not participate to science.

In a nutshell, it is important to work on:

- Primary socialization: the importance of the family, parents, and peers in the formation of interests, aspirations, priorities of young people/girls.
- Education and teaching: the relevance of teachers to consider diversity identities and to support the development of the individual, also presenting diverse role models, examples and experiences that represent the diversity of science/scientific community.
- Organisations (university, departments, companies) and human resources management practices: the importance to avoid bias in recruiting, selection, evaluation and career processes, to promote an open and inclusive organisational climate, to implement policies that support vulnerable groups.
- Society and ICT: the role of technology is central to favour a horizontal, participative, and transversal learning in the “smart cities context” reducing the digital divide and promoting new ways of learning.
- Science and society: the role of scientists and science communicators to promote an inclusive communication that fills the gap between science and society.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

2.5. References

Anzivino, M., Ceravolo, F.A. & Rostan, M. The two dimensions of Italian academics' public engagement. *Higher Education* (2020).

Archer Louise, Jennifer DeWitt, Jonathan Osborne, Justin Dillon, Beatrice Willis & Billy Wong (2013) 'Not girly, not sexy, not glamorous': primary school girls' and parents' constructions of science aspirations, *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 21:1, 171-194.

Ash, Anthony; Wiggan, Greg (2018) Race, multiculturalisms and the role of science in teaching diversity: towards a critical post-modern science pedagogy, in *Multicultural education review*, 2018, Vol.10(2), p.94-120

Aschbacher Pamela R., Erika Li Ellen J. Roth (2010) Is science me? High school students' identities, participation and aspirations in science, engineering, and medicine, in *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, Volume47, Issue5 May 2010 Pages 564-582

Aumiller, Betsy B; Parrott, Roxanne; Lengerich, Eugene J; Dominic, Oralia; Camacho, Fabian; Lehman, Eric; Gallant, Nancy R; Loughran, Thomas P. (2013) Responses to a Theoretically Adapted Clinical Trial Education Session: Faith-Based Sites Versus Rural Work Site Dissemination, *Journal of Cancer Education*, Vol.28(4), p.698-708.

Bertrand, R.L. (2013) Rethinking religious under-representation in science, in *European Journal of Science and Theology* , 2013, Vol.9(6), p.143-152.

Betz, Michael R; Partridge, Mark D; Fallah, Belal (2016) Smart cities and attracting knowledge workers: Which cities attract highly-educated workers in the 21st century? *Papers in regional science*, 2016, Vol.95(4), p.819-841

Bren S. Seel, Rebecca L. Warner and Denise Lach, Gender Differences in Support for Scientific Involvement in U.S. Environmental, in *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, March 2010, Vol. 35, No. 2 (March 2010), pp. 147-173.

Bevan V, Learmonth M. 'I wouldn't say it's sexism, except that ... It's all these little subtle things': Healthcare scientists' accounts of gender in healthcare science laboratories. *Social Studies of Science*. 2013;43(1):136-158.

Bonevski, Billie; Randell, Madeleine; Paul, Chris; Chapman, Kathy; Twyman, Laura; Bryant, Jamie; Brozek, Irena; Hughes, Clare (2014) Reaching the hard-to-reach: a systematic review of strategies for improving health and medical research with socially disadvantaged groups, *BMC medical research methodology*, Vol.14(1).

Brittany Bloodhart, Meena M. Balgopal , Anne Marie A. Casper, Laura B. Sample McMeeking, Emily V. Fischer (2020) Outperforming yet undervalued: Undergraduate women in STEM, *PLOSone*.

Carli LL, Alawa L, Lee Y, Zhao B, Kim E. Stereotypes About Gender and Science: Women ≠ Scientists. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*. 2016;40(2):244-260.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Ceci Stephen J., Wendy M. Williams (2011) Understanding current causes of women's underrepresentation in science, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* Feb 2011, 108 (8) 3157-3162.

Cerinsek, Gregor; Hribar, Tina; Glodez, Natasa; Dolinsek, Slavko (2013) Which are my Future Career Priorities and What Influenced my Choice of Studying Science, Technology, Engineering or Mathematics? Some Insights on Educational Choice—Case of Slovenia, *International journal of science education* , 2013, Vol.35(17), p.2999-3025

Checchi D, Cicognani S, Kulic N. (2019) Gender Quotas or Girls' Networks? Evidence from an Italian Research Selection. *Work, Employment and Society*, 33(3): 462-482.

Cheryan, S., Ziegler, S. A., Montoya, A. K., & Jiang, L. (2017). Why are some STEM fields more gender balanced than others? *Psychological Bulletin*, 143(1), 1–35.

Crettaz von Roten F. Gender Differences in Scientists' Public Outreach and Engagement Activities. *Science Communication*. 2011;33(1):52-75. doi: 10.1177/1075547010378658

Dumančić, M. (2019) Smart education in smart city and student model, *The International Scientific Conference eLearning and Software for Education* , 2019, p.64-71

Eaton, A.A., Saunders, J.F., Jacobson, R.K. et al. (2020) How Gender and Race Stereotypes Impact the Advancement of Scholars in STEM: Professors' Biased Evaluations of Physics and Biology Post-Doctoral Candidates. *Sex Roles* 82, 127–141.

EU, 2020, *Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation*. Policy Review. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020.

Fogg-Rogers L. and Laura Hobbs "Catch 22 — improving visibility of women in science and engineering for both recruitment and retention *Journal of Science Communication* Published: 30 September 2019.

Fraune C., *Gender matters: Women, renewable energy, and citizen participation in Germany*, *Energy Research & Social Science*, 7, 2015, Pages 55-65, ISSN 2214-6296,

Goy, Siew Ching; Wong, Yut Lin; Low, Wah Yun; Noor, Siti Nurani Mohd; Fazli-Khalaf, Zahra; Onyeneho, Nkechi; Daniel, Esther; Azizan, SuzanaAriff; Hasbullah, Maisarah; GinikaUzoigwe, Anthonia (2018) Swimming against the tide in STEM education and gender equality: a problem of recruitment or retention in Malaysia, *Studies in higher education*, Vol.43(11), p.1793-1809

Haynes RD. Whatever happened to the 'mad, bad' scientist? Overturning the stereotype. *Public Understanding of Science*. 2016;25(1):31-44.

Hardcastle, V.G., Furst-Holloway, S., Kallen, R. and Jacquez, F. (2019), "It's complicated: a multi-method approach to broadening participation in STEM", *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, Vol. 38 No. 3, pp. 349-361.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Herman Clem, Suzan Lewis Anne Laure Humbert, Women Scientists and Engineers in European Companies: Putting Motherhood under the Microscope, Gender, Work and Organization, 27 March 2012

Hetsroni A and Lowenstein H (2014) Is She an Expert or Just a Woman? Gender Differences in the Presentation of Experts in TV Talk Shows. *Sex Roles* 70(9): 376–386.

Hirsu, L., Quezada-Reyes, Z. & Hashemi, L. (2021) Moving SDG5 forward: women's public engagement activities in higher education. *High Educ* 81, 51–67.

Hofstra Bas, Vivek V. Kulkarni, Sebastian Munoz-Najar Galvez, Bryan He, Dan Jurafsky, Daniel A. McFarland "The Diversity–Innovation Paradox in Science, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences Apr 2020, 117 (17) 9284-9291.

Howe-Walsh Liza & Sarah Turnbull (2016) Barriers to women leaders in academia: tales from science and technology, *Studies in Higher Education*, 41:3, 415-428.

Hudson, Lorraine; Wolff, Annika; Gooch, Daniel; van der Linden, Janet; Kortuem, Gerd; Petre, Marian; ten Veen, Rianne; O'Connor-Gotra, Sinead (2019) Supporting urban change: Using a MOOC to facilitate attitudinal learning and participation in smart cities, *Computers & education* , 2019, Vol.129, p.37-47.

Jabloner Anna, Sandra Soo-Jin Lee (2020) Who Is the Right Fit? Doing Diversity in Translational Research, *Catalyst, Feminism, Theory and Technoscience*, Vol 6 No 1 (2020): Special Section on Chemical Entanglements: Gender and Exposure

Johnson KM, Simon RM. Women's Attitudes Toward Biomedical Technology for Infertility: The Case for Technological Salience. *Gender & Society*. 2012;26(2):261-289.

Keller, Anita C; Samuel, Robin; Bergman, Manfred Max; Semmer, Norbert K; Mortimer, Jeylan T; Vuolo, Mike; Staff, Jeremy (2014) Agentic Pathways Toward Fulfillment in Work, Psychological, Educational, and Sociological Perspectives on Success and Well-Being in Career Development , 2014, p.99-126.

Klett, F. (2014) Editorial: Smart cities of the future: Creating tomorrow's education toward effective skills and career development today, *Knowledge management & e-learning.* , 2014, Vol.6(4), p.344-355.

Kordaki, Maria; Berdousis, Ioannis (2017) Computing and STEM in Greece: Gender representation of students and teachers during the decade 2002/2012, *Education and information technologies*, Vol.22(1), p.101-124.

Kurtz-Costes, B., Copping, K.E., Rowley, S.J. et al. (2014) Gender and age differences in awareness and endorsement of gender stereotypes about academic abilities. *Eur J Psychol Educ* 29, 603–618.

Latifi, G. R., Monfared, M. P., & Khojasteh, H. A. (2020). Gamification and citizen motivation and vitality in smart cities: a qualitative meta-analysis study. *GeoJournal*, 1-14.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Laurel Elder, Steven Greene, Mary Kate Lizotte, The gender gap on public opinion towards genetically modified foods, *The Social Science Journal*, Volume 55, Issue 4, 2018, Pages 500-509.

Leaper C, Starr CR. Helping and Hindering Undergraduate Women's STEM Motivation: Experiences With STEM Encouragement, STEM-Related Gender Bias, and Sexual Harassment. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*. 2019;43(2):165-183.

Legewie J, DiPrete TA. The High School Environment and the Gender Gap in Science and Engineering. *Sociology of Education*. 2014;87(4):259-280.

Leigh, Elaine W (2017) An Exploration of "Hyper-Local" Community-University Engagement in the Development of Smart Cities, *Equity & excellence in education*. , 2017, Vol.50(4), p.421-433

Losh SC. Stereotypes about scientists over time among US adults: 1983 and 2001. *Public Understanding of Science*. 2010;19(3):372-382.

Maestro, Roselle S; Ramos-Eclevia, Marian; Eclevia, Carlos L; Fredeluces, John Christopherson LT (2018) Teaching Diversity, Becoming Inclusive: Perspectives and Possibilities in ASEAN Library and Information Science Schools, *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association*. , 2018, Vol.67(2), p.96-115

McNutt, David (2019) Building a Workforce for Smart City Governance: Challenges and Opportunities for the Planning and Administrative Professions, *Informatics*. 2019, Vol.6(4).

McKinnon, M., O'Connell, C. Perceptions of stereotypes applied to women who publicly communicate their STEM work. *Humanities Social Sciences Communication* 7, 160 (2020).

Mensah, Felicia Moore (2013) Theoretically and Practically Speaking, What is Needed in Diversity and Equity in Science Teaching and Learning? *Theory into practice*, 2013, Vol.52(1), p.66-72

Miller, D. I., Eagly, A. H., & Linn, M. C. (2015). Women's representation in science predicts national gender-science stereotypes: Evidence from 66 nations. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(3), 631-644.

Miller VM, Rice M, Schiebinger L, et al. Embedding concepts of sex and gender health differences into medical curricula. *J Womens Health*. 2013;22(3):194-202.

Mitchell M, McKinnon M. 'Human' or 'objective' faces of science? Gender stereotypes and the representation of scientists in the media. *Public Understanding of Science*. 2019;28(2):177-190.

Moss-Racusin, C., Sanzari, C., Caluori, N., & Rabasco, H. (2018). Gender bias produces gender gaps in STEM engagement. *Sex Roles*, 79(11-12), 651-670.

Murphy, Marie (2019) Teaching and Learning About Sexual Diversity Within Medical Education: the Promises and Pitfalls of the Informal Curriculum, *Sexuality research & social policy: Journal of NSRC SR & SP*. , 2019, Vol.16(1), p.84-99.

Nygren, T. (2019) Diversity and credibility in young People's news feeds: A foundation for teaching and learning citizenship in a digital era, *Journal of social science education*, Vol.18(2), p.87-109

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Olmos-Gómez, María del Carmen; Luque-Suárez, Mónica; Mohamed-Mohamed, Soraya; Cuevas-Rincón, Jesús Manuel (2020) Validation of the Smart City as a Sustainable Development Knowledge Tool: The Challenge of Using Technologies in Education during COVID-19, *Sustainability*. , 2020, Vol.12(20), p.8384-18

Panel, ACM SIGCSE Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education Seattle, Wash.) 2017 SIGCSE '17 : proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGCSE Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education, March 8-11, 2017, Seattle, WA, USA / , 2017, p.7-666

Patridge, Eric V. Ramon Barthelemy, Susan R. Rankin (2013) Factors Impacting the Academic Climate for Lgbq Stem Faculty, *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, pages 75-98

Paul, David (2013) Creating change: building the capacity of the medical workforce in Aboriginal health, *ANZ journal of surgery*, 2013, Vol.83(1-2), p.55-59.

Potvin, Geoff; McGough, Catherine; Benson, Lisa; Boone, Hank J; Doyle, Jacqueline; Godwin, Allison; Kirn, Adam; Ma, Beverly; Rohde, Jacqueline; Ross, Monique; Verdin, Dina (2018) Gendered Interests in Electrical, Computer, and Biomedical Engineering: Intersections With Career Outcome Expectations, *IEEE transactions on education*, Vol.61(4), p.298-304.

Ran Liu, Do Family Privileges Bring Gender Equality? Instrumentalism and (De) Stereotyping of STEM Career Aspiration among Chinese Adolescents, *Social Forces*, Volume 99, Issue 1, September 2020, Pages 230–254, <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/soz137>

Rainey, K., Dancy, M., Mickelson, R. et al. Race and gender differences in how sense of belonging influences decisions to major in STEM. *International Journal of STEM Education* 5, 10 (2018).

Reuben E., P. Sapienza, Luigi Zingales, How stereotypes impair women's careers in science, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* Mar 2014, 111 (12) 4403-4408.

Sarbeswar, Praharaj, Han, Hoon (2019) Building a typology of the 100 smart cities in India *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*. , 2019, Vol.8(5), p.400-414

Sattari, Sandefur 2018 Gender in academic STEM: A focus on men faculty, *Gender, Work and Organisation* 2019;26:158–179.

Simon RM. Gendered contexts: masculinity, knowledge, and attitudes toward biotechnology. *Public Understanding of Science*, 2011 May;20(3):334-46. doi: 10.1177/0963662509344272. PMID: 21796882.

Steinke J. Adolescent Girls' STEM Identity Formation and Media Images of STEM Professionals: Considering the Influence of Contextual Cues. *Frontiers of Psychology* 2017; 8:716. Published 2017 May 26.

Starr CR. “I’m Not a Science Nerd!”: STEM Stereotypes, Identity, and Motivation Among Undergraduate Women. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*. 2018;42(4):489-503.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Tiainen, Tarja; Berki, Eleni (2019) The re-production process of gender bias: a case of ICT professors through recruitment in a gender-neutral country, *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol.44(1), p.170-184.

Tartari V., Salter, A. (2015) The engagement gap: Exploring gender differences in University – Industry collaboration activities, *Research Policy*, Volume 44, Issue 6, 2015, Pages 1176-1191.

Taragin-Zeller L, Rozenblum Y, Baram-Tsabari A. Public Engagement With Science Among Religious Minorities: Lessons From COVID-19. *Science Communication*. 2020; 42(5):643-678.

Thege, Britta; Popescu-Willigmann, Silvester; Pioch, Roswitha; Badri-Höher, Sabah; Salo, Elaine R; Liersch, Felix; Mohlakoana-Motopi, Lieketseng; Maree, Marinda (2014) Carrots or Sticks? A Study on Incentives to Attract and Retain Women in Science, Engineering and Technology in South Africa, *Paths to career and success for women in science: findings from international research*, p.161-190.

Thomas Nicole R., Daniel J. Poole, Joan M. Herbers Gender in Science and Engineering Faculties: Demographic Inertia Revisited, *PLOSone*. Published: October 21, 2015.

Tiainen Tarja & Eleni Berki (2019) The re-production process of gender bias: a case of ICT professors through recruitment in a gender-neutral country, *Studies in Higher Education*, 44:1, 170-184.

UNESCO. (2017). Cracking the code: Girls' and women's education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). UNESCO. Retrieved from unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0025/002534/253479e.pdf

Valla, Jeffrey M; Williams, Wendy M (2012) Increasing Achievement and Higher-education Representation of Under-represented Groups in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Fields: a Review of Current k-12 Intervention Programs. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering* , 2012, Vol.18(1), p.21-53

Venkatesan, Madhavi; Azeiteiro, Um; Akerman, M; Leal Filho, W; Setti, AFF; Brandli, LL, Promoting Sustainability: The Role of Smart Cities, Lifelong learning and education in healthy and sustainable cities, 2018, p.489-505

Verdugo-Castro, Sonia; García-Holgado, Alicia; Sánchez-Gómez, M^a Cruz (2019) Analysis of instruments focused on gender gap in STEM education, *Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality*, pp. 6-1006.

Wang, MT., Degol, J.L. Gender Gap in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM): Current Knowledge, Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Directions. *Educ Psychol Rev* 29, 119–140 (2017).

Williams Wendy M., Stephen J. Ceci, STEM faculty prefer hiring women professors 2:1, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* Apr 2015, 112 (17) 5360-5365.

Williamson, Ben (2015) Educating the smart city: Schooling smart citizens through computational urbanism *Big data & society* ., 2015, Vol.2(2), p.205395171561778

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Wynn AT, Correll SJ. Puncturing the pipeline: Do technology companies alienate women in recruiting sessions? *Social Studies of Science*. 2018;48(1):149-164. doi:10.1177/0306312718756766

Xie Yu, Michael Fang, Kimberlee Shauman *STEM Education Annual Review of Sociology* 2015 41:1, 331-357 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-071312-145659>

Xu, Y.J., Martin, C.L. Gender Differences in STEM Disciplines: From the Aspects of Informal Professional Networking and Faculty Career Development. *Gender Issues* 28, 134 (2011).

Yuko Ikkatai, Azusa Minamizaki, Kei Kano, Atsushi Inoue, Euan McKay and Hiromi M. Yokoyama (2020) Gender-biased public perception of STEM fields, focusing on the influence of egalitarian attitudes toward gender roles, *Journal of Science Communication* 19 (01).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

3. Social Media Analytics

3.1. Overview

As detailed in the DoA (p.10) in March 2021 (M6) the Social Media Analytics tasks of the project started. According to the GA (p.138) this analysis aimed to:

“provide information about how citizens interact in social media, focusing on the areas of gender and education (O1, O2, O3 & O4). For this analysis, social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Reddit will be considered. The focus will be on how citizen participation in science can be enhanced through online awareness-raising initiatives which link social advancements to the scientific research which led to them.”

For this purpose, ALLINTERACT consortium has followed the Social Impact in Social Media methodology (Pulido et al., 2018)¹, which consists of the identification of quantitative and qualitative evidence of the potential or real impact of research shared on social media.

This chapter contains the Social Media Analytics for topic d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruiting of new talent in science.

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1. Social Media Analysis (SMA)

SMA sought to reach citizens' voices, paying special attention to vulnerable groups and young citizens. For this reason, different social networks were included in this analysis. Considering that each social network has specific characteristics, Table 3.1 compiles the main characteristics of each social network that were considered before the SMA.

¹ Pulido, C. M., Redondo-Sama, G., Sordé-Martí, T., & Flecha, R. (2018). Social impact in social media: A new method to evaluate the social impact of research. *PLoS one*, 13(8).

Table 3.1 - Characteristics of the selected social networks

Network	Options	Characteristics	
Facebook	Pages	Most Facebook pages are not individual initiatives, but they belong to organisations, associations, media or campaigns. Citizens like or follow these pages, so they can see in their home page the contents shared by these pages. When pages share their content, citizens interact with this content through likes, sharing or comments, so this is one way to access citizens' voices	
	Groups	Public	Public groups include the voices of citizens, as all those users who are members of the group can post in the group and interact with the shared content. Users who are not part of the group can find the group (as long as the group is visible) and can see the content and interactions shared within the group, but they can only interact with the content through likes (they cannot publish a new post or comment in existing posts)
		Private	ALLINTERACT will not access private groups
	Individual profiles	<p>One option to search what individual citizens post in their timelines is to browse by hashtags (e.g. #gender). The results will show only those posts containing the hashtag, which are public, including pages and those citizens with a public Facebook profile.</p> <p>NOTE: It is important to ensure that the results obtained through this search are representative of society, because the use of hashtag is not broadly normalised yet and most users do not post using hashtags. In fact, the use of hashtags is more common in pages or institutional profiles than in individual profiles.</p> <p>NOTE: Most citizens do not have their profiles in a public option, so it is difficult to get the whole picture in a search using hashtags.</p> <p>The second option is to use the keyword instead of the hashtag (without the #) in the browser and refining by "publications". However, the results in this search show only publications containing the keyword posted by your friends or public pages. Therefore, this is not a real alternative, as it is impossible to see the whole picture in these results.</p>	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Twitter	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed through RT, comments or likes
Instagram	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed mainly through likes. This social network is the most visual of all and users share pictures with hashtags and sometimes, a brief description. Therefore, it contains less written interactions among users.
Reddit	SubReddit	When you conduct a search in Reddit, you can obtain results by posts and communities/users. As reddit does not use #, the posts results show all posts that use the keyword in every public reddit. When the search is refined by communities, you obtained all communities that mention that word (sorted by relevance, new... and filtered by period of time). In the communities, users share posts and comment posts about different topics. Some communities have categories to filter the posts (e.g: by topic, type of post, location...)
	Individual users	Individual users can join Reddit communities and post or comment existing posts

Source: ALLINTERACT SMA protocol

The procedure carried out for the SMA is based on the ALLINTERACT Social Media Analytics Protocol (Flecha & Pulido, 2021).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	Exclusionary Dimension								
--	------------------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

3.2.2. Social Media Communicative Observation (SMCO)

The SMCO has aimed at further exploring which awareness-raising initiatives are succeeding at enhancing citizen participation in science, in regard to the SDGs of quality education and gender equality, with gender also being considered transversely throughout all SDGs.

Posts identified in mentioning successful awareness-raising initiatives were further explored, in order to identify which of them refer to actions that succeed as well in engaging citizens in active science participation. Researchers reviewed them one by one and classified them following the above-mentioned categories (Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research, Awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation, including the Open Access movement, awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, and policies that promote awareness-raising actions and citizen engagement in science). The success rate of the identified initiatives was also calculated.

3.2.2.1. Selection of the Facebook and Reddit Groups

This research has selected the social media groups/pages taking into account the most used words when talking about gender and education identified in WP1. Based on these words, groups were searched for on the social networks Facebook and Reddit. Specifically, 61 groups were searched, 29 for gender and 32 for education (see Table 3.3).

Table 3.3 - Table summarising the groups pre-selected and contacted for gender and education:

Social Media	Pre-selected Groups Gender	Pre-selected Groups Education
--------------	-------------------------------	----------------------------------

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

<p>Facebook</p>	<p>CAMPAIGN AWARENESS AGAINST GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE & GENDER INEQUALITY!, UNI-Mentors in Violence Prevention, The Feminism Platform, Gender equality in the Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, ETUC Gender Equality, Global Youth Movement Against Gender Based Violence, LGBT Advocacy, EMPOWER EQUALIT. CHILD RIGHT AND GENDER EQUALITY SUPPORT, Gender-based Violence Campaign Group., Gender Based Violence SOLUTIONS, Gender Equity and Reconciliation International, Equality 4 Women, LGBTQ+ Protest Group</p>	<p>Parents for children's education / Parents union from all around the world, School teacher and administrator educational resources, Child Care' Development, Education & Parenting, Our Voice: Communities for Quality Education Group, International Special Needs Teachers/ Learning Support Teachers, Amazing Educational Resources, Special Education Community, Quality Early Childhood Education and Care, PARENTS, TEACHERS AND STUDENTS FORUM, All Teachers' Unity Platform, Teachers and Students, Teachers Throwing Out Grades, The Quality Education Project, Special Education Community, FAME - Families Against Mis-Education.</p>
<p>Reddit</p>	<p>r/feminism, r/feminisms, r/FeMRADebates, r/PurplePillDebate, r/bisexual, r/SRSFeminism, r/AskFeminists, r/Equality, r/TwoXChromosomes, r/AskWomen, r/relationships, r/SexualHarassment, r/GenderIssues, r/MeToo, r/LGBTeens, r/women</p>	<p>r/education, r/ScienceTeachers, r/ApplyingToCollege, r/teaching, r/science, r/Teachers, r/college, r/parenting, r/ParentTeacherGroups, r/ECEC, r/FutureTeachers, r/ScienceEducation, r/highschool, r/specialed, r/Teacher, r/Children.</p>

We contacted the administrators of these groups to participate in the research, of which four replied, two of them decided to participate. However, it was not carried out because they did not provide the ethical consent created to participate in the research.

In parallel, the research team decided to create and search for other social media groups/pages. In the area of gender, five groups on Facebook and five on Reddit were created and selected again, while in the area of education, 5 Reddit groups were created and 5 Facebook groups/pages were contacted where scientific evidence in education was already being discussed.

Table 3.4. shows the names of the gender groups and in which language they are spoken in the group.

Table 3.4 - Facebook and Reddit groups created on gender:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	Spanish	Created	r/Contra_SOSH	Spanish	Created
Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	English	Created	r/Against_SOSH	English	Created
Our right to fall in love	English	Created	r/OurRigthToFallInLove	English	Created
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	Catalan	Selected	r/genderviolence	English	Created
Social Impact Science Platform	English	Created	r/science_gender_sappho	English	Created

The table below lists the names of the education groups and in which language the group speaks.

Table 3.5 - Facebook and Reddit groups or pages created about education:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen
Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/GruposInteractivos	Spanish	Created
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialógicas	Spanish	Selected	r/InteractiveGroups	Spanish	Created
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/TertuliasDialogicas	Spanish	Created

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/DialogicGatherings	English	Created
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/EducacionInclusiva	Spanish	Created

In these groups, posts were written in relation to the results of the ALLINTERACT research, in which users could interact with the content. The groups were also used to provide information and consent for those who wished to participate. The selected groups were informed, and consent was obtained from the administrators and the users whose comments were analysed.

3.2.2.2. Selection of Social Impact Platforms Forums

ALLINTERACT research has been involved since the beginning, in October 2020, in the creation of two Social Impact Platforms, one in gender and the other in education. So, the ALLINTERACT team at the University of Barcelona has decided to incorporate these in the current SMCO analysis.

These platforms are led by the Research Group in Sociological Theory and Impact of Research (TSIR). The two platforms are non-populist participatory platforms, available to everyone, both to consult and to contribute. They are contributing to deepen, on the one hand, in the development of sociological theory at the international level and, on the other hand, to the analysis and improvement of the social impact of research.

These platforms are built with a bottom-up approach that brings together not only researchers and practitioners, but all citizens, both to consult and to contribute. These participatory instruments are committed to promoting an egalitarian dialogue based on validity claims and the sharing of scientific evidence with all citizens. Thus, these platforms are Open Access platforms available to everyone. Any citizen who wants to participate will be able to sign in and contribute. Participation will be totally voluntary.

These platforms are:

- SAPPHO scientific evidence platform is focused on Gender SDG. (<https://socialimpactsience.org/gender/>)
- ADHYAYANA scientific evidence platform is focused on SDG Quality Education, from a multicultural perspective. (<https://socialimpactsience.org/education/>)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The research team contacted the platforms' administration team to inform them of the selection and obtained consent. We also contacted the people selected for the study and obtained consent (Online consent form <https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=qzwxosOxOk-7ESFXRH3btA8lqcPRmYtGj4jVP3l6T1ZUQ1VIVkFIMUVGN1hCN1hHQ1pBQjITMjE4Ry4u>)

3.2.2.3. Data Collection

The information collected has been carried out from May 2021 to December 2021 (6 months) for the social networks Facebook and Reddit. While the information from the Social Impact Science forums has been collected from October 2020 to December 2021 (15 months).

A total of 21,322 members made up the 20 groups selected/created (10 in gender and 10 in education) and the two Social Impact Science Platforms. **A total of 1383 posts related to the research objective** have been made, which have had **3,397 interactions (reactions and sharings)** and **576 comments** have been made.

Data collection on gender

In the field of gender, a total of 885 posts have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit and Social Impact Science on Sappho. Of the 3,171 members who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) 1882 times and made 158 comments.

Details are given below:

Facebook Gender

In relation to the 5 Facebook groups/pages, **486 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published and a total of **600 members have joined**, of which **1875 have interacted and made 38 comments**.

Table 3.6 - Detailed table of the gender-related Facebook groups/pages studied.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. of members / followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	110	106	400	3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	77	110	175	10
Our right to fall in love	25	45	71	2
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	65	10	20	0
Social Impact Science Platform (Gender)	323	215	1,209	23

Reddit Gender

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which **a total of 313 posts** were made about the project and a total of **45 members took part, of which 7 interactions and 4 comments were made.**

In January 2021, when we looked at this data again, we realised that Reddit administrators had deleted around 276 comments in January 2022. So, there are currently 37 public comments left in 2021.

Table 3.7 - Detailed table of Reddit groups on gender.

Reddit				
Group	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/Contra_SOSH	13	98 (6)	3	2
r/Against_SOSH	12	98 (7)	2	2
r/OurRigthToFallInLove	8	65 (6)	0	0
r/genderviolence	3	22(14)	1	0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

r/science_gender_sappho	9	30 (4)	1	0
-------------------------	---	--------	---	---

Social impact Platform Gender

The **2,526 members** of the platform have made **86 related posts** of which other members have made **116 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.8 Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on Sappho Platform.

Sappho Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments
2,526	86	116

Data collection on education

In the field of education, **a total of 498 posts** have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit, and Social Impact Science on Adhyayana. Of the **18,151 members** who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) **1,515 times** and made **418 comments**.

Facebook Education

In the 5 selected Facebook groups/pages on education, about **90 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published. There are **17,527 members** in these groups, of which **1506 interactions and 8 comments** have been made.

Table 3.9 - Detailed table of the education Facebook groups/pages surveyed.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. of members/ followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	4,947	28	338	1
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialogicas	1,107	7	30	0
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	2,617	35	972	7
Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	8,631	8	135	0
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	225	12	31	0

Reddit Education

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which **a total of 203 posts** were made about the project and a total of 49 members took part, of which **9 interactions and 3 comments** were made.

Table 3.10 - Detailed table of Reddit groups on education.

Reddit				
Group/Page	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/GruposInteractivos	13	72	3	0
r/InteractiveGroups	9	70	2	2
r/TertuliasDialogicas	12	55	1	1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

r/DialogicGatherings	9	45	3	0
r/EducacionInclusiva	6	33	0	0

*These Reddit groups are no longer accessible.

In January 2022, when we looked at this data again, we realised that the Reddit administrators have removed the five sub-communities.

Social Impact Science Adhyayana

The **575 members** of the platform have made **133 related posts** of which other members have made **407 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.11 - Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on Adhyayana Platform.

Adhyayana Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments
575	133	407

Final Research Sample

For the final analysis, the first 5 posts on education and 5 on gender that are related to scientific evidence were selected. Finally, **76 comments were analysed (20 on gender and 56 on education)**.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

3.3. Results for SMA

We analysed 824 messages for gender and 429 messages for education (total of 1253). We discarded 9 messages in the section “gender” and 6 messages in the section “education”, when a) there was not a comment (blank); b) the link didn’t work; c) when the topic was not coherent to our research object. At the end, we considered 815 messages for gender and 423 messages for “education” (total of 1238).

Figure 3.2 - Selected and discarded messages in gender and education

The distribution of the messages for the different social media is represented in the figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 - Distribution of the messages included in the analysis.

3.3.1. Gender

Following the protocol, the SMA in *gender* has implemented a twofold strategy, including a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Top-Down

The top-down strategy was conducted in Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and Reddit. Due to the different characteristics of each social networks, they were analysed separately.

Twitter

The SMA in Twitter with a top-down approach included the analysis of the hashtags #Equality (252), #Gender (347), and #GenderEquality (156) with a total of 755 tweets. Less than 8 out of 10 tweets are retweet (79%).

Only the 1% of the total use scientific evidence (we consider tweet and retweet). A total of 13% said they used scientific evidence; the majority don't use scientific evidence.

Figure 3.4 - Distribution of exclusionary/transformative dimensions

The following figure shows that almost all the messages used the transformative dimension while only the 2% used the inclusive dimension. This means that the messages express actions with the aim at closing the gender gap, while the others underline the obstacles to fill this gap. In details:

- The transformative dimension: for the hashtags that we analyzed the dominant idea is to fight against discrimination, to fill the gap in STEM and technological sectors, to create an inclusive and open environment at work and in the society. These initiatives show a different degree of awareness, different forms of engagement and commitment to the topics, but a low level of access to scientific evidence.
- The exclusionary dimension is rare in the hashtags that we analyzed. These messages underline the obstacles and the present discrimination that women face to, the necessity to involve other actors in these “awareness campaign” on gender equality, in particular men that don’t participate and are not fully involved in the gender equality journey.

Figure 3.5 - Distribution of dimensions

The aim/type of the action is very diverse. We categorized the initiatives as follow:

- a) Awareness message/campaign: This category includes messages that stimulate the reflection on “the International Women Day”, gender gaps, women/gender and STEM, LGBT+, racial, age and religious discriminations. These messages are a “call to action”, an invite to reflect and to change the situation.

- b) Call for: These messages posted mainly job-vacancies, call for papers, funds, and other practical initiatives with the aim at recruiting people (in particular women and young people).
- c) Communication initiatives: This category includes messages that promote events, podcasts, talks, interviews, and other activities that favour the awareness-raising.
- d) Corporate initiatives: This category includes messages that promote business programs, mentorship activities and other projects that involve the participation of the business world (companies, employees etc.).
- e) Academic activities: This category includes messages that promote research, seminar and other activities linked to the academic world.
- f) Award: This category includes messages that concern call for awards.
- g) Education and Training: This category includes messages on specific education and training programs.
- h) Other activities.

As showed in the figure 3 most of the messages concern awareness campaigns, followed by call for and other practical communication initiatives. Relevant are both corporate initiatives and academic activities that don't emerge or emerge less in the "education" section.

In the following figures (3, 4, 5) we detailed the differences among the hashtags #Equality (252), #Gender (349), and #GenderEquality (156).

Figure 3.6 - Aim/type of initiatives (#Equality)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.7 - Aim/type of initiatives (#Gender)

Figure 3.8 - Aim/type of initiatives (#GenderEquality)

The level of intervention was categorized considering the top-down and bottom-up dimensions: 'top-down' means that the message expresses an action taken by an institution,

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

a company, a representative of an organisation; 'bottom-up' means that the message was proposed by an individual-private that wanted to show their endorsement to a cause.

Figure 3.9 - Top-down/ bottom-up approach

The main fields of intervention mentioned in the messages concern the topic of gender/women in STEM and technology fields, but emerge also racial and LGBTQ+ issues, environment, agriculture, green and health, gender, diversity and inclusion in a generical way and referred to the workplace too. In the category 'others' we included the following topics: gender and human rights, gender and conflict, gender and violence, gender and poverty, gender and policy, gender and politics, gender and transports, gender and psychiatry, gender and education, disabilities and other communities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.10 - Topics/field of intervention

Facebook

For this section, we count only one message, that mentioned a “call for competition” targeted to young people/students. The message doesn’t contain any scientific evidence.

Instagram

The SMA in Instagram included the hashtags #womenempowerment, #feminism and #genderequality and a total of 43 posts. All the posts express a transformative dimension, because they promote different kind of initiatives for changing the condition of women in STEM, but also for improving their position in other sectors.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.11 - Aim/type of initiatives

In these messages prevails the issue “women/gender and STEM” and the gender equality topic. It emerges the “education” topic, but the number of cases is limited, as the “gender and poverty” category.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.12 - Topics/field of intervention

Reddit

No results were found for this section.

Bottom-Up

Twitter

The SMA in Twitter with a bottom-up approach included hashtags that were retrieved from the daily trending topics in all European countries. In this line, it includes the hashtags #EqualPayDay, #ReclaimTheStreets and #EnoughisEnough and a total number of 16 tweets. None of them shows “scientific evidence”, nor “they said to use scientific evidence”. All of them express a transformative dimension, because of the messages communicate a positive active message for promoting change.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

3.3.2. Education

The SMA in education, as well as in gender, has followed a twofold strategy, including a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

Top-Down

The top-down strategy was conducted in four social networks: Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and Reddit. Due to the different characteristics of each social networks, the messages extracted in each case were analysed separately.

Twitter

No results were found for this section.

Instagram

The SMA in Instagram using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #QualityEducation, #StopBullying, #ScienceEducation, #Learning and #Education. A total of 283 posts were included in the final analysis. None of them include scientific evidence, i.e. they don't refer to articles or results taken by scientific research on the education topic.

Figure 3.13 - Distribution of categories

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Furthermore, all the messages express a transformative dimension, because of showing a positive statement that promotes participation and involvement in science and education.

In terms of initiatives, messages on Twitter celebrate lives of scientist (including women), do congratulations to excellent students for their results, promoting a lot of events, as festival, Olympiad, “Science Day”, comedies, challenges, projects and communicating practical activities to enhance participation (as labs for kid/young people, courses on different topics and training).

Figure 3.14 - Aim/type of initiatives

These messages come mainly from a “top-down” perspective, when they promote call for or other institutional activities; on the contrary, messages come from a bottom-up perspective when they express an awareness message in which emerge both the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.15 - Top-down and bottom-up dimensions

The topics covered by these messages are science and technologies fields, opportunities careers in STEM, gender and science topics, and the area of education that cover different aspects: learning opportunities, new strategies and methodologies to enhance science teaching, problems of accessibility and social exclusion of different categories. Actions are targeted for different publics: these publics are often generic (the message is directed to all) or specific: for students (in general) or for specific sub-groups: young student, low-income students, migrants, etc. Some messages are directed to families and educators with the aim at supporting them in terms of students' learning education experiences.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.16 - Topics/fields of intervention

Figure 3.17 - Targets of the initiatives

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Facebook

We analysed 4 messages referred to “Weareteachers”. These are “inspiring messages” or messages that speak about “math contest competition”. No mention of scientific evidence.

Reddit

We analysed 2 messages for “Education”, 5 for “Science”, 2 for “Teachers” and 7 for “Applying to college”. These messages talk mainly about high school programs and access, and career path. **No mention of scientific evidence**

Bottom-Up

Twitter

The SMA in Twitter using a bottom-up strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #books, #Wikipedia, #FutureOfEurope, #DigitalDecade and #Schools. A total of 120 tweets were included in the final analysis. Almost all the messages don't use scientific evidence, even if there are a lot of references with the aim at promoting women in science or science often adopting an historical perspective.

Figure 3.18 - Distribution of evidence

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the following figure we present the messages analysed following the two dimensions (transformative and exclusionary). The percentage of messages showing an exclusionary dimension is underestimated because of a high level of retweets of a singular message. This message denounces a racial discrimination against a young person (#Schools).

Figure 3.19 - Distribution of dimensions

As in the case of “gender”, the level of intervention was categorized considering the top-down and bottom-up dimensions: in the case of Education prevails the top-down dimension.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.20 - Distribution of dimensions

In terms of initiatives, the analysis shows the prevalence of awareness messages to favour the participation of young people and women in science and education (including topics as bias, discrimination and social exclusion); different messages promote scholarships and calls for to enhance this participation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.21 - Aim/type of initiatives

The SMA in Twitter using a bottom-up strategy shows the prevalence of gender discrimination and social exclusion (in racial/ethnic terms) topics, but also consider different initiatives to enhance the participation of students, teachers and families in science/science education.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.22 - Topics in Twitter

In particular, considering the different hashtags analysed:

- The tweets for the hashtag #Books include topics about books and other resources for promoting women in science.
- Under the hashtag #FutureOfEurope, there are tweets concerning an event on social inclusion in Europe.
- The hashtag #Wikipedia includes topics on women in science and gender discrimination, but also initiatives to increase information on women on Wikipedia.
- The tweets for the hashtag #Schools included awareness campaign for students and call for scholarships.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

3.4. Conclusion

This section presents a summary of the main findings regarding the SMA.

- Almost all the messages show a positive attitude, expressing more frequently the “transformative” dimension rather than the “exclusionary” ones. The idea is that of presenting awareness-raising initiatives presuming that the publics know the factors that obstacle the process of inclusion of disadvantages categories.
- Messages show different degree of awareness and commitment to the topics. Overall, there is a high level of awareness in relation to gender equality topics, social exclusion of specific categories to the educational system, scientific community and correlated sectors (in particular, technological sectors).
- Even if there is a high level of awareness, messages show a low level of access to scientific evidence.
- The awareness-raising initiatives are diverse: from awareness-messages or campaigns, to “call for”, from corporate and academic initiatives to training, courses and other educational projects to favour the participation of people.
- Apart from the awareness messages/campaigns and the call for actions, in the “gender” section we highlight more often corporate and academic initiatives, while in the “education” section emerge learning actions targeted to students and teachers.
- Top-down level prevails on bottom-up level because of the presence of representatives of institutional actors (NGO, government, enterprises, universities) that promote actions to foster the participation; bottom-up initiatives are less frequent, but more emotionally involved.
- In the “education” section, different kinds of publics emerge (students, teachers, families, women, young people, low-income, people, migrants), while in the “gender” section the public was more homogenous (women or all).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

3.5. Results for SMCO

The analysis of the Social Media Communicative Observation consisted in exploring the effects of introducing scientific evidence in the interactions. The selected groups have been studied in detail using the software MAXQDA2020, in order to explore which of the selected actions have succeeded at enhancing participation in science. The comment threads were listed according to the order of appearance (E1, E2, E3 ...), while listing the participants (1, 2, 3...) who made contributions that were related to the object of study. Finally, 57 comments were analysed (21 on gender and 36 on education).

The messages have been categorised by the following selected actions and we have identified for each category the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions. The categories we have analysed are: 1) Aim of the enhancing-participation action; 2) Promoting organisation (i.e., aim; private/public); 3) Level of intervention (i.e., local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down); 4) Field of intervention; 5) Participants (targeted and real); 6) Type of participation (i.e., role of participants); 7) Level of access to scientific evidence; and 8) Social impact.

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e., what facilitates the implementation of the targeted actions) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e., obstacles hindering the implementation of the targeted actions) were identified.

The SMCO analysis has consisted mainly of a review one by one of the posts, classifying them and identifying and selecting the actions that succeed in active science participation. The consent form has been obtained from the participating members of the analysed posts.

Then we have identified the changes in the debate after the scientific evidence was introduced in the discussion.

Once data has been categorised, we have calculated the correlation between the two variables “citizen awareness of the social impact of research” and “citizen engagement in science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The only comment that seems to speak about the need to collect and disseminate scientific evidence to promote the importance of these efforts to achieve inclusive education, and to argue from a human rights approach, so that education is a right available to all. A commentary, which together with insinuations made in other published commentaries, shows the claim that applying scientific evidence in educational centres and socio-cultural spaces can improve the educational success of students. A success that can promote new talents in science.

TOPIC d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences

	Aim of the enhancing-participation action	Promoting organization	Level of intervention	Field of intervention	Participants (targeted & real)	Type of participation (i.e., role of participants)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social Impact
TD*	E1.1: Therefore, scientific evidence should be collected and disseminated to promote the importance of these efforts to achieve inclusive education, and argue from a human rights approach, so that education is a right available to all.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
ED*								

3.6. Conclusion

Only a user shows that applying scientific evidence in educational centres and socio-cultural spaces can improve the educational success of students.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

4. Focus Groups

4.1. Overview

All partners have worked keeping in mind that a Focus Group (FG) “is a group of individuals selected and assembled by researchers to discuss and comment on, from personal experience, the topic that is the subject of the research” (Powell & Single, 1996, p. 499)². Focus groups in gender include the selection of different profiles of participants: Women (including vulnerable women) from a women’s group; Members of an LGBTQI group; Women (including Young women) from a women’s group. Focus groups in education include the selection of different profiles of participants: Parents; Teachers; Students.

The section is divided into three parts: The first one, methodology of the focus, which explains the main characteristics of the implementation and analysis of FG; the second section, which focuses on the results of the FG on gender and education; and the final section, where we present the conclusions obtained on the “Topic A) How citizens’ benefit from scientific research” from the research.

4.2. Methodology

The focus groups conducted by the UOXF, ISCSP-ULISBOA, UNIMIB, UB, UH, and RUG followed the guidelines established in the Focus Group protocol of the projects, as well as the individual and collective protection measures based in the country due to the COVID-19 pandemic. 4.1.1. Implementation of the Focus groups.

Table 4.1 - Distributed of the focus groups among partners of the Consortium:

Gender			Education		
Profile of participants	Partner	C/E	Profile of participants	Partner	C/E
Women (including vulnerable women) from women’s group	UOXF	C/E	Parents	UB	C/E
Member of LGBTQI group	ISCSP- ULisboa	C/E	Teacher	UH	C/E
Women (including Young women) from a women’s group	UNIMIB	C/E	Students	RUG	C/E

² Powell, R. A., & Single, H. M. (1996). Focus groups. *International journal for quality in health care*, 8(5), 499-504.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

All participants have received written and oral information about the project and have signed a consent document, translated into the national language, to participate in the project. The guidelines are set out in terms of format, language and time in Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants.

The methodological procedure used for each of the population groups studied is detailed below:

4.2.1. Gender

Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group

In line with the objective of the ALLINTERACT project to widen and diversify citizens' engagement in science, participants were recruited via the Public and Community Involvement, Engagement and Participation leads at NIHR Oxford Biomedical Research Centre and the NIHR Applied Research Collaboration for Oxford and the Thames Valley with a specific focus on including participants from diverse ethnic groups. One participant required English language translation, which was provided by their family member. Several participants identified themselves as neurodiverse.

Altogether, 33 people expressed interest in participating in FGs. Based on the availability of the majority of the participants, 18 people were invited to participate in two FGs, one participant declined an invitation, and one participant did not attend. As a result, 16 people participated in two FGs.

During recruitment, potential participants were asked if they would be potentially interested in participating 1) in an intervention aimed at raising citizens awareness in order to promote and diversify citizens engagement in science, and 2) in a followed up focus group. Only those who indicated their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Experimental Group. Those who did not indicate their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Control group.

In line with the Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants, all potential participants signed a consent form to participate in the FGs and prior to that had an opportunity to ask researchers questions regarding their potential participation.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and their pseudonyms are detailed in Table 4.2 below.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 4.2 - Socio-demographic characteristics and pseudonyms of participants, UOXF.

Focus Group number and type	Pseudonym	Age	Race/ethnicity
FG1 (Experimental)	P1	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P2	51-60	Mixed (White and Black Caribbean, White and Black African, White and Asian, any other Mixed background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P3	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P4	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P5	51-60	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P6	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P7	51-60	Other
FG1 (Experimental)	P8	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P9	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P10	20-30	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

FG 2 (Control)	P11	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG 2 (Control)	P12	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P13	70+	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P14	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P15	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P16	20-30	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)

Member of LGBTQI group

The Gender Team at University of Lisbon was in charge of conducting two FG sessions, one for an Experimental Group and one for a Control Group. Regarding the Experimental Group, 7 people voluntarily participated in the session, while the Control Group was composed by 8 people.

WP2 followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, based on high standard criteria: a free and voluntary participation and avoidance of any kind of coercion which may have a negative impact on their involvement during the FG. Also, researchers from the WP2 informed the participants that they will not receive any type of reward for their time and presence during the session, as well as the confidentiality on the information analysis and dissemination of results.

Tables 4.3 and 4.4 include the information from participants of the two FG conducted at this stage. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 4.3 - Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Experimental Group conducted by WP2.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Role
FG1 – EG	P1	Participant
FG1 – EG	P2	Participant
FG1 – EG	P3	Participant
FG1 – EG	P4	Participant
FG1 – EG	P5	Participant
FG1 – EG	P6	Participant
FG1 – EG	P7	Participant
FG1 – EG	F1	Facilitator
FG1 – EG	F2	Facilitator

Table 4.4 - Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Control Group conducted by WP2.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Role
FG1 – CG	P1	Participant
FG1 – CG	P2	Participant
FG1 – CG	P3	Participant
FG1 – CG	P4	Participant
FG1 – CG	P5	Participant
FG1 – CG	P6	Participant
FG1 – CG	P7	Participant
FG1 – CG	P8	Participant
FG1 – CG	F1	Facilitator
FG1 – CG	F2	Facilitator

Topics addressed in both sessions were taken from the list included in ALLINTERACT Protocol, according to the objectives in which WP2 has been working throughout the project: a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

Both facilitators welcomed participants and explained the stage of the project in which FG are being conducted. Facilitator 1 (F1) had the role of carrying the conversation along the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

session and invited participants to express their opinions regarding the topics. F1 encouraged an egalitarian intervention from all participants and promoted an open dialogue.

According to the Focus Group Protocol, FG sessions were conducted in the country's official language (Portuguese), in order to assure comprehension and interaction among participants. However, according to the instructions provided by the Central Team, opinions from participants included in this report were translated into English. The records of the FG, as well as the full transcripts of both sessions, have been stored by the CIEG-ISCSP, who collected the data in the dispositive approved by our ethical board.

Women (including young women) from a women's group

The UNIMIB team had to carry out two focus groups involving “women/including young women” that are part of a national association dealing with gender/feminist issues.

After a careful analysis of the Italian associative landscape, the UNIMIB team selected “Casa delle donne”, because of its long history of feminist activism (more than 30 years), in particular on gender violence. It is a “*social promotional association that looks without discrimination at the aspirations and needs of women of all ages and sexual orientations, who (...) live in our city (Milan). The association is linked to other women's associations (...) that share our goals to fight gender-based violence, promote talents and enhance women's knowledge*”³.

UNIMIB team selected this association for two main reasons: 1) this association involves women not only of various ages, but also with different characteristics in terms of nationality, education, socio-economic status, job *etc.*; 2) the association is based in different Italian cities; therefore, it was possible to guarantee a geographical mix.

We illustrated the project's goals, the methodology, the research expectations to the main stakeholders of this association. We indicated the criteria for correctly selecting our participants: we searched people with different ages, with a particular attention to young women (20-29 years old), as indicated by the Protocol; people with different education, so preferably not all people with a degree or a master's degree (coherently with the spirit of the project that wants to engage social disadvantage people or people that historically don't participate to science). We excluded people with STEM education and academics for the same reasons.

We contacted “Casa delle donne di Milano”, “Casa delle donne di Pisa” and, finally, “Casa delle donne di Parma”. They are located in the North and in the Center of Italy. We contacted “Casa delle donne di Roma” too, but we didn't select any participants from there, because the participants' characteristics didn't match with our criteria. We selected these cities because they are representative of the Italian small/medium/large cities, and they have a different but relevant history in terms of feminist activism.

³ The quotation is taken from: <https://www.casadonnemilano.it/chi-siamo/>
“Casa delle donne” is present in different Italian cities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

A very long and meticulous work has been done both to find people interested in the participation in our project and to compose balanced groups.

At the end of the selection's process, we had a list of 17 people; we composed our final groups with 10 people: 5 for the first FG (the experimental group) and 5 for the second FG (the control one). We excluded 5 people because of their characteristics; the other 2 didn't accept to participate for personal reasons. In the following table (Table 4.5) we resume all the women' characteristics.

Table 4.5 - Characteristics of the participants in the focus groups.

Focus Group (n. 1/n. 2)	Participant's initial name	Characteristics (nationality, age, education)	Association (geographical area)	Group (experimental /control)
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	L.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	I	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Parma	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	T.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	E.	Italian, but with foreign parents; 40-50 years; 8 th grade diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	P.	Italian; 60-70 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	G.	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma;	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	M.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	C.	Foreign origin; 40-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Milano	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	S.	Italian, 50-60 years old; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	A.	Italian; 50-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG

Selected participants have received written and oral information about the project. UNIMIB team informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for them. Researchers communicated that all participants will be informed about the evolution of the ALLINTERACT project. All the participants signed an informed

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

consent document. All participants' informed consent documents are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

In line with the national directives in terms of collective safety, the UNIMIB team carried out the FGs online through the WEBEX platform. We conducted the two focus groups in Italian in the following dates:

- Focus Group 1: On Tuesday, the 12th October 2021 from 10.00 to 11.30 a.m. (without a pause); since we didn't finish to discuss all the stimuli, we scheduled another brief meeting on Wednesday the 20th October from 1.30 to 2.00 p.m.
- Focus Group 2: on Thursday, the 14th October 2021 from 6.30 to 8.00 p.m. (without pause).

The UNIMIB team conducted all the FGs in Italian to guarantee the full participation of people. In each of the FGs there were two researchers (Prof. Carmen Leccardi and Dr. Zenia Simonella) who played the role of facilitators of the discussion. The researchers presented themselves. One of the two researchers briefly illustrated: a) the goals of the FGs; b) the possibility for each participant to freely express her opinion without fear; c) the ethical principles related to the protection of all FGs' participants in terms of privacy/anonymity. The other researcher conducted the FGs proposing the selected pool of stimuli (on gender topic) that were reported in the Protocol Document. Every researcher was in charge of involving all the participants, in particular those who participated less to the discussion.

All focus groups and interviews have been audio/video-recorded and literally transcribed. These recordings are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

4.2.2. Education

Parents

At the University of Barcelona, we conducted on the one hand four in-depth interviews with family members of vulnerable groups who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings and two FG with families (15 mothers exactly, and 3 teachers accompanying them). These families did not used to participate in scientific activities. Thus, it will be these families that we will carry out the implementation of the scientific activities carried out by the project.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG and interviews so far. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

Table 4.6. - Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Role
Interview 1 (I)	Maria	Family
Interview 2(I)	Sofia	Family
Interview 3 (I)	Cristina	Family
Interview 4(I)	Francisca	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Elena	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laura	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Angela	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laia	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Nerea	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Estefania	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carolina	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Matilde	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carmen	Teacher
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Hayat	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariana	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariya	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Silvia	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Esther	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Victoria	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Josefa	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Diana	Teacher

FG and interviews have followed five sections: 1) Identification of how societal actors benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education. One of the interviewers will have the role of facilitator of the focus groups and will be in charge of giving turns to

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator will always prioritize those participants who have intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator will also encourage everyone to join the conversation and ensure an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervene to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

Teachers

In this topic the UH team has implemented two focus groups held with educators/teachers. Likewise, the Barcelona team conducted two FG with teachers (17 people) who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG with teachers.

Table 4.7 - Pseudonymous participant in focus groups undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonia	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Dolores	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Sara	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonio	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Javier	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Miguel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Elena	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Raquel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Alejandro	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Juan	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Alba	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mónica	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Laura	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Jesús	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emilio	Teacher

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Students

At the University of Groningen, we conducted two FG with undergraduate students (12 people). All the people participated voluntarily throughout the process, and we followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, which is based on high standard criteria: all conversations between researchers and potential participants about the possibility of participating in the research occurred in a place where the participants felt comfortable and safe to avoid any possible coercion and to ensure that the decision was taken with absolute freedom. Researchers have informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for the participants. Researchers have also explained the possible risks and benefits of participating. The recruitment process was never conducted by someone who may have an unduly influence on potential participants. The language employed ensures comprehension for the participant.

Table 4.8 - Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by RUG.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Julia	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Yara	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kostas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kelly	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Liam	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mary	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Sophie	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Eleni	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Anika	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emma	Student

One of the interviewers will have the role of facilitator of the focus groups and will be in charge of giving turns to participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator will always prioritize those participants who have intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator will also encourage everyone to join the conversation and ensure an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervene to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

All focus groups and interviews have been audio-recorded and literally transcribed, substituting all names for pseudonyms for scientific use for later analysis. Later on, we translated into English. The records of the FG have been stored by each partner who collected the data in the dispositive approved by our ethical board on their institutions.

4.3. Analysis

The ALLINTERACT team has followed the dimensions and initial categories emerged from project topics (a-e), each partner being in charge of the same topic as in the literature review:

Table 4.9 - Definitions of dimensions and categories for Focus Groups.

Dimensions	Transformative dimension includes those messages that evidence what facilitates the social/political/scientific impact mentioned.
	Exclusionary dimension includes those messages that show obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted social/political/scientific impact.
Category	d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences

4.4. Results

4.4.1. Gender

Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group

Although participants acknowledged the importance of awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, they were able to provide only a limited number of examples. In particular, these included actions by local authorities, universities, and professional associations. One participant also mentioned the adverse effects of such actions, namely pressure on women to participate in such actions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

TOPIC d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences

	<i>Aim of the action targeting new talent for science</i>	<i>Promoting organization</i>	<i>Level of intervention</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Type of participation</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
	<p>“The obvious one to think of, which is in Buckinghamshire, all the times going on is the emphasis in schools to promote science, learning to show young people at the age of 14 15 when they're thinking of careers that, you know, science is not just for Oxford and Cambridge graduates, it's for everybody. So yes, I know of that specific where a lot of money being spent at the moment, taxpayers money, obviously, to promote this kind of thing across schools, which means that, you know, ethnic minorities are being, are there girls, boys? So it's open to all.” P14 FG2</p>	Local government	National /Bottom-up	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	High	Yes
	<p>“my sister who graduated this year, one of her friends, a female friend, studied engineering and she was the only person in her year group that was a woman studying engineering, and she received so many emails from her lecturers to attend these women in STEM women in engineering events. Far too many that she could possibly attend by herself” P6 FG1</p>	University	Local/Bottom up	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	High	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>“You're always hearing on the radio or in newspapers about outreach projects. I know, for instance, that the, whatever the professional body of engineers can't remember what they're called, have for years, how to get more women into engineering. And now something like 20 30 percent of undergraduates in engineering are female. And the other thing is, I think most universities have outreach projects where they send undergraduates or graduates into schools to talk.” P13 FG2</p>	Professional association	National /Bottom-up	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	High	Yes
	<p>“I work with the RSC [Royal Society of Chemistry] and we run a couple of competitions each year that are open to all schools in our local area. But we have a real problem with secondary schools, state secondary schools just don't have the resources to get their kids to these things. So again, we have this bias that they're taken up by private schools... but we do prioritize state schools. So if a state school applies now, then they get priority over a private school.” P1 FG2</p>	Professional association	National /Bottom-up	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	High	Yes
	<p>“I think it's terribly important to have more “the people like me” [role models] so that youngsters can have a look and say, you know, female engineer, black scientist, you know, whatever it is that you can't just keep putting up sort of white men as an example of things. And I think the more younger people are exposed to lots of women of different ethnicities doing interesting things, the more it'll fire their imagination and make them think, well, if they can do it, why can't I?” P3 FG 2</p>	Self-organization	local	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	Medium	No
ED*								

Members of LGBTQI group

Participants did not feel entitled to discuss this topic. They did not feel comfortable with speaking about a topic in which they do not manage any relevant information, nor they have any working experience or perception about it.

Women (including young women) from a women's group

This section lacks results as people do not engage in awareness activities that foster the recruitment of new talents. People mentioned general activities carried out by others to foster the participation. We report in table 6 some examples.

In the discussion, however, the participants highlight some relevant, but more general, issues:

- The importance of the school and of the role of teachers in breaking down gender stereotypes (*“Doing an awareness campaign where teachers promote the participation of all students”* (A., FG_2).
- The role of scientists (women and men) in promoting students' participation, and in particular women: *“It is important that there are informed people who go to high schools and tell young women that they are the same as men, indeed... I would say that girls are even more clever... they always have an edge. I see that, at university, my daughter and another friend are on par with their exams, they are ahead of others who attend the Engineering course”*. (S., FG_2).
- The importance for scientists to find new ways to communicate with ordinary people, developing skills that are different from traditional ones: *The scientist has to acquire skills and characteristics that were not previously requested. It could be a new way of doing selection, even for those involved in science. We try to communicate ... but how should it be carried out? Not closed in the university, but perhaps in the street, going towards different cultures, ideas, prejudices* (C., FG_2).
- The role of scientists on TV or social media to communicate scientific results, trying constantly to involve people: *“I really appreciated that during this period... even if men and women who go on TV become ‘prime donne’... everyone speaks in a scientific way... yes, but they became repetitive figures”* (S., FG_2).
- The importance to communicate that the history of science is plenty of women scientists. This could be a way to encourage young women to follow that career: *“Showing that science has not always been a prerogative of men. There were and there are female scientists. Their stories could stay in the textbooks, so this gives courage to girls who want to pursue that career. So... I am not who open a path, but I follow a path that others have opened before me. And this is more reassuring, more encouraging”* (M., FG_2). Linked to this point emerged the importance of deconstructing the idea of the genius as a man, fostering a more diverse representation of the scientist: *“The fact that even for me the image of the genius who deals with science... we consider him the bearer of things that we are not able to do... this genius is a boy ... once a young student came to my high school... he was a bit atypical and everyone said:*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

“Ah, this is a genius”. Would it also happen with a woman? Yes, women are good. But no one told me: “she is a genius.” (C., FG_2).

- Another point that we analyzed also in the previous section concerns the importance of the social context and the necessity to avoid that prejudices flourish especially in disadvantage families: *“I take care of foreign children and I see that part of teachers give guidance to these children who are less advantaged and have less chance to attend a good high school. Many times, it happens that parents and even children take teachers' advice as good. This has to do with both males and females. There is the category of children who are not sufficiently social integrated. We have to be very careful... there is a basic prejudice that probably influences families in more disadvantaged social contexts”*. (C., FG_2).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

TOPIC d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences

	<i>Aim of the action targeting new talent for science</i>	<i>Promoting organization</i>	<i>Level of intervention</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Type of participation</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
TD*	The initial stimulus about museums and researchers... It is an excellent initiative. The museum is alive if there are people who work there. What over the years may have encouraged us to identify ourselves in different figures from the usual ones is the publication of that book for girls that reported figures of women scientists. I think it was a small revolution. It is important to intervene in school publishing... I have seen my nephew's books ... They're far from gender parity. Starting with the language. We always speak in the masculine form. (A., FG_2)	Private company/edition	Top-down	Gender	Potential clients	Participant	High	Yes
TD*	A company created dolls that impersonate important characters. For example, Samanta Cristoforetti. It is important for a little girl to play with this doll. Maybe she might think that she can do that career. (S., FG_2).	Private company/edition	Top-down	Gender	Potential clients	Participant	High	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

<p>The pandemic has brought some very good scientists on TV. And this is already important. There is a feminine authority. I imagine the girls eating with their parents watching TV and saying: “Ah that's a scientist. Maybe I could do it too”. They are not the ones behind the scientist, but these women are the scientists. (M., FG_2).</p>	Public	Top-down	Science/ COVID	Citizens	Participant	High	Yes
--	--------	----------	-------------------	----------	-------------	------	-----

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

4.4.2. Education

Parents

People interviewed point out that the Scientific Dialogic Gatherings encourage the recruitment of talent and the active participation during the scientific process of some of the participants. Some students, family members and teachers, after participating in the dialogue discussions, start attending scientific conferences and congresses. These events encourage pupils to want to become scientists in the future, and at the same time, they encourage some teachers to start their doctoral thesis.

Family members who were not used to participating in scientific activities beforehand reported that they took their children to mathematics competitions or to participate in science programmes, and also reported that some toys enhance their children's interest in science. In relation to the difficulties in fostering new talents, families pointed out that science is socially seen as something very difficult to access and that they are at a loss as to how to foster their children to become new talents in science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

TOPIC d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences

	<i>Aim of the action targeting new talent for science</i>	<i>Promoting organization</i>	<i>Level of intervention</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Type of participation</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
TD*	FG2 Juan: Since I've been in the seminary, which is a few years now, I've transferred it to my work place where I've done interactive groups in high school and then specifically literary gatherings in high school, both with and without family members, not in both ways Feminist Dialogics Gatherings. I'm also doing my thesis on it.	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes
	FG2 Juan: I wanted to do my thesis many years ago and I abandoned it due to lack of motivation. Now I have taken it up again with full motivation, since I am in the Seminary. Personally, I am more and more curious and I don't believe anything anymore. I try to look for them, in fact we have also been doing pedagogical gatherings for teachers for two years, which also has a great impact.	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes
	GD2 Emilio: Now that I find it difficult to imagine another format of access to scientific literature, after reading it and then understanding it and being able to transfer it to the classroom. (He is talking about the Dialogic Scientific Gatherings).	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	High	Yes
	GD2 Emilio: Some people from the seminar have encouraged us to participate in international research congresses such as CIMIE, for example, we can participate in them and each time we have understood how	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	High	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

to make small contributions and some of us have been able to make some contributions from the classroom with all humility. Now, as with Juan with the thesis and, also, I am encouraged to participate in meetings with some people to start participating in science and, moreover, with the Sappho and Adhayana platforms.

GD2 Juan: One of the experiences that had the greatest impact at the Institute was to open a training space for families, more than 7 or 8 years ago, 11 family members came to the teacher training and in total there were 23 of us, including fathers, mothers and we trained together in the 30 hours of training on the learning community project. It is my most beautiful experience in terms of training, since it has a lot of repercussions later when you ask for volunteers for interactive groups, when you open the discussion group to families, when there is a congress or a conference, we sign up for it.

GD2 Alba: In the seminar we read a neuroscience book and then I brought it to read pieces with the children. Then during the course we were talking about connections and whether to do synaptic pruning or not. Throughout the year in conversations about how we couldn't let neurons and connections go to sleep. Even a student who has a special interest in the subject of science, asked me, please, the reference of the book to read it to him.

GD2 Juan: a 15-year-old teenage girl told us that she wanted to do research. So if it happens to you Alba, if it happens to me, if it happens there, the same is that when you bring science closer to boys and girls in schools, family and peer environments that also awakens in them the desire and motivation to study that science and become future researchers and researchers.

FG4 Victoria: My son goes to math contests.

FG4 Victoria: Also the Science in Action program (they did it at her son's school).

Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	High	Yes	
Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes	
Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	High	Yes	
Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	Medium	No	
Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	Medium	Do not know	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	FG4 Victoria: Children do experiments, especially young children. Children come to you and say, "Mom, should I mix this with this? And the microscope and the finger prick and they look at the blood in the microscope.	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	Medium	Yes
ED*	FG4 Esther: Science was presented to you as something very difficult to reach. Later, when you got there, you saw that it was not as hard as they made you believe... It's that science is very difficult to understand and how few people reach it.	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	Medium	No
	FG4. Silvia: Of course I am lost. I know that my daughter has had many tests done before, they have seen that her intelligence is very high, but she has ADD. Of course, I don't know where to start....	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	Medium	No

* TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Teachers

The results for this section are very limited. People mentioned generic actions as “positive discrimination action” as legislation to enforce change and improve citizens’ participation. Participants claimed that teachers have to play a relevant part in fostering a more inclusive society.

Students

TOPIC d) Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences							
	Aim of the awareness-raising initiative	Promoting organization	Level of intervention	Field of intervention	Audience (targeted and real)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social impact
TD	YARA I remember from high school that we had like a day when all the women, all the girls were able to participate in some kind of a women’s day in specifically to technical youths of research because there are some, they are underrepresented. There is mostly a male dominant field, and it was all of the girls were able to join this day for free and go to different companies to learn about what they did, and we could skip the classes of the day just for this day. I didn’t participate myself, but I know that they offered it to us.	private	local/top down	education	students	medium	yes
	YARA Yes, I think maybe just like I mean I did end up in science somehow, so I guess my interest got sparked but maybe just more like I remember the things I liked about science as a child or adolescent, I think it was mostly about experiments. Those kind of things I really like to just kind of to put things together, in different color, or something exploding, I really like those kind of experiments. So, I think those kind of things where you can see what happens that it might awaken some interest but that’s for me. I don’t know if anyone else can relate to that.	private	local/bottom-up	education	students	medium	yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>GIANNIS So, I think, I remember in for example high school and elementary school there were like tournaments about physics, mathematics, and that kind of stuff. So, many kids who were very good in those sciences, those kind of courses, they really liked to take part and also, I think I have a friend at the university, they also took part in a tournament about formula one, so it's very good initiative to attract younger people with that kind of stuff, tournament, and that kind of stuff, because we give them motivation,</p>	private	local/top down	education	students	medium	yes
	<p>JULIA Yes, because I was thinking about the last year of secondary school, I think Yara knows what I mean with [dutch word] but I don't know the English translation. It was mandatory for everyone in the sixth grade to like do your own project so you could do it alone but also with someone else. You could like think of a research question and do the research yourself, not on a scientific level of course, but you got to use the resources and you had to like read all the articles and the books and then you had to come up with your... it had to be not only the experimental but also the literature, what you did and then at the end, when everyone was done, they had like a market place in the school where everyone had to present their own project. So, we were able to see what everybody did and that way you also connected what they did to what you actually could do yourself. Because it was not a scientist who did it, it was you, yourself who did some kind of research. So, I think that was the first time I connected the idea that I could be a scientist myself.</p>	public	local/top down	education	students	medium	yes
	<p>EMMA So I had to think of events that events, this university sometimes organizes, like, open day where citizens can come and they know there are, I don't know the word, they can come to the university, and there they can see examples of experiments. And it's even for children. And it's accessible for all citizens. So I had to think about events like that. I know there are I don't know the word.</p> <p>They can come to the university, and there they can see examples of variables, experiments, and intentions. And it's also, even for children. And so it's accessible for all citizens. So I had to think about events like that, yeah came across my mind.</p>	public	local/top down	education	students	medium	yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>MATEO I would like to say that, apart from from what you explained, I think the best way to promote scientists or people who like science is to show it in a cool way or location. I'm sorry, I'm a teacher. So for me, everything is related to location. So yeah, the point is not only for the students science facts to memorize, because this is boring. And it is worrying for the student. They will not be scientist and they will not be interested in science. Yeah. (...) Yeah, I think, I think one of the most important things is to have examples of people who have studied science already. Because in this way, you'll see that it's not something impossible, because you have an example, a concrete example, near to you. (...) I was thinking, for example: a friend or a sister or a brother or someone near.</p>	public	international/top down	society	citizens	high	yes
	<p>MATEO Yeah, I think one of the most important things is to have examples of people who have studied science, or something already, and make science near for you. Because in this way, you see that it's not something impossible, because you have an example, a concrete example. Near from you.</p> <p>MODERATOR You mean something like a role model? Someone?</p> <p>MATEO Yeah I was thinking, for example, in a friend, in a sister in a brother something near for someone that</p> <p>MODERATOR So you see, it's not impossible, and you can do it as well. Is that what you are saying?</p> <p>MATEO Exactly! Exactly. This is the point. Yeah. Yeah.</p>	public	international/bottom-up	society	citizens	high	yes
	<p>MARY I think it would be beneficial for students to have professionals talk to them and how they work how the profession actually is they can be educated on you know, there's a female doctor or a female microbe biologists that can can inspire people, mostly.</p>	private	local/top down	education.	students	medium	yes
	<p>ELENI Yes. For me, for mathematics students at least it's somehow different. I was good in maths, I studied maths, that's what I did, at least at school. So</p>	private	local/top down	education	students	low	yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>there is not something interesting behind this. But ignore that and to motivate the students engaged with maths. But in order to motivate students engage with maths when I teach, I'm trying to share with them some ideas of eh what are the applications of maths in real life and how they can use mathematics in general. And what I found interesting now in order to engage students is to use memes from the social media. So students use a lot of social media and pictures are there they are funny, sometimes they also have some meaning behind them. And these humans like seeing that okay, scrolling the social media one of their Facebook page or Instagram page, they can found some nice ethical topics or they can find their some meme some gifs related with mathematics. And this is something that makes you this makes students more interested for some reason. And there is some research behind that they started to investigate that a little bit how this kind of approach can facilitate students engagement with mathematics. So I think yeah, that's what I'm doing at least with the students that I did.</p>						
	<p>ELENI Yes I think they would be super nice even in subways for example or a big screen say when you go I don't know to the supermarket if a picture appears with some funny science evidence I don't know cards for decision, something like that.</p> <p>ASSISTENT-MODERATOR: Something like a campaign for example.</p> <p>ELENI Yes, a campaign that may be interesting. I don't know what let's say tomatoes appear in maths an example. So an example in the supermarket how you can have the tomatoes at your plate later this evening. With a small slide or a funny picture in your advertisement. There are ways to introduce science in everyday events, let's say in your every day in every your everyday life.</p>	public	national/ top down	society	citizens	high	yes
	<p>MATEO Yeah, yeah, yeah. Because I mean in a more concrete way in the part of Tiktok videos, I think that they would be amazing for... Because we have to take into account which population we will reach. With this apps, we will reach young people. So it's important to use them.</p>	public	national/ top down	society	citizens	high	yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	ANIKA You can use games as well to make it more interactive or as well with painting or coloring. You can make a math exercise, and then use it like that, because I used that to get a younger girl. She was 9, and she didn't want to do any school things. But she loved to draw. So then I made a clear plastic thing, a drawing that she can only make with the right exercises for mathematics. So she had to do three plus one, okay, all the four answers are green, all the six answers are red. And in that case, she was also doing math, but not feeling like she was doing math because she was painting and coloring and that was the thing she likes. So looking in different ways to learn kids the same, but using alternatives.	public	national/ top down	society	citizens	high	yes
	MATEO Yes. No. I would like to say that. Two weeks ago, I was asked for a national project in Spain. And they asked us companies in a compulsory way to disseminate our research in social fairs. Says there were I don't know how to say, like to present the results with a lot of researchers in in an open area in our media in my city. So and this was compulsory. Yeah, yeah. So this is a way to, to disseminate the results.	private	national/bottom up	science	researchers	high	no
Exclusionary dimension	YARA Hm, yes, maybe, I don't know. I didn't have like a technical program already so I had choses my courses and it wasn't technical at all so I think that maybe they should have done it earlier before we chose the courses. Because to me it was like well... all of those fields were already closed off, so it didn't feel useful to me because I didn't have the opportunity to follow those professions anyway.	private	local/bottom-up	education	students	low	no
	GIANNIS On the other hand, they exclude the rest of the kids, who are not very good on those sciences but at least you know, there is something. (...) Yes, absolutely, for sure. It would be better. If... not only after the school but during the school, I think.	private	national/topdown)	education	science	medium	yes
	KELLY Yes, I wanted to say that I really agree with what she said that the only times I learned something about research was when I read a newspapers or when I saw something on tv stating "this university found this" for example. But if you don't read the newspaper or if you don't watch the television news then you	public	internationa/bottom-up	society	researchers	low	no

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	don't actually get to know who did research. Like she said, they are like at the background, in the shadows.						
	MARY And in Greek schools, we don't get professionals coming and talking to the kids about their their jobs and how they really are. (...) Yes, in Greece, we don't even get the fireman or the police officer. We don't have career day, for example. So yes, if an initiative like that happened, especially in middle school, I'd say and maybe also in primary school, the students can aspire to become the scientists they meet. Because something in their speech or in their everyday life inspired them to, to follow a track since I don't know. They were young.	private	national/bottom-up	education	students	medium	yes
	ANIKA Yeah, I think there's too much of a focus to use the ways to teach kids the things that we know from before, like, there's only that way you do it the good way. And I don't think that's the case. MODERATOR So you say actually, that it should be interesting to the people. And maybe that's also with the initiatives to get new recruitment, maybe. Also, it should be interesting. ANIKA Yeah, because for each case, something else works.	private	national/bottom-up	education	students	medium	yes
	JULIA And what I was thinking when I saw the question about "what are some initiatives or actions" I was thinking that they might not be aware because it's all so in the background, the whole scientific world. You see singers, you see on the street builders and that is really in your face but people who are in the scientific world, they are all so far away from the vision from everyone in society.	public	international/ bottom-up	society	researchers	medium	yes

4.5. Conclusion

Finally, this section presents a summary of the main findings (gender):

Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group

- Based on their personal experience, respondents recollected and discussed a wide range of awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation. These included various university outreach activities, Open Days, Science Festivals, Women in Science Days, Science Museums, popular science shows, Citizen Science websites, online lectures and talks, and numerous individual projects that sought to involve citizens as public contributors.
- Although participants spoke of such initiatives and their experiences rather enthusiastically, there was an agreement that people who participated in them were often the same type of people, or “the usual suspects”. Participants acknowledged a challenge in getting involved those people who are excluded from science or do not show much interest in science. The most salient barrier to widening participation was perceived to be a lack of plain English summary of research.
- Although participants acknowledged the importance of awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, they were able to provide only a limited number of examples. In particular, these included actions by local authorities, universities, and professional associations. One participant also mentioned the adverse effects of such actions, namely pressure on women to participate in such actions.

Member of LGBTQI group

- Participants did not feel entitled to discuss this topic. They did not feel comfortable with speaking about a topic in which they do not manage any relevant information, nor they have any working experience or perception about it.

Women (including young women) from a women's group

- The relationship with science of the participants is informed by both their daily life experiences — even those that pass through the bodies (e.g., a disease) — and their interest and curiosity towards scientific research, in particular when they are involved in political activism.
- Participants showed a different degree of awareness in relation to the issues addressed during focus groups. Particularly discussed among the various topics was that related to the impact of scientific research on their daily lives.
- Their interventions focused more on “the transformative dimension”, but they were able to highlight both the obstacles to a full participation of citizens to science and the possible risks inherent to science communication.
- They made some suggestions about possible activities with the aim at favouring the dialogue between “science and society” (inclusive communication, awareness campaign, role models, open days).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Parents

- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings encourages people to be curious, to increase the knowledge of scientific vocabulary and provides the motivation for people to transform their environment.
- Participating in Scientific Dialogic Gathering increases the awareness and interest about science results and their impact in both people involved and their environment.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings with participating family members encouraged them to attend and to promote other scientific events (gatherings, talks or conferences) in the associations/schools.
- Applying scientific evidence in the educational practices at the school increases family participation in the school or in other teachers' seminars.
- Occasional activities organised by schools or families may have an impact on or benefit some of the children and their families.
- Science is very competitive. It is hard to make it more open to the public.
- Both positive action and positive discrimination can play a part in attracting different groups to science.
- It is important that teachers play a part in fostering a more inclusive society.

Teachers

The results for this section are very limited. People mentioned generic actions as “positive discrimination action” as legislation to enforce change and improve citizens’ participation. Participants claimed that teachers have to play a relevant part in fostering a more inclusive society.

Students

- Organizing science-events in schools, where companies and professionals come to tell students about their jobs. Students can do scientific experiments or can ask questions.
- Organize an open day at the university, so people can see what it is like studying and having a career in science.
- Organizing tournaments in elementary school and high school about physics, mathematics, etc.
- Organizing research projects in secondary school, where students do research themselves.
- Role Models and examples are very important for recruiting new talent in science; students understand that becoming a scientist it is not something impossible; people they know can do it and the students themselves can do it too.
- Using the right media to reach the youth, i.e., the media they use frequently and make it more attractive.
- Let teachers make students familiar with the concept of science.
- Use more marketing tools, like campaigns, big screens in the supermarket or in subways Science representation in everyday life.
- Present the results on a fair accessible for all citizens.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

- Information about courses should be earlier in the curriculum.
- Don't exclude kids who are not good at science.
- Professionals are not coming into the schools and so they don't have someone to inspire them.
- There is too much focus on the only right way to teach children, but different things work for every person.
- Researchers are too much in the background, not visible enough and not easily accessible. The scientific world is not very visible in everyday life.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

5. Survey

5.1. Overview

The data from the survey provide us with valuable information to meet the objective of this report on the use of statistical data. Specifically, objective 4 establishes the following: Analyse the actions which succeed in fostering the recruitment of new talent for science, including their participation in the co-creation of knowledge.

The exploitation of the data was divided into four blocks. A first block addressed the sociodemographic questions; a second block focused on the questions of block four related to actions for the recruitment of new talent in science, a third block about citizens' perception of the importance of scientific research and a fourth block aimed at deepening on citizens' perception of public scientific knowledge on gender and education.

5.2. Sociodemographic questions

The total sample is 7507 cases, whose distribution by gender, as shown in the table below, shows 51.1% of women and 48.9% of men.

Gender

Table 5.1. Distribution by gender.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Women	3839	51,1	51,1	51,1
Men	3668	48,9	48,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The highest proportion of cases is found in the 35 to 49 age group, with 31.8%, followed by the 50 to 60 age group with 25.5%. We will pay special attention to young citizens as a group of particular interest, as reflected in objective one. Young people between 16 and 34 account for 24.6%, with the youngest (16 to 24 years) accounting for 7.8%.

Age

Table 5.2. Distribution by age.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
16-24	582	7,8	7,8	7,8
25-34	1261	16,8	16,8	24,6
35-49	2385	31,8	31,8	56,3
50-64	1917	25,5	25,5	81,9
+65	1362	18,1	18,1	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The distribution of the sample by country shows how Germany, Spain and France are the most represented with 13,3% the first two countries and with 13,5% the third one. That means the 40,1% of the total sample.

Country

Table 5.3. Distribution by country.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Germany	1000	13,3	13,3	13,3
Cyprus	200	2,7	2,7	16,0
Croatia	205	2,7	2,7	18,7
Slovakia	694	9,2	9,2	28,0
Spain	999	13,3	13,3	41,3
Finland	703	9,4	9,4	50,6
France	1011	13,5	13,5	64,1
Ireland	208	2,8	2,8	66,9
Italy	203	2,7	2,7	69,6
Luxemburg	200	2,7	2,7	72,2
Netherlands	686	9,1	9,1	81,4
Portugal	705	9,4	9,4	90,8
Romania	693	9,2	9,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The level of education indicates a low percentage of the population with slighter than lower secondary education, 18.6%. This same percentage in the case of the mother's level of studies increases to 51.7%. In turn, the percentage of the population with a master's degree or

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

doctorate is 16.8%. The mother's level of studies is much lower in this case, at 6.1%. The highest percentage is found among those with upper secondary education, at 25.2%.

Indicate the highest course or educational level you have completed

Table 5.4. Distribution by level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulated %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	100	1,3	1,3	1,3
Basic education	303	4,0	4,0	5,4
Lower secondary education	1000	13,3	13,3	18,7
Upper secondary education	1895	25,2	25,2	43,9
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	406	5,4	5,4	49,3
Short cycle tertiary education	446	5,9	5,9	55,3
Bachelor's degree or equivalent	1709	22,8	22,8	78,0
Master or equivalent	1080	14,4	14,4	92,4
Doctorate or equivalent	183	2,4	2,4	94,9
I do not know	221	2,9	2,9	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

What level of education does (or did) your mother have?

Table 5.5. Distribution by mother's level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	230	3,1	3,1	3,1
Basic education	2134	28,4	28,4	31,5
Lower secondary education	1518	20,2	20,2	51,7
Upper secondary education	1346	17,9	17,9	69,6
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	321	4,3	4,3	73,9
Short cycle tertiary education	325	4,3	4,3	78,2
Bachelor's degree or equivalent	611	8,1	8,1	86,4
Master or equivalent	357	4,8	4,8	91,1
Doctorate or equivalent	94	1,3	1,3	92,4
I do not know	407	5,4	5,4	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The percentages for belonging to an ethnic minority group and a religious group are low, at 7% and 8.6%, respectively. Of those surveyed, 14.8% stated that at least one of their parents was born in another country. However, slightly more surprising is the percentage of people who claim to have disabilities or medical condition that limits their daily activities, reaching the 17,1%.

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group?

Table 5.6. Distribution by ethnic minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	523	7,0	7,0	7,0
No	6439	85,8	85,8	92,7
I do not know	443	5,9	5,9	98,6
Prefer not to answer	102	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group?

Table 5.7. Distribution by religious minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	645	8,6	8,6	8,6
No	6442	85,8	85,8	94,4
I do not know	328	4,4	4,4	98,8
Prefer not to answer	92	1,2	1,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you have a disability or medical condition that limits your daily activities?

Table 5.8. Distribution by people with disabilities.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	1284	17,1	17,1	17,1
No	5924	78,9	78,9	96,0
I do not know	194	2,6	2,6	98,6
Prefer not to answer	105	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Was one of his parents born in a foreign country

Table 5.9. Distribution by people whose parents were born in a foreign country.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes one of them	605	8,1	8,1	8,1
Yes, both	502	6,7	6,7	14,7
No, none of them	6213	82,8	82,8	97,5
I do not know	135	1,8	1,8	99,3
Prefer not to answer	52	,7	,7	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

In terms of employment, it is noteworthy that practically 20% of the people surveyed are retired. The level of unemployment stands at 5.8%. Also noteworthy is the 45.7% percentage of full-time employment among the participants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your current employment status?

Table 5.10. Distribution by employment status.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Full time employee	3427	45,7	45,7	45,7
Part-time employee	637	8,5	8,5	54,1
Unemployed	438	5,8	5,8	60,0
Voluntarily unemployed	80	1,1	1,1	61,0
Student	302	4,0	4,0	65,1
Student with job	102	1,4	1,4	66,4
Retired, disabled	1478	19,7	19,7	86,1
Housewife	384	5,1	5,1	91,2
I do not know	86	1,1	1,1	92,4
Prefer not to answer	573	7,6	7,6	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Regarding employment, both in the present and the past. 21.6% of those surveyed have worked or are working in the education sector related to professions related to the education sector. Therefore, practically one out of every four persons surveyed works in education. This percentage decreases to 8.8% when referring to professions or job positions related to gender issues.

Practices (works) or has practiced (has worked in) any profession in the education sector

Table 5.11. Distribution by professional practices in the educational sector.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	1041	13,9	13,9	13,9
Yes (at the present)	577	7,7	7,7	21,6
No	5666	75,5	75,5	97,0
I do not know	145	1,9	1,9	99,0
Prefer not to answer	78	1,0	1,0	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Practices (works) or has practiced (has worked in) any profession or position in gender matters

Table 5.12. Distribution by professional practices in gender matters.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	376	5,0	5,0	5,0
Yes (at the present)	282	3,8	3,8	8,8
No	6618	88,2	88,2	96,9
I do not know	160	2,1	2,1	99,1
Prefer not to answer	71	,9	,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

30.2% of the people surveyed have a gross annual income of less than €1,043. Approximately one-third of the people surveyed have a net monthly income of at most one thousand euros.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Gross annual household income in euros

Table 5.13. Distribution by gross annual household income.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Less than 10562€	1202	16,0	16,0	16,0
Between 10562€ and 16043€	1069	14,2	14,2	30,3
Between 16043€ and 23.295€	1180	15,7	15,7	46,0
More than 23.295€	2654	35,4	35,4	81,3
I do not know	363	4,8	4,8	86,2
Prefer not to answer	1039	13,8	13,8	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

5.3. Actions for the recruiting of vulnerable groups in science

This section aims to identify those actions that succeed in recruiting new talent in science, especially among vulnerable groups. To do so, we have structured the report in two sections 1) knowledge of actions for the recruitment in science (2 questions) and 2) participation in actions for the recruitment in science.

Knowledge of actions for the recruitment in science

This section includes two questions. The first question is referred to the knowledge of actions for the recruitment in science of different target groups, including vulnerable groups, people from low SES, ethnic and religious minorities, women and LGBTI+ (“Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting... [...] in science?”). In the analysis, we can see that the proportion of respondents who know an action for the recruitment in science ranges from 20.70% in the case of LGBTI+ individuals to 33.01% in the case of women.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 14. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...?”

Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...						
	Vulnerable Groups	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	Women	LGBTI+
Yes	30,58	26,50	26,24	22,23	33,01	20,70
No	39,11	42,83	42,79	46,10	37,39	44,36
I do not know	28,01	28,52	28,55	28,83	27,45	31,69
Prefer not to answer	2,29	2,16	2,42	2,84	2,14	3,25
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

On the contrary, the proportion of respondents who expressed not knowing any action for the recruitment in science was from 37.39% in the case of women to 46.10% in religious minorities.

Figure 5.1. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...?”

The second question asks specifically for the knowledge of actions to recruit new talent in science, specifically among youth aged 16-29. The results show that more than half of the respondents (55.7%) do not know any action, while 26.3% of the respondents know actions to recruit new talent of young people in science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.15. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science?"

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	1974	26,3	26,3
No	4184	55,7	82,0
I do not know	1290	17,2	99,2
Prefer not to answer	59	0,8	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

Responses by vulnerable groups

As we have seen, the proportion of respondents who know actions to promote the recruitment in science of vulnerable groups approximately ranges from 20-30%. If we look at these data across vulnerable groups, we see some differences.

Table 5.16. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the questions "Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...?" and "Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science?", by vulnerable groups

		Participants from vulnerable target groups						
		Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities
Known actions for the recruitment in science of...	Vulnerable groups	31,95	33,33	47,08	40,76	34,74	55,64	49,30
	Women	34,23	33,33	49,14	41,24	34,52	46,85	43,88
	LGBTI+	21,05	25,49	36,25	30,37	22,85	39,77	35,35
	Youth	26,11	17,65	38,66	31,80	28,71	47,99	40,16
	Low SES	25,92	23,53	39,00	33,86	29,02	44,55	41,55
	Ethnic Minorities	26,45	29,41	41,58	33,47	29,46	45,51	41,71
	Religious Minorities	21,76	29,41	32,99	31,40	26,42	42,26	43,88

We can see that in all the actions for the recruitment in science, the responses by vulnerable groups are higher than the total. Specifically, we can observe that actions for the recruitment of women in science are the most known actions, ranging from 33.33% to 49.14%. This proportion is higher than the obtained for the total of respondents (33.01%). As for the less known actions, which are related to the recruitment of LGBTI+ people in science, the proportion across vulnerable groups is between 21.05% and 39.77%, which is still higher than the 22.70% of the total.

If we look at the results across vulnerable groups, we can observe that, in general, youth and ethnic minorities are the vulnerable groups who are more likely to know actions for the recruitment in science, ranging from 39.77% to 55.64% in the case of ethnic minorities and from 30.37% to 49.14% in the case of youth. On the contrary, LGBTI+ people and people from low SES tend to know less actions for the recruitment of different vulnerable groups in science. In this case, the proportions re

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

between 17.65% and 33.33% in the case of LGBTI+ people and between 22.85% and 34.74% in people from low socioeconomic status.

Finally, we can also observe that, in general, actions for the recruitment of people from their own vulnerable group are not among the most or least known by participants of vulnerable groups. The only exception in this line is found when analysing the proportion of women who know actions for the recruitment of women in science, which was the most known actions among women (34.23%).

Therefore, people from vulnerable groups tend to know more initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science compared with the total of respondents. The most known initiatives are those that target women in science.

The impact of interactions

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable groups with science have an impact on participating or not in initiatives or the recruitment of new talent in science. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The analysis of the first of the interactions “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” show that, across all vulnerable groups the affirmative answer to this interaction brings significant increases in the percentage of respondents who know initiatives for the recruitment of target vulnerable groups in science. This way, youth 16-24, ethnic minorities and religious minorities increase the proportion of those who know initiatives up to 25% compared with the total population of each vulnerable group, youth 25-34 and women increase the percentages up to 50% compared with the total population of each vulnerable group, people from low SES up to 100% and in some cases LGBTI+ individuals’ responses are more than the double of those obtained by the total of LGBTI+ individuals.

In general, the most known initiatives across all vulnerable groups are those who target vulnerable groups (between 45.78% and 66.67%) and women (between 46.83% and 66.67%). Aligned with the results of the previous section, respondents who belong to ethnic and religious minorities are more likely to know more initiatives for the recruitment in science. On the contrary, women are less likely to know any. Finally, in this case we can also observe that, in general, actions for the recruitment of people from their own vulnerable group are not among the most or least known by participants of vulnerable groups.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.17. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” AND YES to the questions “Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...?” and “Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science?”, by vulnerable groups

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Participants from vulnerable target groups							
		Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Known actions for the recruitment in science of...	Vulnerable groups	45,78	66,67	53,30	54,43	53,47	64,06	59,72	45,90
	Women	46,83	66,67	60,91	52,22	51,81	53,13	53,71	47,23
	LGBTI+	31,29	58,33	43,65	40,15	36,10	49,22	45,23	31,82
	Youth	41,84	25,00	49,75	47,54	48,34	64,45	57,95	42,64
	Low SES	35,60	50,00	45,69	42,86	43,50	50,78	50,88	38,59
	Ethnic Minorities	38,39	75,00	52,28	45,07	44,41	54,69	51,24	39,93
	Religious Minorities	32,73	58,33	40,10	41,38	40,94	51,56	54,06	33,96

The analysis of the second of the interactions “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” show that, in all vulnerable groups and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

initiatives this interaction impacts notable to the proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups who know actions for the recruitment of new talent in science. Generally, the impact of the interaction can be observed in increases ranging from 25% to 50%, compared with the total of populations (with and without interactions). In some cases (LGBTI+ community and people from low SES), the increase is even higher (between 50 and 100%).

In general, the most known initiatives are those who target vulnerable groups and women, ranging from 44.44% to 67.68% in the first case and from 52.12% to 61.09% in the second. Aligned with the results of the previous section, ethnic and religious minorities tend to know more initiatives for the recruitment in science. On the contrary, the, in this case women and LGBTI+ are less likely to know any. As observed in the previous interaction, actions for the recruitment of people from their own vulnerable group are in the middle of the most known initiatives by participants of each vulnerable group.

Table 5.18. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” AND YES to the questions “Do you know any actions in your surroundings for recruiting...?” and “Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science?”, by vulnerable groups

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

		Participants from vulnerable target groups							
		Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Known actions for the recruitment in science of...	Vulnerable groups	46,00	44,44	54,27	52,56	52,24	67,68	61,47	44,21
	Women	50,86	55,56	61,09	52,38	52,12	58,17	53,52	48,68
	LGBTI+	31,43	38,89	43,00	38,64	35,79	53,23	44,65	29,85
	Youth	42,48	44,44	52,90	47,25	49,25	67,30	57,49	43,85
	Low SES	38,09	44,44	47,10	44,51	43,52	57,79	53,82	39,27
	Ethnic Minorities	38,87	50,00	48,12	43,59	44,14	58,94	53,82	38,59
	Religious Minorities	31,43	50,00	37,20	38,83	39,65	56,65	55,35	32,20

Participation in actions for the recruitment in science

This section includes the answers to the question:

- Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?

The results point out that most of the respondents (81.7%) have never participated in any initiative for the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, and only 9.7% expressed having taken part in some.

Table 5.19. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?"

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	725	9,7	9,7
No	6135	81,7	91,4
I do not know	579	7,7	99,1
Prefer not to answer	68	0,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

Responses by vulnerable groups

As abovementioned, less than 10% of the respondents expressed having participated in any action to increase the participation of new talent in science. However, if we look at the results across vulnerable groups, we can see that there are differences in some of the vulnerable groups.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 5.2. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, across vulnerable groups.

If we look closer to the results by sex, they indicate that, while the total proportion of respondents who have participated in actions for the promotion of new talent was 9.7%, the percentage among women is 8.49% and 10.92% among men. In this line, the percentage among LGBTI+ people is slightly higher 11.76%.

Table 5.20. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by gender

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	8,49	10,92	11,76	3,03	9,66
No	82,46	81,21	70,59	69,70	81,72
I do not know	8,13	7,10	17,65	12,12	7,71
Prefer not to answer	0,92	0,78	0,00	15,15	0,91
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The results by the age of respondents show that youth are more likely to having participated in an initiative to increase the participation of new talent in science (19.76% in youth aged 16-24 and 16.57% in youth aged 25-34), compared with the total of 9.66%. The observed trend is that the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

proportion of participation decreases with age, with only 4.11% of the respondents aged more than 65 who have participated in initiatives of this kind.

Table 5.21. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by age

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Yes	19,76	16,57	9,48	6,21	4,11	9,66
No	66,15	72,32	80,59	86,65	92,14	81,72
I do not know	12,37	9,91	9,06	6,21	3,45	7,71
Prefer not to answer	1,72	1,19	0,88	0,94	0,29	0,91
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The analysis related to people from low socioeconomic status indicates that the proportion of people from low SES⁴ who have participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science is higher than the total (12.95% vs 9.66%).

Table 5.22. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by low SES.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Yes	12,95	9,66
No	78,38	81,72
I do not know	8,10	7,71
Prefer not to answer	0,57	0,91
Total	100,00	100,00

The results for respondents belonging to an ethnic minority group more than one third of the respondents from ethnic minorities (36.33%) have participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science, compared with the 9.66% of the total of respondents.

⁴ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.23. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for participants belonging to ethnic minorities

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	36,33	7,59	9,03	5,88	9,66
No	56,41	85,79	58,69	54,90	81,72
I do not know	6,88	6,09	31,15	12,75	7,71
Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,53	1,13	26,47	0,91
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Finally, if we look at the results of respondents belonging to a religious minority group, we can observe that almost one third of the respondents from religious minorities have participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science, compared with the 9.66% of the total.

Table 5.24. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you ever participated in any actions aimed at recruiting new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for participants belonging to religious minorities

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	29,92	7,82	7,32	4,35	9,66
No	62,79	85,33	54,88	57,61	81,72
I do not know	6,98	6,30	36,28	9,78	7,71
Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,54	1,52	28,26	0,91
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

In general, people from vulnerable groups responded that they had participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science in a higher proportion than the total of respondents.

The impact of interactions

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable groups with science have an impact on participating or not in initiatives or the recruitment of new talent in science. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The results show among women who had interacted with science through any of the two analysed interactions, the proportion of those who have participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science is more than the double than the proportion among the total of women (8.49% among the total of women, 17.37% among women who had changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families and 17.01% among women who follow a scientist on social media). Similar results are found in the LGBTI+ community. In this case, among LGBTI+ individuals who expressed that had changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, the proportion increased from 11.76% to 25.00% (increase of more than 100%). Finally, among LGBTI+ individuals who follow a scientist on social media, the proportion increased to 22.22% (and increase of almost 100%).

Table 5.25. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by gender

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE					
Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	17,37	24,66	25,00	33,33	20,63
No	75,05	70,45	41,67	66,67	72,81
I do not know	6,91	4,64	33,33	0,00	6,08
Prefer not to answer	0,67	0,24	0,00	0,00	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

Table 5.26. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by gender

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE					
Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	17,01	22,41	22,22	14,29	19,63
No	75,47	72,86	66,67	71,43	74,14
I do not know	6,90	4,48	11,11	0,00	5,75
Prefer not to answer	0,63	0,25	0,00	14,29	0,48

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

The results by the age of respondents show that among youth who expressed that changed their mind about science due to previous experiences, the proportion of those who participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent are 31.98% for youth 16-24 and 29.56% for youth 25-34. These results represent an increase between 50-100% compared with the total of youth (19.76% for those aged 16-24 and 16.57% for those 25-34). When looking at the impact of this interaction in other age groups, the percentages of increase are even higher. The results for those youth who follow a scientist on social media indicate increases of less than 50% in the case of youth 16-24 (27.65% compared with 19.76%) and more than 50% in the case of youth 25-34 (26.01% compared with 16.57%)

Table 5.27. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by age

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE						
Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Yes	31,98	29,56	21,08	12,56	9,92	20,63
No	56,85	63,55	71,67	82,19	87,19	72,81
I do not know	11,17	6,40	6,58	4,57	2,89	6,08
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,49	0,67	0,68	0,00	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

Table 5.28. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by age

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE						
Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Yes	27,65	26,01	19,27	15,30	9,40	19,63
No	63,82	67,77	74,06	78,20	88,09	74,14
I do not know	8,19	5,86	6,18	5,93	1,88	5,75

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	0,34	0,37	0,48	0,57	0,63	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

The analysis related to people from low socioeconomic status indicate that among people from low SES⁵ who changed their mind due to previous experiences with science, 25.83% had participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science (an increase of almost 100% compared with the 12.95% of the total). The results among people from low SES who follow a scientist on social media indicate similar percentages but in this case the increase is more than 100% (26.31% compared with 12.95% of the total).

Table 5.29. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by low SES

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE		
Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Yes	25,83	20,63
No	67,52	72,81
I do not know	6,04	6,08
Prefer not to answer	0,60	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

⁵ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.30. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, by low SES

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE		
Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Yes	26,31	19,63
No	66,46	74,14
I do not know	6,86	5,75
Prefer not to answer	0,37	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

The results for respondents belonging to an ethnic minority group indicate that the impact of the interaction is observed in all groups of respondents. Among those belonging to ethnic minorities, the increase is up to 50% in both interactions. This way, 51.17% of participants from ethnic minorities who changed their mind about science because something happened to them and 53.99% of participants from ethnic minorities who follow a scientist on social media, had participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science (in comparison with 36.33% of the total of ethnic minorities). In both cases, the percentage of respondents from ethnic minorities who had participated in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science are notably higher than those who do not belong to ethnic minority groups.

Table 5.31. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE					
Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	51,17	15,55	20,00	14,29	20,63
No	43,75	78,82	57,89	57,14	72,81
I do not know	5,08	5,10	22,11	21,43	6,08
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,53	0,00	7,14	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.32. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE					
Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	53,99	15,12	24,49	25,00	19,63
No	41,44	78,96	60,20	56,25	74,14
I do not know	4,18	5,54	14,29	6,25	5,75
Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,38	1,02	12,50	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
	Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
	Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

Finally, the results for belonging to a religious minority group indicate that the proportions of respondents from ethnic minority groups who had participated in initiatives for the recruitment of talent in science increase more than 50% in both interactions. Specifically, in the first interaction (“Something happened that changed their mind about science”) the increase goes from 29.92% to 47.70% and in the second interaction (“Following a scientist person on social media”) from 29.92% to 46.48%. Aligned with other vulnerable groups, participants from religious minority groups tend to participate more than participants who do not belong to religious minorities.

Table 5.33. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for belonging to religious minorities

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE					
Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	47,70	15,58	21,88	14,29	20,63
No	47,35	78,28	59,38	57,14	72,81
I do not know	4,59	5,74	18,75	14,29	6,08
Prefer not to answer	0,35	0,40	0,00	14,29	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
--	--

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
 Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

Table 5.34. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” and answers to the question “Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups?”, for belonging to religious minorities

PARTICIPATION IN INITIATIVES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF NEW TALENT IN SCIENCE

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	46,48	15,44	21,88	11,76	19,63
No	47,40	78,50	67,19	76,47	74,14
I do not know	5,50	5,62	10,94	5,88	5,75
Prefer not to answer	0,61	0,43	0,00	5,88	0,48
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Increase up to 50% compared with the total of participants
 Increase up to 100% compared with the total of participants
 Increase higher than 100% compared with the total of participants

Both interactions increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who participate in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science. The increase in most cases is approximately 100%, in comparison with the total of respondents.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

5.4. The importance of scientific research

This section is focused on the importance that respondents give to scientific research and includes two sections. The first one is related to citizens' perceptions of the benefits of scientific research in their lives and the second is referred to the investment in science.

Benefits of scientific research

This section includes the analysis to the question: "Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?" and the results show that more than three-quarter parts of the respondents (76.3%) responded affirmatively, compared with the 9.9% of those who responded the contrary.

Table 5.35. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?"

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	5730	76,3	76,3
No	743	9,9	86,2
I do not know	954	12,7	98,9
Prefer not to answer	80	1,1	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

Responses by vulnerable groups

Most of the respondents believe that scientific results can benefit citizens' lives. If we look closer at the data across vulnerable groups, we see that, in general there are not relevant differences, in comparison with the total of respondents. The only exception in this regard is in the LGBTI+ community, where the proportion of respondents who think that science benefit citizens' lives is 58.82%, compared with the 76.3% of the total.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 5.3. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, across vulnerable groups.

The results by sex show that there are no differences between men and women (77.91% vs 75.26%) Therefore, the variable “sex” does not influence the perception of the benefits of science. On the contrary the responses of the LGBTI+ community indicate that the proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who think that scientific results benefit citizens’ lives is lower 58.82%.

Table 5.36. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, by gender

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	75,26	77,91	58,82	54,55	76,33
No	9,44	10,25	19,61	9,09	9,90
I do not know	14,15	10,98	19,61	24,24	12,71
Prefer not to answer	1,15	0,86	1,96	12,12	1,07
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The results by the age of respondents show little differences in the results across respondents’ age. In this vein, 72.51% of youth aged 16-24 and 75.42% of youth aged 25-34 think that scientific results can benefit citizens’ lives. This result is very similar to the 76.33% obtained from the total population. In this case, there is no trend in the perception of the benefits of science by age.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.37. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, by age

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Yes	72,51	75,42	74,47	78,20	79,44	76,33
No	11,34	11,58	11,36	8,09	7,71	9,90
I do not know	13,23	11,74	13,25	12,68	12,48	12,71
Prefer not to answer	2,92	1,27	0,92	1,04	0,37	1,07
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

When analysing the influence of household income, we find that the proportion of respondents from low socioeconomic status who think that science benefits citizens' lives is slightly lower than the total (74.72% for participants from low SES and 76.33% for the total of participants).

Table 5.38. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?” by low SES.

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Yes	74,72	76,33
No	11,76	9,90
I do not know	12,90	12,71
Prefer not to answer	0,62	1,07
Total	100,00	100,00

Finally, the results for belonging to ethnic and religious minorities show no differences compared with the total. In this line, while the total of respondents who think that scientific results can benefit citizens is 76.33%, the results of participants from ethnic minorities are 76.10% and 76.90% in the case of religious minorities.

Table 5.39. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, for participants belonging to ethnic minorities

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	76,10	79,14	44,24	39,22	76,33
No	13,96	9,27	14,22	9,80	9,90
I do not know	8,80	10,96	40,63	21,57	12,71
Prefer not to answer	1,15	0,62	0,90	29,41	1,07
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.40. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, for participants belonging to religious minorities

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?					
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Yes	76,90	78,62	39,94	41,30	76,33
No	11,01	9,69	12,20	8,70	9,90
I do not know	11,63	11,02	46,04	19,57	12,71
Prefer not to answer	0,47	0,67	1,83	30,43	1,07
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

In general, there are no differences across vulnerable groups in the perception of the benefits of scientific research.

The impact of interactions

This section analyses the impact of interactions of respondents from vulnerable groups with science have an impact on perceiving science as beneficial for citizens' lives. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

In general, the analysis of the impact of these interactions on the perception of the benefits of science on citizens' lives points out that both interactions increase the proportion of respondents from all vulnerable groups who perceive science as beneficial for citizens. Additionally, the results show that the increase is even higher when respondents interact with science through interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks). The only exception in this line, is found among the LGBTI+ individuals who expressed that changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families (interaction 1).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 5.4. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions “ and YES to the question “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, by vulnerable groups

Now we are going to look closer at data across vulnerable groups. The first analysis is referred to the impact of these two interactions on responses by gender. While the proportion of women and LGBTI+ individuals who perceived benefits of science in citizens’ lives were 75.26% and 58.82% respectively, the proportion among those women and LGBTI+ individuals who have interacted with science show some differences. This way, the proportion of women who think that science benefit citizens is higher among those who have interacted with science; 83.97% in the case of interaction 1 and 87.15% in interaction 2. This result point to an increase in the perception of the benefits of science after interacting with science. However, in the case of the LGBTI+ community the results are moderately different. In this case, in one of the interactions (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families), the proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who perceive science as beneficial decreases (50%). On the contrary, in the second interaction (following a scientific person on social networks), the proportion increases almost a 50% compared with the total (72.22%).

Table 5.41. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, by gender

		Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?				
		Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Interaction 1	Yes	83,97	85,35	50,00	66,67	84,33
	No	8,16	8,79	25,00	0,00	8,53

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	I do not know	7,20	5,49	25,00	33,33	6,61
	Prefer not to answer	0,67	0,37	0,00	0,00	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Yes	87,15	89,46	72,22	100,00	88,19
	No	6,35	7,05	11,11	0,00	6,70
	I do not know	5,96	3,49	16,67	0,00	4,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,55	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The second analysis refers to the impact of interactions across age groups. In this line, we can see how in all age groups, the proportion of respondents who perceive the benefits of scientific research on citizens' lives grow when introducing interactions with science. Specifically, the results among youth show that, while the total proportion of youth 16-24 and 25-34 who perceive the benefits of scientific research is 72.51% and 75.42% respectively, among those who have interacted with science, they increase. This way, in the case of the first interaction (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families) the percentages are 77.66% (youth 16-24) and 82.76% (youth 25-34) and in the second interaction (following a scientist on social media), 84.98% (youth 16-24) and 88.10 (youth 25-34).

Table 5.42. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question "Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?", by age

		Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?					
		16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Interaction 1	Yes	77,66	82,76	84,82	86,76	86,78	84,33
	No	12,18	10,10	8,77	5,94	7,02	8,53

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	I do not know	9,14	6,90	5,90	6,85	5,37	6,61
	Prefer not to answer	1,02	0,25	0,51	0,46	0,83	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Yes	84,98	88,10	86,55	92,73	88,09	88,19
	No	8,87	7,33	7,88	3,06	6,58	6,70
	I do not know	5,80	4,21	5,21	4,21	5,02	4,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,34	0,37	0,36	0,00	0,31	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Among people from low SES is where we find the highest increase in the proportion of respondents who perceive the benefits of science, in comparison with other vulnerable groups. This way, while the percentage among the total of people from low SES is 74.72%, in the case of those who have interacted with science increases up to 84.59% (interaction 1: changing their mind about science due to a previous experience) and 87.53% (interaction 2: following a scientific person on social media).

Table 5.43. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, by low SES

		Low SES	TOTAL
Interaction 1	Yes	84,59	84,33
	No	8,61	8,53
	I do not know	6,34	6,61
	Prefer not to answer	0,45	0,53

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Yes	87,53	88,19
	No	8,23	6,70
	I do not know	4,11	4,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,12	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The results for respondents belonging to an ethnic minority group show similar trends. In this case, the proportion of people from ethnic minorities who perceived the benefits of science was 76.10%. If we look closer at the results by respondents from ethnic minorities who had previously interacted with science, we can see how in the case of those who changed their mind about science due to previous experiences, 80.86% perceive scientific research as beneficial for citizens' lives. Similarly, in the case of respondents from ethnic minorities who follow a scientist on social networks, 84.79% perceive so.

Table 5.44. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question "Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?", for belonging to ethnic minorities

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?						
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Interaction 1	Yes	80,86	85,84	69,47	85,71	84,33
	No	12,89	7,21	18,95	0,00	8,53
	I do not know	6,25	6,35	11,58	7,14	6,61
	Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,60	0,00	7,14	0,53

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Yes	84,79	89,81	68,37	50,00	88,19
	No	12,17	5,45	19,39	6,25	6,70
	I do not know	3,04	4,56	12,24	25,00	4,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,19	0,00	18,75	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Finally, the analysis for religious minorities shows similar results. In this case, the total proportion of respondents from religious minority groups who think that scientific research benefits citizens lives is 76.90%. If we introduce the impact of interactions, we can observe how this proportion increases up to 80.21% (interaction 1) and 82.87% (interaction 2). In this case, the two interactions have very similar results.

Table 5.45. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?”, for belonging to religious minorities

Do you think that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens?						
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Interaction 1	Yes	80,21	85,81	67,19	85,71	84,33
	No	10,60	7,92	14,06	7,14	8,53
	I do not know	8,13	5,87	18,75	0,00	6,61
	Prefer not to answer	1,06	0,40	0,00	7,14	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Interaction 2	Yes	82,87	89,66	75,00	58,82	88,19
	No	10,70	5,86	10,94	17,65	6,70
	I do not know	6,12	4,29	14,06	11,76	4,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,19	0,00	11,76	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Therefore, the analysed interactions have a notable impact on the perception of the benefits of science on citizens' lives, increasing the proportion of respondents from all vulnerable groups who perceive science as beneficial for society. Additionally, the impact is even more remarkable when respondents interact with science through interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks).

Investment in scientific research

This section includes the following questions:

- To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?
- To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?

Respondents were given four options: totally disagree, quite disagree, quite agree, and totally agree. The responses were distributed as follows:

Table 5.46. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research"

To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research		
	Your country	EU
Totally disagree	6,33	5,54
Quite disagree	5,36	5,83
Quite agree	34,25	30,69
Totally agree	44,69	48,06

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know	8,34	8,78
Prefer not to answer	1,04	1,09
Total	100,00	100,00

We can observe how almost half of the respondents totally agree that their country (44.69%) and the EU (48.06%) should increase their investment in scientific research. If we include those who agree and those who totally agree, the proportions are 78.94% of respondents who agree that their country should increase the investment in scientific research and 78.75% in the case of the EU.

Figure 5.5. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research"

Responses by vulnerable groups

Most of the respondents think that their country and also the EU should increase their investment in scientific research. This section analyses the results across all vulnerable groups.

The results by sex indicate that, on the one hand, 80.93% of men agree or totally agree that their country should increase the investment in scientific research and 80.07% in the case of the EU. On the other hand, the proportion of women is slightly lower, 77.48% in the case of the country and 77.98% in the EU. In both cases, the results are very similar to the ones obtained with the total of respondents (78.94% and 78.75%). Therefore, the variable “sex” does not influence the opinion about the investment in scientific research. On the contrary the responses of the LGBTI+ community indicate that the proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who think that their country and the EU should increase their investment in science are lower (66.66% in the case of country and 64.71% for the EU).

Table 5.47. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, by gender

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”						
		Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Your country	Totally disagree	5,92	6,76	3,92	9,09	6,33
	Quite disagree	5,66	4,79	13,73	18,18	5,36
	Quite agree	36,46	31,96	31,37	33,33	34,25
	Totally agree	41,02	48,97	35,29	15,15	44,69
	I do not know	9,86	6,62	15,69	9,09	8,34
	Prefer not to answer	1,07	0,89	0,00	15,15	1,04
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	5,03	5,93	7,84	18,18	5,54
	Quite disagree	5,90	5,71	7,84	9,09	5,83
	Quite agree	32,87	28,52	25,49	24,24	30,69
	Totally agree	45,11	51,55	39,22	21,21	48,06
	I do not know	9,96	7,32	19,61	15,15	8,78
	Prefer not to answer	1,13	0,97	0,00	12,12	1,09
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure presents the results for the gender vulnerable groups (women and LGBTI+):

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 5.6. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, by gender vulnerable groups

The results by the age show how the proportion of respondents who think that their country and the EU should increase their investment in scientific research increases with age. This way, while 15.66% and 12.20% of youth aged 16-24 totally disagree with an increase in investment in scientific research in their country and the EU, the proportion among respondents older than 65 is only 1.40% for country and 1.54% for the EU. In the same line, the total proportion of youth that agree and total agree with an increase of investment in science is 67.78% (age 16-24) and 71.05% (age 25-34) in the case of country and 67.53% (age 16-24) and 72.09% (age 25-34), while for responders older than 65 is 88.47% for the country and 87.52% for the EU.

Table 5.48. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, by age

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”							
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL	
Your country	Totally disagree	15,64	11,66	6,12	3,76	1,40	6,33
	Quite disagree	6,70	8,88	5,70	3,65	3,30	5,36
	Quite agree	35,05	33,70	34,21	34,79	33,70	34,25
	Totally agree	32,82	37,35	43,35	47,63	54,77	44,69
	I do not know	7,56	7,22	9,64	9,18	6,24	8,34
	Prefer not to answer	2,23	1,19	0,96	0,99	0,59	1,04
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	
EU	Totally disagree	12,20	9,44	5,70	3,60	1,54	5,54
	Quite disagree	9,62	9,20	5,83	4,12	3,52	5,83
	Quite agree	30,07	30,77	31,32	30,62	29,88	30,69
	Totally agree	37,46	41,32	46,29	51,12	57,64	48,06

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know	8,59	7,77	9,85	9,60	6,75	8,78
Prefer not to answer	2,06	1,51	1,01	0,94	0,66	1,09
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure shows the results for youth aged 16-24 and 25-34:

Figure 7. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, in youth

The results by household income indicate that the proportion of respondents who totally disagree with an increase of investment in scientific research is moderately higher than the total (9.29% vs 6.33% for country and 7.13% vs 5.54% for EU). The total of participants from low SES who agree with an increase of investment in science in their country is 74.86, compared with the 78.94% of the total. In the case of the EU, the proportion among people from low SES is 75.47%, compared with the 78.75%.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.49. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, by low SES

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”			
		Low SES	TOTAL
Your country	Totally disagree	9,29	6,33
	Quite disagree	6,52	5,36
	Quite agree	34,70	34,25
	Totally agree	40,16	44,69
	I do not know	8,50	8,34
	Prefer not to answer	0,84	1,04
	Total	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	7,13	5,54
	Quite disagree	7,71	5,83
	Quite agree	31,04	30,69
	Totally agree	44,43	48,06
	I do not know	8,98	8,78
	Prefer not to answer	0,70	1,09
	Total	100,00	100,00

The following figure represents the results for people from low socioeconomic status.

Figure 5.8. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, by low SES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The results for belonging to ethnic minorities show relevant differences in comparison with the total of respondents. In this line, while 6.33% of the total disagree with an increase of investment in scientific research in their country and 5.54% in the EU, the proportion among people from ethnic minorities rises to 18.74% for country and 14.15% for the EU. Therefore, only 65.96% and 66.35% agree or totally agree with an increase of investment in research, compared with the 78.94% and 78.75% of the total population.

Table 5.50. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, for participants belonging to ethnic minorities

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”						
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Your country	Totally disagree	18,74	4,71	13,32	14,71	6,33
	Quite disagree	10,13	4,72	8,35	7,84	5,36
	Quite agree	28,87	35,19	29,57	22,55	34,25
	Totally agree	37,09	47,46	18,51	22,55	44,69
	I do not know	4,59	7,19	28,67	11,76	8,34
	Prefer not to answer	0,57	0,73	1,58	20,59	1,04
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	14,15	4,40	10,16	13,73	5,54
	Quite disagree	12,24	4,99	9,93	8,82	5,83
	Quite agree	25,24	31,51	27,77	19,61	30,69
	Totally agree	41,11	50,83	21,67	23,53	48,06
	I do not know	6,31	7,53	28,67	13,73	8,78
	Prefer not to answer	0,96	0,75	1,81	20,59	1,09
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure shows the results for people from ethnic minorities:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 5.9. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, in ethnic minorities

Similar results are found among respondents from religious minorities. In this case, 18.29% and 14.73% totally disagree with increasing national and EU investment in science, compared with the 6.33% and 5.54% of the total. Therefore, the proportion of people from religious minorities who agree or totally agree with an increase of investment is 67.60% for country and 68.57% for the EU. These results are notably below those obtained with the total of respondents (78.94% and 78.75%).

Table 5.51. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, for participants belonging to religious minorities

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”						
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Your country	Totally disagree	18,29	4,77	11,89	11,96	6,33
	Quite disagree	9,15	4,81	7,62	8,70	5,36
	Quite agree	33,80	34,85	26,22	23,91	34,25
	Totally agree	33,80	47,30	21,95	19,57	44,69
	I do not know	4,50	7,50	30,79	14,13	8,34
	Prefer not to answer	0,47	0,78	1,52	21,74	1,04
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	14,73	4,28	10,06	13,04	5,54
	Quite disagree	10,70	5,12	9,76	7,61	5,83
	Quite agree	30,85	31,20	23,78	18,48	30,69
	Totally agree	37,52	50,67	23,78	26,09	48,06
	I do not know	5,43	7,92	30,79	14,13	8,78
	Prefer not to answer	0,78	0,81	1,83	20,65	1,09
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The following figure show the results for religious minorities:

Figure 5.10. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”, in religious minorities

The impact of interactions

This section analyses the impact of interactions of respondents from vulnerable groups with science have an impact on their perception of the need to increase the investment in scientific research in their country and the EU. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

If we zoom at data by sex, we find that generally the results in women and men are very similar and follow similar trends of increase and decrease compared with the total (see numbers in green/blue and in red). The total amount of women who agreed to some extent with the increase of investment in scientific research was 77.48% (country) and 77.98% (EU). The results by interactions show that in both cases, the total proportion increases (82.73% and 82.05% in the first interaction and 86.06%

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

and 84.72% in the second). Therefore, interactions with science increase the total proportion of women who agree with an increase in investment in scientific research. Regarding the LGBTI+ community only the second interaction (following a scientist on social networks) increases the total proportion of those who agree to some extent (77.78% in country and 66.66% in EU, compared with 66.67% in country and 64.71% in EU).

In addition, when looking at data from women, we observe that in the two questions (increase of investment in scientific research in the country and the EU) and the two interactions (changing their mind about science due to previous experiences and following a scientist on social networks), the extreme options (totally agree and totally disagree) increase while the middle options (quite agree and quite disagree) decrease. One possible hypothesis in this line may be that the interaction with science provide respondents with evidence to base their arguments and this way, they do not base their responses on personal opinions. For this reason, they feel more confident to answer the extreme options (totally agree and totally disagree). This trend is not always observed in the LGBTI+ community. However, due to the low number of responses, the results are not significant.

Table 5.52. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?” and “To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?”, by gender

		“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”				
		Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Interaction 1	COUNTRY					
	Totally disagree	8,45	10,50	16,67	0,00	9,38
	Quite disagree	4,89	7,08	25,00	33,33	6,02
	Quite agree	35,51	28,08	16,67	33,33	32,14
	Totally agree	47,22	51,53	33,33	33,33	48,99
	I do not know	3,36	2,32	8,33	0,00	2,93
	Prefer not to answer	0,58	0,49	0,00	0,00	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	EU					
	Totally disagree	7,39	9,40	16,67	33,33	8,37
	Quite disagree	6,05	7,94	16,67	0,00	6,93

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	Quite agree	29,17	26,13	16,67	33,33	27,77
	Totally agree	52,88	52,75	33,33	33,33	52,67
	I do not know	4,13	2,93	16,67	0,00	3,68
	Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,85	0,00	0,00	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	Totally disagree	7,99	8,71	11,11	0,00	8,34
	Quite disagree	3,92	3,24	11,11	42,86	3,75
	Quite agree	31,43	26,14	38,89	14,29	28,89
	Totally agree	52,35	59,92	38,89	42,86	55,87
	I do not know	3,76	1,99	0,00	0,00	2,87
	Prefer not to answer	0,55	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Totally disagree	6,58	6,64	11,11	14,29	6,66
	Quite disagree	4,55	5,81	16,67	28,57	5,31
	Quite agree	27,35	23,15	22,22	0,00	25,22
EU	Totally agree	57,37	61,49	44,44	57,14	59,26
	I do not know	3,53	2,74	5,56	0,00	3,15
	Prefer not to answer	0,63	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,40
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Decrease compared with the total

Increase compared with the total

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Increase more than 25% compared with the total

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Regarding young people, we can see that in all cases, the proportion of respondents who totally agree in increasing the investment in scientific research increase in comparison with the total. However, the biggest impact is achieved in youth 25-34 who interact with science following a scientist on social media (interaction 2), with percentages of 49.08% and 52.20% (which represent increases of more than 25% in comparison with 37.35% and 41.23%). It is also relevant that in most of the cases, the proportion of respondents who stated the contrary also increases when introducing the effect of interactions with science, while the proportion of respondents who expressed intermediate opinions (quite agree and quite disagree) decreases. This finding is more accentuated in interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks). One hypothesis that may explain these results is that interactions with science provide citizens with tools and scientific knowledge to base their arguments and therefore, they expressed evidence-based arguments instead of personal opinions.

As observed in the analysis by gender, the proportion of youth who agree to some extent with an increase of the investment in science increases in both interactions. Thus, while the proportion among the total of youth aged 16-24 were 67.87% (country) and 67.53% (EU), among youth who changed their mind due to previous experiences the results were 74.11% (country) and 69.03% (EU) and among those who follow a scientist on social media 77.47% (country) and 76.45% (EU). The same trend is observed among youth 25-34. In this case, the total percentages were 71.05% (country) and 72.09% (EU) and 72.41% (country) and 74.39% (EU) for interaction 1 and 77.47% (country) and 78.57% (EU) for interaction 2. Therefore, interactions with science increase the total proportion of youth who agree to some extent with an increase of investment in science and the impact of the second interaction is more notable than the first.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.53. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?” and “To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?”, by age

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”								
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL		
COUNTRY	Totally disagree	17,26	14,78	8,77	5,71	2,07	9,38	
	Quite disagree	5,58	9,11	5,56	5,48	3,31	6,02	
	Quite agree	40,61	29,06	31,70	32,19	31,40	32,14	
	Totally agree	33,50	43,35	49,92	52,97	61,57	48,99	
	I do not know	1,52	3,45	3,54	3,20	1,24	2,93	
	Prefer not to answer	1,52	0,25	0,51	0,46	0,41	0,53	
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	
Interaction 1	Totally disagree	15,23	11,58	8,94	5,48	1,24	8,37	
	Quite disagree	10,15	9,85	6,91	4,57	3,72	6,93	
	Quite agree	29,44	26,85	26,64	30,82	25,21	27,77	
	Totally agree	39,59	47,54	53,63	54,57	66,12	52,67	
	I do not know	4,57	3,69	3,20	4,34	2,89	3,68	
	Prefer not to answer	1,02	0,49	0,67	0,23	0,83	0,59	
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	
Interaction 2	COUNTRY	Totally disagree	15,36	12,45	7,27	6,12	1,25	8,34
		Quite disagree	4,10	6,78	3,03	2,10	2,82	3,75

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Quite agree	37,88	28,39	26,79	28,30	27,90	28,89
Totally agree	39,59	49,08	58,42	61,19	67,08	55,87
I do not know	2,73	2,93	4,12	2,10	0,94	2,87
Prefer not to answer	0,34	0,37	0,36	0,19	0,00	0,28
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Totally disagree	13,65	8,42	6,55	4,78	0,63	6,66
Quite disagree	6,14	9,16	4,24	3,25	4,08	5,31
Quite agree	31,06	26,37	24,12	24,47	21,94	25,22
EU Totally agree	45,39	52,20	60,97	63,86	72,10	59,26
I do not know	3,07	3,11	3,76	3,44	1,25	3,15
Prefer not to answer	0,68	0,73	0,36	0,19	0,00	0,40
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Similar trends are found in the analysis by household income. Among people from low socioeconomic status, the total proportion of those that agree to some extent with an increase of investment in science is 74.86% (country) and 75.47% (EU). When we introduce the impact of interactions, this proportion increases. Thus, among people from low SES who expressed that something happened to them of their families that changed their minds about science, 76.38% of the respondents agree to some extent with an increase of investment in science in their country and 76.74% in the EU. The impact of the second interaction is more notable, with percentages of 78.93%

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

(country) and 79.80% (EU). Therefore, in this case interactions with science also increase the total percentage of respondents from low SES who agree to some extent with an increase of investment in scientific research.

In addition, the impact of interactions with science is also perceived in an increase of the level of confidence of respondents from low SES. In this vein, we can observe how, when we introduce the impact of any of the two interactions, the extreme options (totally agree and totally disagree) increase, while the intermediate options (quite agree and quite disagree) decrease or maintain similar. The hypothesis behind this finding may be that interactions with science provides citizens with the tools and knowledge to base their arguments in scientific evidence and therefore, feel confident enough to express these evidence-based arguments instead of their personal opinions.

Table 5.54. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?” and “To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?”, by low SES

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”				
		Low SES	Total	
Interaction 1	COUNTRY	Totally disagree	13,14	9,38
		Quite disagree	6,95	6,02
		Quite agree	32,18	32,14
		Totally agree	44,26	48,99
		I do not know	2,57	2,93
		Prefer not to answer	0,91	0,53
		TOTAL	100,00	100,00
EU		Totally disagree	10,42	8,37
		Quite disagree	9,06	6,93
		Quite agree	28,55	27,77
		Totally agree	48,19	52,67

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	I do not know	3,02	3,68
	Prefer not to answer	0,76	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
Interaction 1	Totally disagree	12,97	8,34
	Quite disagree	4,86	3,75
	Quite agree	29,68	28,89
	Totally agree	49,25	55,87
	I do not know	2,62	2,87
	Prefer not to answer	0,62	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	9,60	6,66
	Quite disagree	6,98	5,31
	Quite agree	26,31	25,22
	Totally agree	53,49	59,26
	I do not know	2,87	3,15
	Prefer not to answer	0,75	0,40
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
	Increase compared with the total		Decrease compared with the total

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of ethnic minorities, interactions with science also influence the perception of the need of investment in scientific research. Thus, among people from ethnic minorities who interact with science through any of the initiatives the percentage of those who totally disagree with the increase of investment in scientific research increases notable (from 18.74% to 23.05% and 23.19% in the case of country and from 14.15% to 17.58% and 16.73% in the EU). However, although the more remarkable increases are found in the percentage of people who totally disagree with the increase of investment in scientific research, the total percentage of people who agree to some extent is approximately two thirds in the two interactions (62.5% for the country and the EU in the first interaction and 64.26% and 65.05% in the country and the EU in the second interaction). Unlike in the other vulnerable groups, these results are slightly below in comparison with the total (65.96% in the case of country and 66.35% in the case of the EU)

Table 5.55. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?” and “To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities

		“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Interaction 1	COUNTRY					
	Totally disagree	23,05	6,49	17,89	14,29	9,38
	Quite disagree	11,33	4,70	13,68	0,00	6,02
	Quite agree	25,39	33,69	27,37	21,43	32,14
	Totally agree	37,11	52,22	28,42	57,14	48,99
	I do not know	3,13	2,38	11,58	0,00	2,93
	Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,53	1,05	7,14	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
EU	Totally disagree	17,58	6,35	15,79	7,14	8,37
	Quite disagree	15,23	5,10	13,68	7,14	6,93
	Quite agree	23,83	28,72	25,26	14,29	27,77

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	Totally agree	38,67	56,45	29,47	57,14	52,67
	I do not know	4,30	2,85	14,74	7,14	3,68
	Prefer not to answer	0,39	0,53	1,05	7,14	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	Totally disagree	23,19	6,06	16,33	18,75	8,34
	Quite disagree	9,13	2,96	5,10	12,50	3,75
	Quite agree	27,38	29,26	28,57	6,25	28,89
	Totally agree	36,88	59,14	36,73	50,00	55,87
	I do not know	3,04	2,35	13,27	6,25	2,87
	Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,23	0,00	6,25	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Totally disagree	16,73	5,07	12,24	18,75	6,66
	Quite disagree	13,69	3,99	10,20	12,50	5,31
	Quite agree	22,43	25,88	21,43	6,25	25,22
EU	Totally agree	42,59	62,19	42,86	43,75	59,26
	I do not know	3,80	2,58	12,24	12,50	3,15
	Prefer not to answer	0,76	0,28	1,02	6,25	0,40
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	Increase compared with the total		
			Increases more than 25% compared with the total

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The results for respondents belonging to religious minorities are aligned with the results for ethnic minorities. In both cases and unlike in other vulnerable groups, the total proportion of respondents who agree to some extent (totally agree or quite agree) with an increase in the investment in scientific research is lower in people who interacted with science, compared with the total. In this vein, the total proportion was 67.60% in the country and 68.37% in the EU. The results by interactions show that, on the one hand, among respondents from religious minority who changed their mind about science due to previous experiences the proportions are 62.54% (country) and 61.13% (EU). On the other hand, among people from religious minorities who follow a scientist on social media the proportions are slightly below the total (65.75% for the country and 66.36% for the EU). Additionally, in most cases in both interactions, the percentage of respondents who totally disagree with an increase of investment in scientific research increases more than 25% compared with the total.

Table 5.56. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research?” and “To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research?”, for belonging to religious minorities

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”							
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	COUNTRY	Totally disagree	25,09	6,07	17,19	14,29	9,38
		Quite disagree	9,89	5,35	6,25	0,00	6,02
		Quite agree	28,62	32,94	28,13	35,71	32,14
		Totally agree	33,92	52,34	37,50	42,86	48,99
		I do not know	2,12	2,77	9,38	7,14	2,93
		Prefer not to answer	0,35	0,53	1,56	0,00	0,53
		TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

EU	Totally disagree	20,49	5,74	15,63	14,29	8,37
	Quite disagree	14,49	5,41	9,38	7,14	6,93
	Quite agree	24,03	28,65	26,56	14,29	27,77
	Totally agree	37,10	56,17	39,06	50,00	52,67
	I do not know	3,53	3,43	7,81	14,29	3,68
	Prefer not to answer	0,35	0,59	1,56	0,00	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
COUNTRY	Totally disagree	22,94	5,77	12,50	29,41	8,34
	Quite disagree	9,17	2,86	3,13	11,76	3,75
	Quite agree	28,75	29,12	28,13	5,88	28,89
	Totally agree	37,00	59,34	43,75	35,29	55,87
	I do not know	1,53	2,67	12,50	17,65	2,87
	Prefer not to answer	0,61	0,24	0,00	0,00	0,28
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Totally disagree	18,04	4,67	10,94	17,65	6,66
	Quite disagree	12,23	4,00	9,38	17,65	5,31
	Quite agree	25,69	25,36	20,31	17,65	25,22
	Totally agree	40,67	62,73	48,44	29,41	59,26
	I do not know	2,75	2,86	10,94	17,65	3,15
	Prefer not to answer	0,61	0,38	0,00	0,00	0,40
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Therefore, in gender vulnerable groups, youth and people from low SES, interactions with science increase the proportion of those who agree to some extent with increasing investment in scientific research and the increase is bigger in interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks). However, this is not the case of ethnic and religious minorities. In all cases, interactions with science have an effect in an increase of the responses “totally agree” and “totally disagree”. One underlying hypothesis that may explain this result is that interactions with science provide citizens with tools and knowledge to base their opinions on scientific arguments and therefore, they feel more confident to respond on the basis of arguments and not personal opinions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

5.5. Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence

To analyze citizens' perception about the knowledge of scientific evidence in education and gender we have introduced two questions in the questionnaire:

- What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?
- What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?

In both cases, response options included less than other countries, in the middle and more than other countries. The results to these questions show that, in both cases approximately 11% of the respondents (11.52% in education and 11.84% in gender) think that citizens in their country know more about scientific evidence on education and gender than in other EU countries. On the contrary, approximately 30% (30.64% in education and 28.81% in gender) think the opposite. In both cases, approximately 35% of the respondents place the knowledge of citizens in their country in the middle.

Table 5.57. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education/gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?"

To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research		
	Education	Gender
Less than other countries	30,64	28,81
In the middle	35,93	35,43
More than other countries	11,52	11,84
I do not know	20,61	22,35
Prefer not to answer	1,31	1,56
Total	100,00	100,00

Figure 5.11. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education/gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”

Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education

This section includes the analysis of citizens' perception of the knowledge on scientific evidence on education in their country. The questionnaire included the following question:

- What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?

Respondents were given three options: less than other countries, in the middle and more than other countries. The responses were distributed as follows:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.58. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

Perception of public knowledge on education in your country compared to other EU countries			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulate percentage
Less than other countries	2300	30,64	30,6
In the middle	2697	35,93	66,6
More than other countries	865	11,52	78,1
I do not know	1547	20,61	98,7
Prefer not to answer	98	1,31	100,0
Total	7507	100,00	100,0

As observed, only 11.52% of the respondents think that citizens in their country have a higher level of knowledge on scientific evidence on education, while 30.64% thinks the opposite. The following figure represents these responses.

Figure. 12. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

Responses by vulnerable groups

If we look closer to the data across vulnerable groups, we can see that the proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups who perceive that citizens in their country have more knowledge on scientific evidence on education ranges from 9.75% (in the case of women) to 23.53% (in the case of LGBTI+), the proportion of respondents who think that their country is in the middle is comprised between 19.61% (for LGBTI+) and 36.49% (women) and those who think that is less than other countries is between 29.41% (LGBT+) and youth (37.44%).

Figure 5.13. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?” by vulnerable groups

First, the results by sex indicate that there are not remarkable differences between men and women. On the one hand, 31.18% of men considered that citizens in their country had less, 35.59% similar and 13.19% more scientific knowledge on education than other countries. On the other hand, the results among women were 30.33% (less), 36.49% (in the middle) and 9.75% (more). The results for LGBTI+ individuals, however, indicate different trends. This way, 23.53% of LGBTI+ individuals consider that citizens in their country have more scientific knowledge on education than other EU countries, compared with 19.61% who think they have similar levels of knowledge and 29.41% who think that they have less than other countries.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.59. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by gender

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Less than other countries	30,33	31,18	29,41	9,09	30,64
In the middle	36,49	35,59	19,61	33,33	35,93
More than other countries	9,75	13,19	23,53	15,15	11,52
I do not know	21,86	19,15	25,49	27,27	20,61
Prefer not to answer	1,57	0,89	1,96	15,15	1,31
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The results by the age indicate that the proportion of respondents who think that citizens in their country have less scientific knowledge on education decreases with age (37.63% for youth 16-24 and 22.69 for respondents older than 65). The same trend is observed among those who think the contrary. On the contrary, the proportion of those who perceive similar levels of knowledge increases with age (31.62% in youth 16-24 and 40.23% in the elderly).

Table 5.60. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by age

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Less than other countries	37,63	37,35	32,66	27,23	22,69	30,64
In the middle	31,62	33,54	33,92	38,24	40,23	35,93
More than other countries	14,26	12,85	11,57	10,69	10,21	11,52
I do not know	13,92	14,59	20,63	22,43	26,43	20,61
Prefer not to answer	2,58	1,67	1,22	1,41	0,44	1,31
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Regarding socioeconomic status, the analysis for this vulnerable group does not indicate relevant differences, in comparison with the total of respondents.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.61. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by low SES

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Less than other countries	33,60	30,64
In the middle	34,92	35,93
More than other countries	11,62	11,52
I do not know	18,93	20,61
Prefer not to answer	0,92	1,31
Total	100,00	100,00

The results for belonging to ethnic and religious minorities indicate the existence of differences in comparison with the total of respondents. In this line, while 11.52% of the total perceive that the level of scientific knowledge on education in their country is higher than in other EU countries, the results among ethnic and religious minorities are moderately higher (17.21% for ethnic minorities and 15.04% for religious minorities). The same happens when looking at those who perceive that the level of scientific knowledge on education in their country is lower than in other EU countries. In this vein, the results indicate that while 30.64% of the total think so, the proportion among ethnic minorities is 33.65% and among religious minorities 35.50.

Table 5.62. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, for participants belonging to ethnic and religious minorities

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country in comparison with other EU countries?			
	Ethnic minority	Religious minority	TOTAL
Less than other countries	33,65	35,50	30,64
In the middle	33,84	36,28	35,93
More than other countries	17,21	15,04	11,52
I do not know	14,34	12,25	20,61
Prefer not to answer	0,96	0,93	1,31
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00

The impact of interactions

This section analyses the impact of interactions of respondents from vulnerable groups with science have an impact on their perception of public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in their country, compared to other EU countries. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

If we look at the results by gender, we can see that, in general participants tend to respond less “I do not know” or “Prefer not to answer” and are more comfortable responding one of the three options. Therefore, the percentages of the responses “Less than other countries”, “In the middle” and “More than other countries” increase in both interactions, compared with the total of respondents within the vulnerable group. One hypothesis behind this finding is that, when citizens interact with scientific evidence feel more confident to answer based on the knowledge they have acquired in these interactions. On the contrary, when they do not interact with science, they tend to respond that they do not know. One exception in this line I found in the LGBTI+ community. However, the results are not significative due to the low number of responses (n=12 and n=18).

Table 5.63. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by gender

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?						
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	38,00	36,75	66,67	33,33	37,63
	In the middle	36,95	36,39	0,00	0,00	36,41
	More than other countries	10,27	16,73	25,00	33,33	13,22
	I do not know	13,82	9,40	0,00	33,33	11,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,96	0,73	8,33	0,00	0,91
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	36,21	35,60	27,78	14,29	35,79
	In the middle	40,60	39,25	16,67	57,14	39,82
	More than other countries	13,17	15,85	44,44	28,57	14,72
	I do not know	9,48	9,13	11,11	0,00	9,30
	Prefer not to answer	0,55	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,36
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

In this figure we observe the abovementioned trend among women. One interesting finding in this line is that interaction 1 (Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?) has a greater impact on increasing the proportion of respondents who think that citizens in their country have lower levels of knowledge of scientific evidence on education, compared with other EU countries, while interaction 2 (Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?) has a greater impact in the responses “In the middle” and “More than other countries”

Figure 5.14. Distribution of responses from women to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?” and the two interactions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

When looking closer at data across age groups we observe the same trend. Respondents are more likely to respond any of the three response options when they have interacted with science through any of the analysed interactions and less likely to respond “I do not know” or “Prefer not to answer”. In this case, we can observe that older age group tend to increase their responses at greater extent in comparison with youth (see numbers in blue, which indicate percentages increased more than 25%).

Table 5.64. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by age

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?							
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	46,70	39,66	39,12	34,25	29,34	37,63
	In the middle	32,99	34,73	33,39	39,73	43,39	36,41
	More than other countries	10,66	15,27	14,84	11,42	11,16	13,22
	I do not know	9,14	8,87	11,80	13,47	16,12	11,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,51	1,48	0,84	1,14	0,00	0,91
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	43,34	38,28	37,09	33,46	25,08	35,79
	In the middle	33,45	38,10	37,45	42,26	50,78	39,82
	More than other countries	16,04	15,75	14,67	14,15	12,85	14,72
	I do not know	6,83	7,33	10,30	9,94	11,29	9,30
	Prefer not to answer	0,34	0,55	0,48	0,19	0,00	0,36
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

As observed in the case of gender, in younger respondents we observe how having interacted with science through interaction 1 (changing mind about science because something happened) has a more notable impact on the responses “Less than other EU countries”, while in the case of following a scientific person on social media the impact is perceived on the responses “In the middle” and “More than other countries”.

Figure 5.15. Distribution of responses from youth to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?” and the two interactions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The analysis for low socioeconomic status indicates that, as observed in other vulnerable groups, the impact of the two interactions is perceived in an increase of the three responses as well as a decrease in respondents who do not know what to answer. This finding suggests that interacting with science provides citizens with tools and knowledge to base their arguments and enhances citizens confidence to respond.

Table 5.65. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by low SES

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?			
	Low SES	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	38,67	37,63
	In the middle	36,25	36,41
	More than other countries	13,75	13,22
	I do not know	9,82	11,83
	Prefer not to answer	1,51	0,91
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	39,53	35,79
	In the middle	37,41	39,82
	More than other countries	16,08	14,72
	I do not know	6,36	9,30
	Prefer not to answer	0,62	0,36
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

In this case, in the three responses, the impact is greater in those participants who interact with science by following a scientific person on social media. It is especially relevant the increase of more than 25% of respondents who think that the level of public scientific knowledge on education in their country is more than in other EU countries (from 11.62% to 16.08%)

Figure 5.16. Distribution of responses from low SES to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?” and the two interactions

The same trend is observed in the case of respondents belonging to an ethnic minority group. In this case, respondents with interactions with science tend to respond one of the three response options instead of the option “I do not know”, as they may have more tools to feel confident enough to answer the question.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.66. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?						
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	35,16	38,39	32,63	35,71	37,63
	In the middle	34,38	37,66	24,21	21,43	36,41
	More than other countries	19,14	11,78	20,00	14,29	13,22
	I do not know	10,55	11,32	21,05	28,57	11,83
	Prefer not to answer	0,78	0,86	2,11	0,00	0,91
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	32,32	36,21	36,73	31,25	35,79
	In the middle	34,98	40,86	31,63	31,25	39,82
	More than other countries	23,57	13,76	11,22	18,75	14,72
	I do not know	8,75	8,88	18,37	18,75	9,30
	Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,28	2,04	0,00	0,36
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Figure 17. Distribution of responses from ethnic minority groups to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?” and the two interactions

Finally, the impact of interactions with science is also perceived among respondents from religious minorities. This way, the proportion of respondents who do not know or prefer not to answer decreases compared to the total of respondents from religious minorities. On the contrary, the proportion of those who think that public scientific knowledge on education in their country is lower or higher than in other countries increase. Unlike in other vulnerable groups, this is not the case of those who think that their country is in the middle and this proportion in both interactions is slightly below the obtained for the total of respondents from religious minorities (35.69% and 35.47% compared to 36.28%).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 67. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, for belonging to religious minorities

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?						
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	37,10	37,95	31,25	42,86	37,63
	In the middle	35,69	36,90	28,13	35,71	36,41
	More than other countries	16,25	12,48	15,63	21,43	13,22
	I do not know	9,54	11,95	21,88	0,00	11,83
	Prefer not to answer	1,41	0,73	3,13	0,00	0,91
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	37,92	35,46	32,81	47,06	35,79
	In the middle	35,47	40,85	29,69	35,29	39,82
	More than other countries	18,65	14,01	20,31	5,88	14,72
	I do not know	7,34	9,39	17,19	5,88	9,30
	Prefer not to answer	0,61	0,29	0,00	5,88	0,36
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

	The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group
	The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group
	The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The following figure presents this finding.

Figure 18. Distribution of responses from religious minority groups to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?” and the two interactions

To sum up, interactions with science may provide citizens with tools and knowledge that make them feel confident enough to answer any of the three response options instead of the “I do not know” or “Prefer not to answer” responses.

Citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender

This section includes the analysis of participants perception of public knowledge on scientific evidence on gender in their country. The questionnaire included the following question:

- What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Respondents were given three options: less than other countries, in the middle and more than other countries. The responses were distributed as follows:

Table 5.68. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

Perception of public knowledge on gender in your country compared to other EU countries			
	Frequence	Percentage	Accumulate percentage
Less than other countries	2163	28,8	28,8
In the middle	2660	35,4	64,2
More than other countries	889	11,8	76,1
I do not know	1678	22,4	98,4
Prefer not to answer	117	1,6	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The proportion of respondents who perceive those citizens in their country have a higher level of scientific knowledge on gender is 11.8%, while the proportion of those who think that they citizens have a lower level is almost here out od ten (28.8%). The following figure represent these results.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 19. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following question "What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?"

Responses by vulnerable groups

If we look closer to the data, we can see differences in all the vulnerable groups. In this line, the proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups who perceive that citizens in their country have more knowledge on scientific evidence on education ranges from 9.52% (in the case of women) to 19.31% (in the case of ethnic minority groups), the proportion of respondents who think that their country is in the middle is comprised between 27.45% (for LGBTI+) and 35.50% (religious minorities) and those who think that is less than other countries is between 23.53% (LGBT+) and youth (35.27%).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 520. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?” by vulnerable groups

First, the results by sex indicate that the existence of small differences between men and women. On the one hand, 37.38% of men considered that citizens in their country had less, 36.28% similar and 14.19% more scientific knowledge on gender than other countries. On the other hand, the results among women were 30.41% (less), 34.81% (in the middle) and 9.52% (more). The results for LGBTI+ individuals, however, indicate moderate differences. This way, 23.53% of LGBTI+ individuals consider that citizens in their country have less scientific knowledge on gender than other EU countries, compared with 27.45% who think they have similar levels of knowledge and 15.69% who think that they have more than other countries.

Table 5.69. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by gender

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?					
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Less than other countries	30,41	27,38	23,53	9,09	28,81
In the middle	34,81	36,28	27,45	27,27	35,43

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

More than other countries	9,52	14,19	15,69	18,18	11,84
I do not know	23,67	20,81	27,45	30,30	22,35
Prefer not to answer	1,60	1,33	5,88	15,15	1,56
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The results by the age indicate that, aligned with the results on scientific knowledge on education, the proportion of respondents who think that citizens in their country have less scientific knowledge on gender decreases with age (34.88% for youth 16-24 and 20.56% for respondents older than 65). The same trend is observed among those who think the opposite. Nevertheless, the proportion of those who perceive similar levels of knowledge increases with age (34.02% in youth 16-24 and 38.84% in the elderly).

Table 5.70. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by age

“To what extent do you agree that [...] should increase its investment in scientific research”						
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL
Less than other countries	34,88	35,45	30,40	26,50	20,56	28,81
In the middle	34,02	33,54	34,38	35,99	38,84	35,43
More han other countries	13,57	13,48	11,49	11,32	10,94	11,84
I do not know	14,43	15,70	22,35	24,47	28,93	22,35
Prefer not to answer	3,09	1,82	1,38	1,72	0,73	1,56
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

As happened in scientific knowledge on education, the results of scientific knowledge on gender for socioeconomic status does not indicate relevant differences, in comparison with the total of respondents.

Table 5.71. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, by low SES

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?		
	Low SES	TOTAL
Less than other countries	31,62	28,81
In the middle	34,35	35,43
More han other countries	12,51	11,84
I do not know	20,39	22,35
Prefer not to answer	1,14	1,56
Total	100,00	100,00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The main difference for belonging to ethnic and religious minorities can be observed in the proportion of those who perceive that the level of scientific knowledge on gender in their country is higher than in other EU countries (11.84% in the total of population and 19.31% and 16.12% in ethnic and religious minorities). The proportion of those who perceive similar or lower levels are less remarkable in comparison with the total of respondents.

Table 5.72. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following questions “What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?”, for participants belonging to ethnic and religious minorities

What is your perception about the citizen knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country in comparison with other EU countries?			
	Ethnic minority	Religious minority	TOTAL
Less than other countries	31,55	31,63	28,81
In the middle	31,74	35,50	35,43
More han other countries	19,31	16,12	11,84
I do not know	16,06	15,50	22,35
Prefer not to answer	1,34	1,24	1,56
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00

The impact of interactions

This section aims to identify the impact of two interactions on respondents' perception of public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in their country, compared to other EU countries. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

The impact of interactions by gender shows that, in most cases, participants respond less “I do not know” or “Prefer not to answer” and tend to respond one of the three options. Therefore, aligned with the findings of the previous section, the percentages of the responses “Less than other countries”, “In the middle” and “More than other countries” increase, compared with the total of respondents within the vulnerable group. The underlying reason behind this finding may be that, through interactions with science citizens acquire scientific tools and arguments to respond and feel more confident to answer based on the knowledge they have acquired in these interactions. One exception in this line is found in the LGBTI+ community. However, the low number of responses make these results not significant (n=12 and n=18). Finally, it is important to remark that in interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social media), the highest increase is observed in those participants across all gender groups who think that the level of public scientific knowledge on gender in their country is higher than other EU countries.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.73. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by gender

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?						
	Woman	Man	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	38,58	31,87	41,67	0,00	35,61
	In the middle	34,36	38,10	25,00	0,00	35,87
	More than other countries	10,27	17,46	8,33	66,67	13,49
	I do not know	15,83	11,48	8,33	33,33	13,91
	Prefer not to answer	0,96	1,10	16,67	0,00	1,12
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	36,52	31,12	22,22	14,29	33,76
	In the middle	38,40	40,00	33,33	42,86	39,15
	More than other countries	12,30	17,76	27,78	42,86	15,12
	I do not know	11,99	10,46	11,11	0,00	11,21
	Prefer not to answer	0,78	0,66	5,56	0,00	0,76
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

This figure represents the results among women. In this case, the percentages obtained in the three options of response increase when interacting with science. This way, interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families) has a notable impact in increasing in more than 25% the percentage of “Less than other countries”. In the other two options of response, the greater impact is achieved in interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social media).

Figure 5.21. Respondents from religious minorities who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

If we look at data across age groups, we observe the same trend. Respondents across all age groups are more likely to respond any of the three response options when they have interacted with science through any of the two interactions and less likely to respond, “I do not know” or “Prefer not to answer”.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.74. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by age

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?							
	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	44,16	36,70	37,27	34,02	25,62	35,61
	In the middle	30,46	37,68	33,90	38,13	38,02	35,87
	More than other countries	13,71	14,29	14,00	11,64	14,05	13,49
	I do not know	10,66	9,85	13,66	15,30	21,49	13,91
	Prefer not to answer	1,02	1,48	1,18	0,91	0,83	1,12
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	37,54	37,55	34,79	32,12	23,82	33,76
	In the middle	37,54	36,45	37,82	41,30	45,14	39,15
	More than other countries	14,68	16,30	14,42	13,58	17,87	15,12
	I do not know	8,53	8,79	12,48	12,43	12,54	11,21
	Prefer not to answer	1,71	0,92	0,48	0,57	0,63	0,76
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

As observed in the case of gender, in youth aged 16-35 we observe the impact of how having interacted with science. In this case, interaction 1 (changing mind about science because something happened) has also a more notable impact on increase of people who think that the public scientific knowledge on gender on their country is less than other EU countries. On the contrary, among those youth who follow a scientific person on social media, the impact is more perceived on the responses “In the middle” and “More than other countries”.

Figure 5.22. Youth respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

The same trend is observed in the analysis related to socioeconomic status. As observed in other vulnerable groups, the impact of the two interactions is perceived in an increase of the three responses as well as a decrease in respondents who do not know what to answer. This finding suggests that interacting with science provides citizens with tools and knowledge to base their arguments and enhances citizens confidence to respond.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 5.75. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, by low SES

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries?			
	Low SES	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	37,16	35,61
	In the middle	34,59	35,87
	More than other countries	16,47	13,49
	I do not know	10,42	13,91
	Prefer not to answer	1,36	1,12
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	37,66	33,76
	In the middle	36,78	39,15
	More than other countries	15,96	15,12
	I do not know	8,48	11,21
	Prefer not to answer	1,12	0,76
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00

	The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group
	The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group
	The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In this case, we can see that the proportion of participants who respond “More than other country” increases more than 25% in both interactions, which represents the higher proportional increase. In this case, the impacts of both interactions are very similar in the three response options.

Figure 5.23. Respondents from low SES minorities who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

Similar results can be obtained of the analysis for belonging to an ethnic minority group. However, ne particularity in this case is that, unlike in other vulnerable groups, the proportion of respondents who expressed that citizens in their country know less about scientific research on gender, compared with other EU countries.

Table 5.76. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL
Inter actio Less than other countries	32,42	36,80	25,26	35,71	35,61

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	In the middle	34,38	36,40	33,68	21,43	35,87
	More than other countries	21,09	11,98	16,84	14,29	13,49
	I do not know	10,55	13,90	21,05	28,57	13,91
	Prefer not to answer	1,56	0,93	3,16	0,00	1,12
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	Less than other countries	27,76	34,43	35,71	31,25	33,76
	In the middle	34,98	40,21	29,59	25,00	39,15
Interaction 2	More than other countries	25,10	14,14	10,20	12,50	15,12
	I do not know	11,03	10,66	20,41	31,25	11,21
	Prefer not to answer	1,14	0,56	4,08	0,00	0,76
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This figure represents the above-mentioned findings:

Figure 5.25. Respondents from ethnic minorities who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

Finally, the results for belonging to a religious minority group also point to the same direction. Interactions with science provides citizens with tools and arguments to base their responses. In this case, the results indicate that interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks) has a greater impact in this regard.

Table 5.77. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”, for belonging to religious minorities

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	TOTAL	
Interaction 1	Less than other countries	33,57	36,37	20,31	64,29	35,61
	In the middle	33,22	36,37	39,06	21,43	35,87
	More than other countries	22,26	12,08	9,38	7,14	13,49
	I do not know	9,19	14,19	29,69	7,14	13,91

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	Prefer not to answer	1,77	0,99	1,56	0,00	1,12
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Interaction 2	Less than other countries	33,33	33,79	31,25	47,06	33,76
	In the middle	36,09	40,04	32,81	11,76	39,15
	More than other countries	20,18	14,35	12,50	23,53	15,12
	I do not know	10,09	11,06	21,88	11,76	11,21
	Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,76	1,56	5,88	0,76
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The percentage has decreased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

The percentage has increased more than 25% compared to the total of people within the vulnerable group

Interaction 1: Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

Interaction 2: Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

This figure represents these results among religious minority respondents.

Figure 5.26. Respondents from religious minorities who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries?”

5.6. Interpretation of the data

When we ask whether the person knows of any initiative in his/her environment to increase the participation of vulnerable groups, when he/she states that something happened to s/he or someone in their family that made him/her change his/her mind about science or become interested in science, we see that in general there is hardly any correlation (the measures referring to nominal by nominal variables do not go beyond 0.287 - Phi - in the total of the people who responded to the survey). For women, the Phi value is 0.293, compared to 0.276 for men. The other nominal indicators show similar values (Cramer's V for women is 0.169 compared to 0.159 for men; and if we look at the contingency coefficients we see that the values are, respectively, 0.281 and 0.266). In all cases the results are significant (for men and women; for other genders this is not the case, because the sample size is not large enough). This indicates that having someone in the family to whom something related to science has happened does not seem to have a strong impact on whether the person knows (or not) of any initiative in their environment to increase the participation of vulnerable groups in science (regardless of whether they claim to be male or female).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,276	,000
		V for Cramer	,159	,000
		Contingency ratio	,266	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,459
		V for Cramer	,471	,459
		Contingency ratio	,426	,459
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,622	,326
		V for Cramer	,440	,326
		Contingency ratio	,528	,326
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,500	,827
		V for Cramer	,354	,827

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,447	,827
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,874	,019
		V for Cramer	,504	,019
		Contingency ratio	,658	,019
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,555	,337
		V for Cramer	,321	,337
		Contingency ratio	,485	,337
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

When analysing these data according to age, there do not seem to be major differences with what happens in the case of gender either: in general, the overall data indicate that there is a Phi of 0.287 (and this value does not vary much across the different age groups, as can be seen in the attached table). In all cases this data is significant.

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recorded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,233	,000
		V for Cramer	,134	,000
		Contingency ratio	,227	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,282	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,316	,000
		V for Cramer	,183	,000
		Contingency ratio	,302	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,275	,000
		V for Cramer	,159	,000
		Contingency ratio	,265	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of those who say they belong to an ethnic minority group, the result remains similar. The symmetric measures indicate that the association between knowing about an initiative in their environment to increase the participation of vulnerable groups in science and whether something has happened to someone in the family to change their mind about science or become interested in science does not have a large impact. Again we find values around 0.242 (Phi), or even lower (0.140 Cramer's V). For those who say that they do not belong to an ethnic minority group, the values are similar, so there does not seem to be a strong association either.

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,242	,000
		V for Cramer	,140	,000
		Contingency ratio	,235	,000
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,225	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,130	,000
		Contingency ratio	,220	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,317	,000
		V for Cramer	,183	,000
		Contingency ratio	,302	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,607	,000
		V for Cramer	,350	,000
		Contingency ratio	,519	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

The data indicate similar findings for people who claim to belong to religious minority groups.

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,224	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,234	,000
		V for Cramer	,135	,000
		Contingency ratio	,228	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,348	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,329	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,016
		V for Cramer	,272	,016
		Contingency ratio	,426	,016
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	V for Cramer	,166	,000
	Contingency ratio	,276	,000
N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of people who claim to belong to the SES (level 2), we see that there does seem to be a greater impact of the interaction with someone in the family who made you change your mind about science or become interested in science because something happened to him/her. In this case, Phi is 0.345 (which, although far from the value of 1.00, indicates a greater impact of this type of interaction than in the previous cases).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,149	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,345	,000
		V for Cramer	,199	,000
		Contingency ratio	,326	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,209	,000
		V for Cramer	,121	,000
		Contingency ratio	,205	,000
	N of valid cases	1180		
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,210	,000
		V for Cramer	,121	,000
		Contingency ratio	,205	,000
	N of valid cases	2654		
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,330	,000
		V for Cramer	,190	,000
		Contingency ratio	,313	,000
	N of valid cases	363		
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,384	,000
		V for Cramer	,222	,000
		Contingency ratio	,358	,000
	N of valid cases	1039		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of asking if they know of any initiative in their environment to increase the participation of vulnerable groups in science, in the case of following a scientific person or person interested in science on social networks, in this case we do see that it has a greater impact (Phi in the case of women increases to 0.314, while in the case of men it is 0.248). In both cases this is a significant association (whereas, again, in the case of other gender groups, as the number of responses was so low, they are not sufficient to produce significant results).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,314	,000
		V for Cramer	,181	,000
		Contingency ratio	,299	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,248	,000
		V for Cramer	,143	,000
		Contingency ratio	,240	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,817
		V for Cramer	,333	,817
		Contingency ratio	,426	,817

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases				
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,721	,182
		V for Cramer	,510	,182
		Contingency ratio	,585	,182
N of valid cases				
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,736	,517
		V for Cramer	,520	,517
		Contingency ratio	,593	,517
N of valid cases				
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,606	,145
		V for Cramer	,428	,145
		Contingency ratio	,518	,145
N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,861	,004
		V for Cramer	,497	,004
		Contingency ratio	,652	,004
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000
		Contingency ratio	,273	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

In contrast, in the case of age groups, in general, whether or not they participate in social networks does not have a significant impact on whether or not they are aware of initiatives in their environment to increase the participation of vulnerable groups in science. Only in the case of the 25-34 age group does there appear to be a stronger association (Phi of 0.353 and contingency coefficient of 0.333).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,249	,000
		V for Cramer	,144	,000
		Contingency ratio	,242	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,353	,000
		V for Cramer	,204	,000
		Contingency ratio	,333	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,283	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,272	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,245	,000
		V for Cramer	,142	,000
		Contingency ratio	,238	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000
		Contingency ratio	,273	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Membership or not of an ethnic minority group has hardly any discernible impact either (Phi of 0.273).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,264	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,328	,000
		V for Cramer	,189	,000
		Contingency ratio	,311	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,586	,000
		V for Cramer	,338	,000
		Contingency ratio	,506	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,273	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

Something similar happens in the case of people who claim to belong to a religious minority group: again, this does not seem to be relevant when we consider people who follow scientists or people interested in science on social networks.

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,292	,000
		V for Cramer	,168	,000
		Contingency ratio	,280	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,224	,000
		V for Cramer	,130	,000
		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
Nominal by Nominal		Phi	,318	,000

I do not know		V for Cramer	,184	,000
		Contingency ratio	,303	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,605	,000
		V for Cramer	,349	,000
		Contingency ratio	,517	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000
		Contingency ratio	,273	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

On the other hand, in the case of people who say they are in a low SES (level 2), in this case there does appear to be a greater impact (Phi of 0.322). This means that people who are low SES say that having interactions on social networks with people who are scientists or interested in science does allow them to learn about initiatives in their environment to increase their participation in science (at least moderately).

Of vulnerable groups* in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,310	,000
		V for Cramer	,179	,000
		Contingency ratio	,296	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,322	,000
		V for Cramer	,186	,000
		Contingency ratio	,306	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,181	,000
		V for Cramer	,105	,000
		Contingency ratio	,178	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,216	,000
		V for Cramer	,125	,000
		Contingency ratio	,212	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,353	,000
		V for Cramer	,204	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,333	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,384	,000
		V for Cramer	,221	,000
		Contingency ratio	,358	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000
		Contingency ratio	,273	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In contrast, gender is not revealed as a variable that has an impact on whether the interactions that people in whose families there is someone who has had something happen to make them change their mind about science or become interested in science. We cannot see that there is a strong relationship (Phi of 0.281 for females, and 0.265 for males).

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,270	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,265	,000
		V for Cramer	,153	,000
		Contingency ratio	,256	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	,495
		V for Cramer	,258	,495
		Contingency ratio	,250	,495
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,370	,802
		V for Cramer	,261	,802
		Contingency ratio	,347	,802
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,080	,136
		V for Cramer	,764	,136

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,734	,136
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,561	,515
		V for Cramer	,324	,515
		Contingency ratio	,490	,515
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,497	,518
		V for Cramer	,287	,518
		Contingency ratio	,445	,518
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Something similar happens with the age variable: in this case, age is not an aspect that has a significant impact on the impact that the interactions of people whose families have had something happen to them to change their minds about science or become interested in science. We see that in any case, for people over 35 years of age, they do show greater awareness of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in citizen science in low socio-economic environments when something has happened in their families to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,256	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,248	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,263	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,255	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,300	,000
		V for Cramer	,173	,000
		Contingency ratio	,287	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,275	,000
		V for Cramer	,159	,000
		Contingency ratio	,265	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,264	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,255	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of the variable "consider yourself belonging to an ethnic minority group", we can see that the values of the symmetric measures of association (Phi, Cramer's V and Contingency Coefficient) do not yield relevant values either. This means that belonging or not to an ethnic minority group also does not make a person more or less aware of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science from low socio-economic backgrounds.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,195	,018
		V for Cramer	,113	,018
		Contingency ratio	,192	,018
		N of valid cases	523	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,221	,000
		V for Cramer	,128	,000
		Contingency ratio	,216	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,500	,002
		V for Cramer	,289	,002
		Contingency ratio	,447	,002
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This result is similar to what happens in the case of people who claim to belong to religious minority groups. Nor do the values of the symmetric measures mean that there is a strong relationship between these variables.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Appr signi
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,237	
		V for Cramer	,137	
		Contingency ratio	,230	
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,214	
		V for Cramer	,123	
		Contingency ratio	,209	
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,308	
		V for Cramer	,178	
		Contingency ratio	,295	
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,497	
		V for Cramer	,287	
		Contingency ratio	,445	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	
		V for Cramer	,158	
		Contingency ratio	,263	
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of socio-economic status, on the other hand, we would expect a greater impact. We do see that the values of Phi, Cramer's V and Contingency Coefficient are somewhat higher than in the case of considering other vulnerable groups (such as ethnic or religious minorities, for instance). However, the data indicate that the behaviour is similar to what happens when we consider other vulnerable groups: people from low SES do not report knowing more or less about initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science by citizens from low socio-economic backgrounds than people from other socio-economic backgrounds, or from other vulnerable groups.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,248	,000
		V for Cramer	,143	,000
		Contingency ratio	,241	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,217	,000
		V for Cramer	,126	,000
		Contingency ratio	,212	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,199	,000
		V for Cramer	,115	,000
		Contingency ratio	,195	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,357	,000
		V for Cramer	,206	,000
		Contingency ratio	,336	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In contrast, as before, the type of interactions people have on social networks does have a greater impact on their awareness (or not) of initiatives to increase participation in science among citizens from lower socio-economic backgrounds than people from other socio-economic backgrounds. In this case the values of the symmetric measures (Phi, Cramer's V, and contingency coefficient) suggest that there is some relationship. For example, for women, the Phi is 0.313 (for men it is 0.268). This result suggests that for women, following a scientific person or person interested in science on social networks does have some impact on their awareness or lack of awareness of initiatives to increase participation in science.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,313	,000
		V for Cramer	,181	,000
		Contingency ratio	,299	,000
N of valid cases			3815	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,154	,000
		Contingency ratio	,258	,000
		N of valid cases	3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	,792
		V for Cramer	,258	,792
		Contingency ratio	,250	,792
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,825	,086
		V for Cramer	,583	,086
		Contingency ratio	,636	,086
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,833	,384
		V for Cramer	,589	,384
		Contingency ratio	,640	,384
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,550	,247
		V for Cramer	,389	,247
		Contingency ratio	,482	,247
		N of valid cases	26	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,981	,000
		V for Cramer	,566	,000
		Contingency ratio	,700	,000
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,285	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of different age groups, the data indicate that the younger the respondents to the survey, the greater the impact that social networks have on their awareness (or not) of initiatives to increase participation in science by citizens from lower socio-economic backgrounds than people from other socio-economic backgrounds. People aged 16-24 have a Phi of 0.313, which increases to a Phi of 0.375 for people aged 25-34. After that, the values start to decrease gradually with age. This suggests that age is indeed a relevant variable in terms of the impact of social network interactions.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science *
Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,313	,000
		V for Cramer	,181	,000
		Contingency ratio	,299	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,375	,000
		V for Cramer	,216	,000
		Contingency ratio	,351	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,290	,000
		V for Cramer	,168	,000
		Contingency ratio	,279	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,150	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,285	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

In the case of belonging (or not) to ethnic minority groups, the data are also consistent with the fact that for those who do belong to ethnic minority groups, participating (or not) in social networks explains that they are aware of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science from low socio-economic backgrounds. The phi in this case is again 0.313.

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,313	,000
		V for Cramer	,181	,000
		Contingency ratio	,299	,000
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,241	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,139	,000
		Contingency ratio	,234	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,326	,000
		V for Cramer	,188	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,555	,000
		V for Cramer	,320	,000
		Contingency ratio	,485	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,285	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In contrast, the effect (or relationship) of belonging to a religious minority group is more discrete. Being from one religious group or another does not have as much impact on whether people from lower socio-economic backgrounds are aware of initiatives to increase participation in science as people from other socio-economic backgrounds, despite using social networks.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,239	,000
		V for Cramer	,138	,000
		Contingency ratio	,233	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,338	,000
		V for Cramer	,195	,000
		Contingency ratio	,320	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,665	,000
		V for Cramer	,384	,000
		Contingency ratio	,554	,000
	N of valid cases		92	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,285	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

On the other hand, in the case of the socio-economic variable, it does seem that following scientists or people interested in science on social networks has a certain impact on whether the respondent is aware (or not) of initiatives to increase participation in science by citizens from lower socio-economic backgrounds than people from other socio-economic levels. This is especially true for the case of socio-economic level 1 (the lowest) and 2. When we talk about people with middle or high incomes, following scientists or people interested in science on social media stops having an impact. This means that social networks are a gateway to science for people with low SES levels.

In the science of citizenship of low socioeconomic backgrounds * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,331	,000
		V for Cramer	,191	,000
		Contingency ratio	,314	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,238	,000
		V for Cramer	,137	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,231	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,224	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,237	,000
		V for Cramer	,137	,000
		Contingency ratio	,231	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,328	,000
		V for Cramer	,189	,000
		Contingency ratio	,312	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,375	,000
		V for Cramer	,216	,000
		Contingency ratio	,351	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,285	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of knowing (or not) about initiatives to increase participation in science by ethnic minorities, we find similar results as above. Having had something happen to someone in the family, or to oneself, that makes them change their mind about science or become interested in science, does not seem to have a relevant impact, neither for men nor for women. In other words, gender does not make the relationship between these variables any stronger or weaker than it already is (which is weak).

In the science of ethnic minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,288	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,291	,000
		V for Cramer	,168	,000
		Contingency ratio	,280	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,354	,831
		V for Cramer	,354	,831
		Contingency ratio	,333	,831
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,622	,326
		V for Cramer	,440	,326
		Contingency ratio	,528	,326
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,736	,517
		V for Cramer	,520	,517
		Contingency ratio	,593	,517
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,805	,051
		V for Cramer	,465	,051
		Contingency ratio	,627	,051
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,580	,269
		V for Cramer	,335	,269
		Contingency ratio	,502	,269

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

Here too, age does not seem to have a marked impact. The data suggest that it is not a variable that has a notable impact either. Being of a particular age group or not does not change the answer to the question of whether there are known initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by minorities.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science *
Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,283	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000
		Contingency ratio	,272	,000
N of valid cases			582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,292	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,280	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,318	,000
		V for Cramer	,184	,000
		Contingency ratio	,303	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,266	,000
		V for Cramer	,154	,000
		Contingency ratio	,257	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,288	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

On the other hand, one might expect that the ethnic minority group variable would make a difference. However, the symmetric measures also do not indicate that belonging to an ethnic minority group of people who have interactions in the family that have made them more interested in science has a

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

relevant impact. We cannot claim that minority individuals, because they are minorities and have interactions with people in their family that have made them more interested in science, are more aware of initiatives to increase participation in minority science.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,277	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,267	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,230	,000
		V for Cramer	,133	,000
		Contingency ratio	,224	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,272	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,262	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Nominal by Nominal		Phi	,480	,005

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	V for Cramer		,277	,005
	Contingency ratio		,433	,005
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of people who claim to belong to religious minority groups, something similar happens: the variable "belonging to a religious minority group", even if having interactions in the family makes the respondent still feel more interested in science, does not have a noticeable impact.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,216	,000
		V for Cramer	,125	,000
		Contingency ratio	,211	,000
	N of valid cases		645	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,235	,000
		V for Cramer	,136	,000
		Contingency ratio	,229	,000
		N of valid cases	6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,364	,000
		V for Cramer	,210	,000
		Contingency ratio	,342	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,495	,007
		V for Cramer	,286	,007
		Contingency ratio	,443	,007
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

When we look at the results by SES level, we see that for people with lower incomes, there does seem to be some impact (Phi of 0.318), and the lower the income level, the greater the impact. This result suggests that having interactions with people interested in science in the family leads to greater access to science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the science of ethnic minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,318	,000
		V for Cramer	,184	,000
		Contingency ratio	,303	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,260	,000
		V for Cramer	,150	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,244	,000
		V for Cramer	,141	,000
		Contingency ratio	,237	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,211	,000
		V for Cramer	,122	,000
		Contingency ratio	,207	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,338	,000
		V for Cramer	,195	,000
		Contingency ratio	,320	,000
N of valid cases			363	
Prefer to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,350	,000
		V for Cramer	,202	,000
		Contingency ratio	,331	,000
N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

As before, following scientists or people interested in science via social media has a greater impact on whether or not they are aware of science participation initiatives, also in the case of ethnic minorities. This is especially true for women (Phi of 0.304, compared to 0.244 for men).

In the science of ethnic minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,304	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,244	,000
		V for Cramer	,141	,000
		Contingency ratio	,237	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,816	,587
		V for Cramer	,577	,587
		Contingency ratio	,632	,587
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,577	,406
		V for Cramer	,408	,406
		Contingency ratio	,500	,406
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,054	,155
		V for Cramer	,745	,155
		Contingency ratio	,725	,155

N of valid cases				
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,626	,116
		V for Cramer	,443	,116
		Contingency ratio	,531	,116
N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,987	,000
		V for Cramer	,570	,000
		Contingency ratio	,702	,000
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In the case of the age groups we see a somewhat erratic behaviour: people aged 25-34 (Phi of 0.358) are more aware of initiatives for participation in ethnic minority science than younger people (16-24, Phi of 0.272). People older than them (35 to 49) are also aware of fewer initiatives; but people aged 50 to 64 are again aware of more initiatives (Phi of 0.301). This means that age does not seem to have an important predictive value, because we cannot find a concrete associative trend.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,272	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,358	,000
		V for Cramer	,207	,000
		Contingency ratio	,337	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,263	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,254	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,301	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,288	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,242	,000
		V for Cramer	,140	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,235	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

With regard to the variable "belonging to an ethnic minority group", the data suggest that there is a low impact on whether or not people are aware of minority science participation initiatives. Minority people who follow scientists or people interested in science on networks do know more about initiatives for participation in ethnic minority science, but the relationship is low.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,309	,000
		V for Cramer	,178	,000
		Contingency ratio	,295	,000
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,219	,000

		V for Cramer	,127	,000
		Contingency ratio	,214	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,405	,000
		V for Cramer	,234	,000
		Contingency ratio	,375	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,547	,000
		V for Cramer	,316	,000
		Contingency ratio	,480	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of people who claim to be from religious minority groups, the trend is the same as before: whether or not they are from such a minority does not seem to have an impact on whether or not they are aware of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science by people from ethnic minority groups.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,282	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,218	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,368	,000
		V for Cramer	,212	,000
		Contingency ratio	,345	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,566	,001
		V for Cramer	,327	,001
		Contingency ratio	,492	,001
	N of valid cases		92	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

The trend we have seen previously of the impact that interactions on social networks have on people according to their income level (socioeconomic class) is also confirmed in this case. For people from low SES, having interactions (in this case through social networks) with scientists or people interested in science, is what makes it possible for them to have access to initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by people from ethnic minority groups.

In the science of ethnic minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,309	,000
		V for Cramer	,178	,000
		Contingency ratio	,295	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,248	,000
		V for Cramer	,143	,000
		Contingency ratio	,240	,000

	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,205	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,201	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,198	,000
		V for Cramer	,114	,000
		Contingency ratio	,194	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,327	,000
		V for Cramer	,189	,000
		Contingency ratio	,311	,000
	N of valid cases		363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,393	,000
		V for Cramer	,227	,000
		Contingency ratio	,366	,000
	N of valid cases		1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

In the case of knowing initiatives that increase participation in science by people from religious minorities, the data suggest that there is little impact of family interactions, regardless of the gender of the survey respondent (Phi for women of 0.288 and 0.263 for men).

In the science of religious minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,288	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,263	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,254	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	,792

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,258	,792
		Contingency ratio	,250	,792
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,370	,802
		V for Cramer	,261	,802
		Contingency ratio	,347	,802
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,500	,472
		V for Cramer	,500	,472
		Contingency ratio	,447	,472
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,673	,226
		V for Cramer	,389	,226
		Contingency ratio	,559	,226
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,523	,436
		V for Cramer	,302	,436
		Contingency ratio	,463	,436
		N of valid cases	33	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,278	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	V for Cramer	,160	,000
	Contingency ratio	,268	,000
N of valid cases		7507	

Nor do the data by age group seem to provide any evidence that interactions change anything (or not) about the knowledge of ace in the environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities.

In the science of religious minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science *
Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,154	,000
		Contingency ratio	,258	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	

35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,301	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,288	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,266	,000
		V for Cramer	,154	,000
		Contingency ratio	,257	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,290	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,278	,000
	N of valid cases		1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,278	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,268	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of people who say they are from ethnic minority groups, we do see that the data indicate a certain impact of having interactions in the family on science topics. People who say that they are from ethnic minorities have a Phi of 0.302, which indicates that there is some relationship between being from an ethnic minority group and knowing about initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the science of religious minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,302	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,289	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,222	,000
		V for Cramer	,128	,000
		Contingency ratio	,216	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,263	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,254	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,476	,006
		V for Cramer	,275	,006
		Contingency ratio	,430	,006

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,278	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,268	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

One would expect that the variable "belonging to a religious minority group" would also have some impact, but the data suggest that it does not, as can be seen in the table below.

In the science of religious minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,240	,000
		V for Cramer	,139	,000
		Contingency ratio	,234	,000
N of valid cases			645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,218	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,315	,000
		V for Cramer	,182	,000
		Contingency ratio	,300	,000
N of valid cases			328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,487	,009
		V for Cramer	,281	,009
		Contingency ratio	,438	,009
N of valid cases			92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,278	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,268	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

We also do not find relevant impacts of interactions when we consider the SES level variable. The data suggest that being from one SES level group or another is not strongly related to whether interactions in the family lead to a change in knowledge about initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities.

In the science of religious minorities * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,286	,000
		V for Cramer	,165	,000
		Contingency ratio	,275	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,158	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,251	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,244	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,207	,000
		V for Cramer	,120	,000
		Contingency ratio	,203	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,353	,000
		V for Cramer	,204	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,333	,000
	N of valid cases		363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,311	,000
		V for Cramer	,180	,000
		Contingency ratio	,297	,000
	N of valid cases		1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,278	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,268	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of the impact of having interactions through social networks, the data seem to indicate that it does not have much impact on knowing about initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities. In the case of women, the Phi is 0.288 and in the case of men, it is 0.220. This suggests that survey respondents are not likely to be aware of initiatives to increase participation in science by religious minorities, despite having science interactions in the networks.

In the science of religious minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,288	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
		N of valid cases	3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,220	,000
		V for Cramer	,127	,000
		Contingency ratio	,215	,000
		N of valid cases	3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,632	,592
		V for Cramer	,447	,592
		Contingency ratio	,535	,592
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,825	,086
		V for Cramer	,583	,086
		Contingency ratio	,636	,086
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,354	,687
		V for Cramer	,354	,687
		Contingency ratio	,333	,687
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,648	,091

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,458	,091
		Contingency ratio	,544	,091
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,976	,000
		V for Cramer	,564	,000
		Contingency ratio	,699	,000
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases		7507

The same is true when considering the age group, as can be seen in the table below.

In the science of religious minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases	582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,310	,000
		V for Cramer	,179	,000
		Contingency ratio	,296	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,244	,000
		V for Cramer	,141	,000
		Contingency ratio	,237	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,244	,000
		V for Cramer	,141	,000
		Contingency ratio	,237	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,252	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of people from ethnic minorities, there does seem to be a greater sensitivity. People who say that they belong to an ethnic minority group do happen to be aware of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities and they do have interactions about science on social networks (Phi of 0.331).

In the science of religious minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,331	,000
		V for Cramer	,191	,000
		Contingency ratio	,314	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,207	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,203	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,294	,000
		V for Cramer	,170	,000
		Contingency ratio	,282	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,542	,000
		V for Cramer	,313	,000
		Contingency ratio	,477	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Again, it is surprising that when people who say they identify with religious minority groups are asked whether they are aware of initiatives in their environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities, the symmetric measures suggest that the relationship is almost non-existent, i.e. that despite interacting in social networks with scientists or people interested in science, they are not aware of initiatives that increase the participation of people from religious minorities in science.

In the science of religious minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,270	,000
		V for Cramer	,156	,000
		Contingency ratio	,261	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,207	,000
		V for Cramer	,120	,000
		Contingency ratio	,203	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,337	,000
		V for Cramer	,194	,000
		Contingency ratio	,319	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,475	,014
		V for Cramer	,274	,014
		Contingency ratio	,429	,014
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

In the case of people from different SES groups, income level also does not seem to have an effect on knowing more or less about initiatives in the environment to increase participation in science by people from religious minorities.

In the science of religious minorities * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,294	,000
		V for Cramer	,170	,000
		Contingency ratio	,282	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,227	,000
		V for Cramer	,131	,000
		Contingency ratio	,221	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,215	,000
		V for Cramer	,124	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,210	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,197	,000
		V for Cramer	,114	,000
		Contingency ratio	,194	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,309	,000
		V for Cramer	,178	,000
		Contingency ratio	,295	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,347	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,328	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,151	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

On knowing about initiatives that increase women's participation in science, having had an experience that has changed your mind about science or become interested in science (or having someone in the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

family to whom this has happened), does not seem to have an impact on whether such initiatives are known about. This is true for both women (Phi of 0.296) and men (Phi of 0.276). For other gender groups the data are not significant, probably due to the effect of the sample size (there were few respondents who said they were either trans, LGTBI+, etc.).

Of women in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,296	,000
		V for Cramer	,171	,000
		Contingency ratio	,284	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,276	,000
		V for Cramer	,160	,000
		Contingency ratio	,266	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,354	,646
		V for Cramer	,354	,646
		Contingency ratio	,333	,646

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases				
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,549	,728
		V for Cramer	,388	,728
		Contingency ratio	,481	,728
N of valid cases				
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,661	,269
		V for Cramer	,661	,269
		Contingency ratio	,552	,269
N of valid cases				
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,896	,013
		V for Cramer	,517	,013
		Contingency ratio	,667	,013
N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,412	,779
		V for Cramer	,238	,779
		Contingency ratio	,381	,779
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,289	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

On the other hand, it seems that age does have some impact: the younger one is (under 34), it seems that having someone in the family who has changed their mind about science or become interested in science does have some impact on knowing about initiatives aimed at increasing women's participation in science (in the 16-34 age group the phi is 0.302, and in the 25-34 age group the phi is 0.319; it then decreases in the following age groups).

Of women in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,302	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,289	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,319	,000
		V for Cramer	,184	,000
		Contingency ratio	,304	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,298	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,286	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,301	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,289	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,289	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

On the other hand, when considering the variable "belonging to an ethnic minority group", the data suggest that there is no relationship.

Of women in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,211	,006
		V for Cramer	,122	,006
		Contingency ratio	,206	,006
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,242	,000
		V for Cramer	,140	,000
		Contingency ratio	,235	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,255	,001
		V for Cramer	,147	,001
		Contingency ratio	,247	,001
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,546	,000
		V for Cramer	,315	,000
		Contingency ratio	,479	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,289	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,277	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

Nor can we find a link when it comes to people claiming to belong to religious minorities.

Of women in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,218	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,241	,000
		V for Cramer	,139	,000
		Contingency ratio	,234	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,494	,008
		V for Cramer	,285	,008
		Contingency ratio	,443	,008
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,289	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

However, in the case of people with low SES, we can see that having interactions with other people in their family who have changed their minds about science or become interested in science does have an impact on having access to knowledge about initiatives that increase women's participation in science.

Of women in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,315	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,182	,000
		Contingency ratio	,301	,000
		N of valid cases	1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,203	,000
		V for Cramer	,117	,000
		Contingency ratio	,199	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,217	,000
		V for Cramer	,125	,000
		Contingency ratio	,212	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,347	,000
		V for Cramer	,200	,000
		Contingency ratio	,328	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,357	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	V for Cramer		,206	,000
	Contingency ratio		,336	,000
	N of valid cases		1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,289	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,277	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

On the effect of interactions with scientists or people interested in science, through social networks, we see that it does have an impact on knowing about initiatives that increase women's participation in science. In the case of women, they have a Phi of 0.341 (compared to 0.256 for men). This means that there is a certain relationship between these variables, and this relationship is significant (as indicated by the associated significance level).

Of women in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,341	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000
		Contingency ratio	,323	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,256	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,248	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,577	,675
		V for Cramer	,408	,675
		Contingency ratio	,500	,675
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,671	,494
		V for Cramer	,474	,494
		Contingency ratio	,557	,494
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,050
		V for Cramer	1,000	,050
		Contingency ratio	,707	,050
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,672	,068
		V for Cramer	,476	,068
		Contingency ratio	,558	,068
	N of valid cases		26	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,954	,000
		V for Cramer	,551	,000
		Contingency ratio	,690	,000
	N of valid cases			
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of the age groups, it stands out that the group of people between 25 and 34 years of age has a Phi of 0.420. This means that for these people, interactions in networks with scientists or people interested in science do have a bearing on whether or not they are aware of initiatives that increase women's participation in science. This relationship is also relevant for 16-24 year olds (Phi of 0.365).

Of women in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,365	,000
		V for Cramer	,211	,000
		Contingency ratio	,343	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		N of valid cases	582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,420	,000
		V for Cramer	,243	,000
		Contingency ratio	,387	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,286	,000
		V for Cramer	,165	,000
		Contingency ratio	,275	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,279	,000
		V for Cramer	,161	,000
		Contingency ratio	,269	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,280	,000
		V for Cramer	,161	,000
		Contingency ratio	,269	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

In the case of the variable "belonging to an ethnic minority group", the data indicate that this is not a variable that has little impact.

Of women in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Appr signi
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	
		V for Cramer	,158	
		Contingency ratio	,263	
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	
		V for Cramer	,149	
		Contingency ratio	,250	
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,395	
		V for Cramer	,228	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,367	
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,526	
		V for Cramer	,304	
		Contingency ratio	,465	
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	
		V for Cramer	,177	
		Contingency ratio	,293	
		N of valid cases	7507	

Something similar occurs with the variable "belonging to a religious minority group". It is hardly related to knowing or not knowing about initiatives that increase women's participation in science, not even taking into account having interactions with scientists or people interested in science through social networks.

Of women in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,227	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,131	,000
		Contingency ratio	,222	,000
		N of valid cases	645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,261	,000
		V for Cramer	,150	,000
		Contingency ratio	,252	,000
		N of valid cases	6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,457	,000
		V for Cramer	,264	,000
		Contingency ratio	,416	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,658	,000
		V for Cramer	,380	,000
		Contingency ratio	,550	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of people with lower income levels, as before, we see that for people with lower income levels, participating in social networks and following scientists or people interested in science is a way of accessing information and learning about initiatives that increase women's participation in science.

Of women in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,387	,000
		V for Cramer	,223	,000
		Contingency ratio	,361	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,265	,000
		V for Cramer	,153	,000
		Contingency ratio	,256	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,222	,000
		V for Cramer	,128	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,249	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,144	,000
		Contingency ratio	,242	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,339	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,321	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,383	,000
		V for Cramer	,221	,000
		Contingency ratio	,358	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of LGBTQI people, the results are not significant (probably because few LGBTQI people responded to the survey). When we look at the results of whether there are known initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science, the results suggest that there is no relationship between having interactions with someone in the family who has changed their mind about science or become interested in science and gender.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,265	,000
		V for Cramer	,153	,000
		Contingency ratio	,256	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,354	,831
		V for Cramer	,354	,831
		Contingency ratio	,333	,831
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,622	,591
		V for Cramer	,440	,591
		Contingency ratio	,528	,591
	N of valid cases			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,173	,083
		V for Cramer	,829	,083
		Contingency ratio	,761	,083
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,751	,101
		V for Cramer	,433	,101
		Contingency ratio	,600	,101
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,613	,191
		V for Cramer	,354	,191
		Contingency ratio	,523	,191
	N of valid cases			
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

With respect to age groups, the results also do not seem to suggest that they have a noticeable impact on whether or not they are aware of initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
*** Recoded age**

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,299	,000
		V for Cramer	,173	,000
		Contingency ratio	,287	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,264	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,255	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,291	,000
		V for Cramer	,168	,000
		Contingency ratio	,280	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,266	,000
		V for Cramer	,153	,000
		Contingency ratio	,257	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,236	,000
		V for Cramer	,136	,000
		Contingency ratio	,230	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

The same is true for "belonging to an ethnic minority group". As can be seen below, the results suggest that there is almost no relationship between having someone in the family who has had something happen to change their mind about science or become interested in science, and knowing about initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science.

**From the LGBTQI community in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
* Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group**

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,232	,001
		V for Cramer	,134	,001
		Contingency ratio	,226	,001

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,199	,000
		V for Cramer	,115	,000
		Contingency ratio	,195	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,351	,000
		V for Cramer	,203	,000
		Contingency ratio	,331	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,607	,000
		V for Cramer	,351	,000
		Contingency ratio	,519	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

The same is true for those who claim to belong to a religious minority group.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

From the LGBTQI community in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
*** Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group**

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,213	,000
		V for Cramer	,123	,000
		Contingency ratio	,208	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,327	,000
		V for Cramer	,189	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,496	,007
		V for Cramer	,286	,007
		Contingency ratio	,444	,007

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

Again, we find somewhat more of a relationship when we consider survey respondents according to their level of SES. Respondents who report being in the lowest income bracket have the highest Phi (0.306), which confirms our interpretation of the impact of the SES variable on having access to information about initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
N of valid cases			1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,286	,000
		V for Cramer	,165	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,275	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,226	,000
		V for Cramer	,130	,000
		Contingency ratio	,220	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,185	,000
		V for Cramer	,107	,000
		Contingency ratio	,182	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,271	,002
		V for Cramer	,156	,002
		Contingency ratio	,261	,002
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,357	,000
		V for Cramer	,206	,000
		Contingency ratio	,336	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,260	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of having interactions through social media, it also does not seem to have a large impact on knowing (or not) about initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science. The data suggest that the effect is small (Phi of 0.295).

From the LGBTQI community in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,295	,000
		V for Cramer	,170	,000
		Contingency ratio	,283	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,207	,000
		V for Cramer	,120	,000
		Contingency ratio	,203	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,816	,587
		V for Cramer	,577	,587
		Contingency ratio	,632	,587

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases				
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,721	,397
		V for Cramer	,510	,397
		Contingency ratio	,585	,397
N of valid cases				
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,882	,323
		V for Cramer	,624	,323
		Contingency ratio	,661	,323
N of valid cases				
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,641	,098
		V for Cramer	,453	,098
		Contingency ratio	,540	,098
N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,894	,002
		V for Cramer	,516	,002
		Contingency ratio	,666	,002
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

Age also does not seem to have a relevant impact on whether or not initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science are known or unknown. The data in the table below indicate that the relationship between these variables in any of the age groups is low.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,298	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,286	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,348	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,329	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,225	,000
		V for Cramer	,130	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,170	,000
		V for Cramer	,098	,000
		Contingency ratio	,168	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of belonging to an ethnic minority group, it does seem that being from an ethnic minority group is somewhat related to knowing about initiatives that increase LGBTQI participation in science through social media interactions. We found a Phi of 0.341.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,341	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000
		Contingency ratio	,323	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,188	,000
		V for Cramer	,109	,000
		Contingency ratio	,185	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,342	,000
		V for Cramer	,198	,000
		Contingency ratio	,324	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,436	,022
		V for Cramer	,252	,022
		Contingency ratio	,400	,022
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,249	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

However, this relationship is not confirmed in the case of people who claim to belong to a religious minority group.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,209	,000
		V for Cramer	,120	,000
		Contingency ratio	,204	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,331	,000
		V for Cramer	,191	,000
		Contingency ratio	,315	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,532	,002
		V for Cramer	,307	,002
		Contingency ratio	,469	,002
N of valid cases			92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

The results by SES group also do not seem to provide evidence of any relevant impact on awareness of initiatives to increase LGBTQI participation in science.

From the LGBTQI community in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,286	,000
		V for Cramer	,165	,000
		Contingency ratio	,275	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,271	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,262	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,190	,000
		V for Cramer	,110	,000
		Contingency ratio	,186	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,183	,000
		V for Cramer	,106	,000
		Contingency ratio	,180	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,326	,000
		V for Cramer	,188	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
	N of valid cases		363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,355	,000
		V for Cramer	,205	,000
		Contingency ratio	,335	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,257	,000
		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

Having interactions with someone in the family who is interested in science has a relevant impact for both women (phi of 0.505) and men (phi of 0.497). In both cases, knowing someone in the family who has an interest in science is related to respondents saying that they are aware of initiatives to promote the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science.

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,505	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
N of valid cases			3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,497	,000
		V for Cramer	,287	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,445	,000
		N of valid cases	3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,459
		V for Cramer	,471	,459
		Contingency ratio	,426	,459
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,458	,641
		V for Cramer	,324	,641
		Contingency ratio	,417	,641
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,199
		V for Cramer	,707	,199
		Contingency ratio	,707	,199
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,371	,733
		V for Cramer	,262	,733
		Contingency ratio	,348	,733
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,800	,012
		V for Cramer	,462	,012

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,624	,012
		N of valid cases	33	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,506	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This trend is even more pronounced when age groups are taken into account. The youngest (16-24 years) say that having someone in the family who had something happen to them that made them change their mind about science or become interested in science explains their awareness of initiatives to promote the involvement of new talent, especially young people, in science (phi of 0.657). This trend is maintained in the 25-34 age group (phi of 0.638), and also in the next age group (35-49), although somewhat less so (phi of 0.517). In any case, the results seem to suggest that interaction with someone who shows an interest in science explains the awareness of initiatives that promote new talent, especially among young people.

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,657	,000
		V for Cramer	,379	,000
		Contingency ratio	,549	,000
		N of valid cases	582	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,638	,000
		V for Cramer	,368	,000
		Contingency ratio	,538	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,517	,000
		V for Cramer	,298	,000
		Contingency ratio	,459	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,431	,000
		V for Cramer	,249	,000
		Contingency ratio	,396	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,232	,000
		V for Cramer	,134	,000
		Contingency ratio	,226	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,506	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

On the other hand, in the case of those who identify themselves as members of ethnic minority groups, belonging to such groups has less impact than the two previous variables. As can be seen below, the data reveal that the relationship is rather discrete.

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,370	,000
		V for Cramer	,214	,000
		Contingency ratio	,347	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,339	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,321	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,512	,000
		V for Cramer	,296	,000
		Contingency ratio	,456	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,852	,000
		V for Cramer	,492	,000
		Contingency ratio	,648	,000
N of valid cases			102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,506	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

The same is true for those who claim to belong to a religious minority group.

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,353	,000
		V for Cramer	,204	,000
		Contingency ratio	,333	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,343	,000
		V for Cramer	,198	,000
		Contingency ratio	,324	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,598	,000
		V for Cramer	,346	,000
		Contingency ratio	,514	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,895	,000
		V for Cramer	,517	,000
		Contingency ratio	,667	,000
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,506	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of people with the lowest income level, we also see that knowing someone in the family who has an interest in science influences whether or not they are aware of initiatives to promote the involvement of new talent, especially young people, in science. The phi value for SES level 1 (0.529), and the marked trend that in the following SES groups the phi value decreases, confirms this possible interpretation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,529	,000
		V for Cramer	,305	,000
		Contingency ratio	,467	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,373	,000
		V for Cramer	,215	,000
		Contingency ratio	,350	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,270	,000
		V for Cramer	,156	,000
		Contingency ratio	,261	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,328	,000
		V for Cramer	,189	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,311	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,509	,000
		V for Cramer	,294	,000
		Contingency ratio	,453	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,696	,000
		V for Cramer	,402	,000
		Contingency ratio	,572	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,506	,000
		V for Cramer	,292	,000
		Contingency ratio	,451	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of social media interactions, in this case they do not seem to have as much impact as knowing someone in the family who is interested in science. The data suggest that there is less of a relationship between following scientists or people interested in science on social media and knowing about an initiative that promotes the involvement of new talent, especially young people, in science. Although the data do reveal that there is a relationship (Phi of 0.438 for women, and 0.477 for men), it is not as high as in the case of interactions with people who feel closer to them (family members).

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,438	,000
		V for Cramer	,253	,000
		Contingency ratio	,401	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,477	,000
		V for Cramer	,275	,000
		Contingency ratio	,431	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,414	,007
		V for Cramer	1,000	,007
		Contingency ratio	,816	,007
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,622	,326
		V for Cramer	,440	,326
		Contingency ratio	,528	,326
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,833	,384

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,589	,384
		Contingency ratio	,640	,384
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,571	,076
		V for Cramer	,404	,076
		Contingency ratio	,496	,076
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,961	,000
		V for Cramer	,555	,000
		Contingency ratio	,693	,000
	N of valid cases			
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of the age groups, something similar happens: it seems that the family environment has more impact on knowing about any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science, than interactions through social networks. Here the group with the strongest relationship is 25-34 year olds (phi of 0.619), dropping to 0.577 for 16-24 year olds. Again, the data suggest that there is a relationship, but it was more significant when the interaction occurs in a close context (such as the family), rather than when it occurs in a context such as social networks.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,577	,000
		V for Cramer	,333	,000
		Contingency ratio	,500	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,619	,000
		V for Cramer	,357	,000
		Contingency ratio	,526	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,429	,000
		V for Cramer	,248	,000
		Contingency ratio	,394	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,510	,000
		V for Cramer	,294	,000
		Contingency ratio	,454	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,271	,000
		V for Cramer	,156	,000
		Contingency ratio	,261	,000
N of valid cases			1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

On the other hand, being from an ethnic minority group does seem to matter here: people who are from ethnic minority groups say that they do know of some initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science (phi of 0.617).

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,617	,000
		V for Cramer	,356	,000

		Contingency ratio	,525	,000
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000
		V for Cramer	,185	,000
		Contingency ratio	,305	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,528	,000
		V for Cramer	,305	,000
		Contingency ratio	,467	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,668	,000
		V for Cramer	,386	,000
		Contingency ratio	,556	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

However, this tendency is not confirmed in the case of people from religious minority groups. Although there is a relationship (Phi of 0.439), it is less pronounced than for people from cultural minorities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,439	,000
		V for Cramer	,253	,000
		Contingency ratio	,402	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,326	,000
		V for Cramer	,188	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,601	,000
		V for Cramer	,347	,000
		Contingency ratio	,515	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,780	,000
		V for Cramer	,450	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,615	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Finally, the variable that seems to have the least impact is income level. The Phi value in each of the groups is markedly lower than in the case of the previous variables.

Do you know of any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,378	,000
		V for Cramer	,218	,000
		Contingency ratio	,354	,000
		N of valid cases	1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,374	,000
		V for Cramer	,216	,000
		Contingency ratio	,351	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,329	,000
		V for Cramer	,190	,000
		Contingency ratio	,313	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,326	,000
		V for Cramer	,188	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,550	,000
		V for Cramer	,318	,000
		Contingency ratio	,482	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,654	,000
		V for Cramer	,377	,000
		Contingency ratio	,547	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

As regards participation in any initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, again the impact of close interaction contexts is marked (more for men than for women, as can be seen in the table below).

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
*** What is your gender**

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,518	,000
		V for Cramer	,299	,000
		Contingency ratio	,460	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,540	,000
		V for Cramer	,312	,000
		Contingency ratio	,475	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,645	,233
		V for Cramer	,645	,233

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,542	,233
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,775	,125
		V for Cramer	,548	,125
		Contingency ratio	,613	,125
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,866	,343
		V for Cramer	,612	,343
		Contingency ratio	,655	,343
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,611	,137
		V for Cramer	,432	,137
		Contingency ratio	,522	,137
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,139	,000
		V for Cramer	,658	,000
		Contingency ratio	,751	,000
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,471	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

This trend is maintained when analysing the responses according to age groups: in all groups of people aged 49 and under, the Phi value is always higher than 0.5 (in the case of the 25-34 age group it is 0.657 and in the case of 16-24 year olds it is 0.632). This means that family background has a very large impact on participation in any initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
 * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,632	,000
		V for Cramer	,365	,000
		Contingency ratio	,534	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,657	,000
		V for Cramer	,380	,000
		Contingency ratio	,549	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,517	,000
		V for Cramer	,298	,000
		Contingency ratio	,459	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,460	,000
		V for Cramer	,266	,000
		Contingency ratio	,418	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,343	,000
		V for Cramer	,198	,000
		Contingency ratio	,324	,000
	N of valid cases		1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000
		Contingency ratio	,471	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In contrast, for ethnic minorities the relationship (although it exists) is less marked, as can be seen in the table below:

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,487	,000
		V for Cramer	,281	,000
		Contingency ratio	,437	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,352	,000
		V for Cramer	,203	,000
		Contingency ratio	,332	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,594	,000
		V for Cramer	,343	,000
		Contingency ratio	,511	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,829	,000
		V for Cramer	,479	,000
		Contingency ratio	,638	,000
	N of valid cases		102	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000
		Contingency ratio	,471	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

The same is true for people who say they belong to religious minority groups. Although interaction in the family context is also important in terms of any initiative to increase the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, it is not as important as if we consider other variables such as age or gender.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,403	,000
		V for Cramer	,233	,000
		Contingency ratio	,374	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,346	,000
		V for Cramer	,200	,000
		Contingency ratio	,327	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,753	,000
		V for Cramer	,435	,000
		Contingency ratio	,601	,000
N of valid cases			328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,809	,000
		V for Cramer	,467	,000
		Contingency ratio	,629	,000
N of valid cases			92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000
		Contingency ratio	,471	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In the case of SES level, it also seems to be related to being aware of some initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups. However, here the relationship is more erratic, in the sense that we cannot find a linear trend between having more (or less) income and knowing (or not knowing) about some initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
 * Household Annual Income in Euros

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,508	,000
		V for Cramer	,293	,000
		Contingency ratio	,453	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,283	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000
		Contingency ratio	,272	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,445	,000
		V for Cramer	,257	,000
		Contingency ratio	,407	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,386	,000
		V for Cramer	,223	,000
		Contingency ratio	,360	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,651	,000
		V for Cramer	,376	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,545	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,650	,000
		V for Cramer	,375	,000
		Contingency ratio	,545	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000
		Contingency ratio	,471	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

As before, it seems that the (closer) family context also explains the tendency to participate (or not) in some initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups. People who interact through social networks with scientists or with people who say they are interested in science are less likely to say that they participate in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, than those who have someone in the family who has changed their way of thinking about science. This does not mean that there is no relationship, but that the relationship is less marked.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Approximate significance
What is your gender		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,397	,000
		V for Cramer	,229	,000
		Contingency ratio	,369	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,136
		V for Cramer	,707	,136
		Contingency ratio	,707	,136
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,507	,544
		V for Cramer	,359	,544
		Contingency ratio	,452	,544
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,913	,287
		V for Cramer	,645	,287
		Contingency ratio	,674	,287
	N of valid cases			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,477	,206
		V for Cramer	,337	,206
		Contingency ratio	,430	,206
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,104	,000
		V for Cramer	,638	,000
		Contingency ratio	,741	,000
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of age groups, the data suggest that the context of the interaction does not seem to be as influential. In both cases (either family or social media), it seems to influence participation in some initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,612	,000
		V for Cramer	,353	,000
		Contingency ratio	,522	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,000
		V for Cramer	,308	,000
		Contingency ratio	,471	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,427	,000
		V for Cramer	,247	,000
		Contingency ratio	,393	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,385	,000
		V for Cramer	,222	,000
		Contingency ratio	,360	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,265	,000
		V for Cramer	,153	,000
		Contingency ratio	,256	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In contrast, the variable "belonging to an ethnic minority group" seems to have less impact, as can be seen from the results in the table below.

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,412	,000
		V for Cramer	,238	,000
		Contingency ratio	,381	,000
N of valid cases			523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,270	,000
		V for Cramer	,156	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,261	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,486	,000
		V for Cramer	,281	,000
		Contingency ratio	,437	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,771	,000
		V for Cramer	,445	,000
		Contingency ratio	,611	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

The same applies to the variable "belonging to a religious minority group".

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,386	,000
		V for Cramer	,223	,000
		Contingency ratio	,360	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,271	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,262	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,543	,000
		V for Cramer	,313	,000
		Contingency ratio	,477	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,737	,000
		V for Cramer	,426	,000
		Contingency ratio	,593	,000
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,397	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

Finally, income level does not seem to be as strongly related to participating in any initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, as other variables above (gender, age).

Have you ever participated in an initiative aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,328	,000
		V for Cramer	,190	,000
		Contingency ratio	,312	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,328	,000
		V for Cramer	,190	,000
		Contingency ratio	,312	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,313	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,181	,000
		Contingency ratio	,298	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,282	,000
		V for Cramer	,163	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,688	,000
		V for Cramer	,397	,000
		Contingency ratio	,567	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,567	,000
		V for Cramer	,327	,000
		Contingency ratio	,493	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,433	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

On the belief that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens, the results suggest that there seems to be some relationship with living in a family context where there is someone who has changed their mind about science or become interested in science (phi of 0.427 for women, and 0.397 for men); although this relationship is not as strong as in other cases discussed above.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,427	,000
		V for Cramer	,247	,000
		Contingency ratio	,393	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,397	,000
		V for Cramer	,229	,000
		Contingency ratio	,369	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,459
		V for Cramer	,471	,459
		Contingency ratio	,426	,459
	N of valid cases			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,775	,126
		V for Cramer	,548	,126
		Contingency ratio	,612	,126
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,414	,017
		V for Cramer	1,000	,017
		Contingency ratio	,816	,017
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,492	,392
		V for Cramer	,348	,392
		Contingency ratio	,441	,392
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,862	,004
		V for Cramer	,498	,004
		Contingency ratio	,653	,004
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,423	,000
		V for Cramer	,244	,000
		Contingency ratio	,390	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In fact, looking at the results by age group, we see that people aged 16-24 or 25-34 do show a certain tendency to believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens (phi of 0.526 and 0.569 respectively). These are people who have interactions in their family circle with other family members who have changed their mind about science or become interested in science.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,526	,000
		V for Cramer	,304	,000
		Contingency ratio	,466	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,569	,000
		V for Cramer	,328	,000
		Contingency ratio	,494	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,432	,000
		V for Cramer	,249	,000
		Contingency ratio	,396	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,368	,000
		V for Cramer	,212	,000
		Contingency ratio	,345	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,172	,000
		V for Cramer	,099	,000
		Contingency ratio	,169	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,423	,000
		V for Cramer	,244	,000
		Contingency ratio	,390	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In this case, belonging to an ethnic minority group also has a relevant impact. The value of Phi is 0.621, which suggests that in the case of people from ethnic minority groups, having someone in the family who has changed their mind about science or become interested in science makes them believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,621	,000
		V for Cramer	,359	,000
		Contingency ratio	,528	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,214	,000
		V for Cramer	,123	,000
		Contingency ratio	,209	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,566	,000
		V for Cramer	,327	,000
		Contingency ratio	,493	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,751	,000
		V for Cramer	,434	,000
		Contingency ratio	,601	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,423	,000
		V for Cramer	,244	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,390	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

In contrast, in the case of people who say they belong to a religious minority group, this is completely different: the data suggest that there is no relationship between these variables. That is, whether they believe (or not) that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens has nothing to do with whether they have (or not) someone in the family who has changed their mind about science or become interested in science, nor whether they are from a religious minority group.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,195	,003
		V for Cramer	,113	,003
		Contingency ratio	,192	,003
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,247	,000
		V for Cramer	,143	,000
		Contingency ratio	,240	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
Nominal by Nominal		Phi	,584	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know		V for Cramer	,337	,000		
			Contingency ratio	,504	,000	
				N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,830	,000		
			V for Cramer	,479	,000	
				Contingency ratio	,639	,000
					N of valid cases	92
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,423	,000		
			V for Cramer	,244	,000	
				Contingency ratio	,390	,000
					N of valid cases	7507

In the case of the results by SES level, the relationship does not seem to be very strong either, as can be seen in the table below.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,336	,000

		V for Cramer	,194	,000
		Contingency ratio	,318	,000
		N of valid cases	1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,198	,000
		V for Cramer	,114	,000
		Contingency ratio	,194	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,349	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,329	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,243	,000
		V for Cramer	,140	,000
		Contingency ratio	,236	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,568	,000
		V for Cramer	,328	,000
		Contingency ratio	,494	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,566	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	V for Cramer		,327	,000
	Contingency ratio		,493	,000
N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,423	,000
		V for Cramer	,244	,000
		Contingency ratio	,390	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of changing the context of interaction towards social networks, we see that the results are very similar to what happens when the context of interaction is that of the family. The phi values are similar for both women and men. As before, in the rest of the gender groups, the fact that we hardly have trans people, non binary, etc., in the sample, means that the results for these cases are not significant.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,413	,000
		V for Cramer	,239	,000
		Contingency ratio	,382	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	

Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,389	,000
		V for Cramer	,225	,000
		Contingency ratio	,363	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,667	,539
		V for Cramer	,471	,539
		Contingency ratio	,555	,539
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,387	,772
		V for Cramer	,274	,772
		Contingency ratio	,361	,772
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,173	,083
		V for Cramer	,829	,083
		Contingency ratio	,761	,083
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,227	,854
		V for Cramer	,161	,854
		Contingency ratio	,222	,854
	N of valid cases		26	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,996	,000
		V for Cramer	,575	,000
		Contingency ratio	,706	,000
	N of valid cases			
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,419	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,386	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of age groups, we can see that among 16-24 year olds the impact of interactions on the belief that scientific results can benefit people's lives is more marked than family interactions (phi of 0.610). This trend also holds for the next age group (25-34 years); but then it gradually declines as people get older.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science *
Recorded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,610	,000
		V for Cramer	,352	,000
		Contingency ratio	,521	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		N of valid cases	582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,576	,000
		V for Cramer	,333	,000
		Contingency ratio	,499	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,404	,000
		V for Cramer	,233	,000
		Contingency ratio	,374	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,442	,000
		V for Cramer	,255	,000
		Contingency ratio	,404	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,159	,000
		V for Cramer	,092	,000
		Contingency ratio	,157	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,419	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,386	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

Unlike interactions in the family context, when it comes to interactions in social networks, they seem to have less influence on the belief that scientific results can benefit people's lives.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,372	,000
		V for Cramer	,215	,000
		Contingency ratio	,348	,000
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,272	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,371	,000
		V for Cramer	,214	,000
		Contingency ratio	,348	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,723	,000
		V for Cramer	,417	,000
		Contingency ratio	,586	,000
N of valid cases			102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,419	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,386	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

As before, belonging to a religious minority group seems to be unrelated to the belief that scientific results can benefit people's lives.

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,269	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,260	,000
		N of valid cases	645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,276	,000
		V for Cramer	,159	,000
		Contingency ratio	,266	,000
		N of valid cases	6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,474	,000
		V for Cramer	,274	,000
		Contingency ratio	,428	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,783	,000
		V for Cramer	,452	,000
		Contingency ratio	,617	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,419	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,386	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Finally, income level also does not seem to weigh very heavily on beliefs that scientific results can benefit people's lives.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science *
Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,364	,000
		V for Cramer	,210	,000
		Contingency ratio	,342	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,321	,000
		V for Cramer	,186	,000
		Contingency ratio	,306	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,279	,000
		V for Cramer	,161	,000
		Contingency ratio	,269	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,233	,000
		V for Cramer	,135	,000
		Contingency ratio	,227	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,586	,000
		V for Cramer	,338	,000
		Contingency ratio	,506	,000
N of valid cases			363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,545	,000
		V for Cramer	,314	,000
		Contingency ratio	,478	,000
N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,419	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,386	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

When asked to what extent you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research, the results suggest that interactions in the family context do not seem to have a strong influence on the answer to this question. The phi value is 0.326 for women, and 0.362 for men. This means that the answers they give to the question are neither related to gender nor to having interactions in the family environment with someone interested in science.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,326	,000
		V for Cramer	,188	,000
		Contingency ratio	,310	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,362	,000
		V for Cramer	,209	,000
		Contingency ratio	,340	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,072
		V for Cramer	1,000	,072
		Contingency ratio	,707	,072
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,778	,508
		V for Cramer	,550	,508
		Contingency ratio	,614	,508
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,414	,062
		V for Cramer	1,000	,062

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,816	,062
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,750	,263
		V for Cramer	,433	,263
		Contingency ratio	,600	,263
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,871	,049
		V for Cramer	,503	,049
		Contingency ratio	,657	,049
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of the age groups, we see that the youngest respondents (aged 16-24) do seem to find that their interactions with family members interested in science are somewhat related to what they say about whether they agree that their country should increase its investment in scientific research (they have a phi of 0.441). But for the other age groups this value drops in all cases, indicating that for all but the youngest respondents, for the rest of the people who responded to the survey such interactions do not have much impact.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recorded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,441	,000
		V for Cramer	,254	,000
		Contingency ratio	,403	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,336	,000
		V for Cramer	,194	,000
		Contingency ratio	,318	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,368	,000
		V for Cramer	,212	,000
		Contingency ratio	,345	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,237	,000
		V for Cramer	,137	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,231	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of people who claim to be ethnic minorities, the ratio is even lower (phi is 0.271).

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,271	,001
		V for Cramer	,156	,001
		Contingency ratio	,262	,001
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,206	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,202	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,445	,000
		V for Cramer	,257	,000
		Contingency ratio	,406	,000
N of valid cases			443	
Prefer to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,709	,000
		V for Cramer	,409	,000
		Contingency ratio	,578	,000
N of valid cases			102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

The same is true for people who are from religious minority groups.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group	Value	Approximate significance
--	-------	--------------------------

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,272	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
		N of valid cases	645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,207	,000
		V for Cramer	,120	,000
		Contingency ratio	,203	,000
		N of valid cases	6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,476	,000
		V for Cramer	,275	,000
		Contingency ratio	,429	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,752	,000
		V for Cramer	,434	,000
		Contingency ratio	,601	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of income level (which we used to determine the SES category of survey respondents), we see that this is also not a variable that has much bearing on whether they agree that their country should increase its investment in scientific research.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,259	,000
		V for Cramer	,149	,000
		Contingency ratio	,251	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,185	,001
		V for Cramer	,107	,001
		Contingency ratio	,182	,001
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,227	,000
		V for Cramer	,131	,000
		Contingency ratio	,221	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,311	,000
		V for Cramer	,180	,000
		Contingency ratio	,297	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,564	,000
		V for Cramer	,326	,000
		Contingency ratio	,492	,000
	N of valid cases		363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,000
		V for Cramer	,272	,000
		Contingency ratio	,426	,000
	N of valid cases		1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

For people who have social media interactions with scientists or people interested in science, this also does not seem to have a relevant bearing on whether they agree that their country should increase its investment in scientific research. The data seem to suggest that the answer to this question is rather based on beliefs or personal opinions, which do not depend on either gender or the context of interaction.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,309	,000
		V for Cramer	,179	,000
		Contingency ratio	,296	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,273	,000
		V for Cramer	,157	,000
		Contingency ratio	,263	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,155	,156
		V for Cramer	,816	,156
		Contingency ratio	,756	,156
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,966	,191
		V for Cramer	,683	,191

		Contingency ratio	,695	,191
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,202	,193
		V for Cramer	,850	,193
		Contingency ratio	,769	,193
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,534	,493
		V for Cramer	,378	,493
		Contingency ratio	,471	,493
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,986	,006
		V for Cramer	,569	,006
		Contingency ratio	,702	,006
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

Younger people do seem to be more influenced by social relationships in social networks, because their responses tend to show a stronger relationship between their answers to the question of whether they agree that their country should increase its investment in scientific research and their age group.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

For those aged 16-24, the phi is 0.436, and for those aged 25-34 the phi is 0.420 (values that indicate that there is some relationship, albeit low).

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,436	,000
		V for Cramer	,252	,000
		Contingency ratio	,400	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,420	,000
		V for Cramer	,242	,000
		Contingency ratio	,387	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,298	,000
		V for Cramer	,172	,000
		Contingency ratio	,286	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,384	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,221	,000
		Contingency ratio	,358	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,196	,000
		V for Cramer	,113	,000
		Contingency ratio	,192	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In contrast, in the case of ethnic minority groups, it seems that following scientists or people interested in science on social media is not related to their thoughts on whether they agree that their country should increase its investment in scientific research.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group	Value	Approximate significance

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,213	,069
		V for Cramer	,123	,069
		Contingency ratio	,209	,069
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,396	,000
		V for Cramer	,229	,000
		Contingency ratio	,368	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,707	,000
		V for Cramer	,408	,000
		Contingency ratio	,577	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

The same is true for people from religious minority groups.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,236	,002
		V for Cramer	,136	,002
		Contingency ratio	,230	,002
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,220	,000
		V for Cramer	,127	,000
		Contingency ratio	,215	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,384	,000
		V for Cramer	,222	,000
		Contingency ratio	,359	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Nominal by Nominal		Phi	,760	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer		V for Cramer	,439	,000
		Contingency ratio	,605	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of the SES level, the results suggest that the relationship is also very low. Only in the case of people with the lowest income do we see a phi of 0.300, which is also low. This indicates that having social media interactions does not affect their views on whether or not to invest more in science.

To what extent do you agree that your country should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,300	,000
		V for Cramer	,173	,000
		Contingency ratio	,287	,000
		N of valid cases	1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,199	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,115	,000
		Contingency ratio	,195	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,205	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,201	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,206	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,202	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,495	,000
		V for Cramer	,286	,000
		Contingency ratio	,444	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,493	,000
		V for Cramer	,285	,000
		Contingency ratio	,442	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	V for Cramer	,175	,000
	Contingency ratio	,290	,000
N of valid cases		7507	

When the question is not about whether it is their country that should invest in science, but whether it is the EU that should increase its investment in scientific research, the answers remain very similar to the previous ones (when asked about the country). This does not seem to be a question on which respondents have a strong opinion, nor can we identify response trends or relationships. It seems that the answers are rather individual opinions, rather than a social trend.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,300	,000
		V for Cramer	,173	,000
		Contingency ratio	,287	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,345	,000
		V for Cramer	,199	,000
		Contingency ratio	,326	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.	
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,548	,463
		V for Cramer	,548	,463
		Contingency ratio	,480	,463
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,050
		V for Cramer	1,000	,050
		Contingency ratio	,707	,050
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,523	,851
		V for Cramer	,302	,851
		Contingency ratio	,463	,851
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,544	,460
		V for Cramer	,385	,460
		Contingency ratio	,478	,460
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000
		V for Cramer	,185	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Contingency ratio	,305	,000
N of valid cases	7507	

c. Statistics have not been calculated because *Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science* is a constant.

Thus, in the case of the age groups, what we see in the results in this question is very similar to what they answered when asked about their country, rather than the EU.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,432	,000
		V for Cramer	,250	,000
		Contingency ratio	,397	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,333	,000
		V for Cramer	,192	,000
		Contingency ratio	,316	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,356	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,206	,000
		Contingency ratio	,336	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,203	,000
		V for Cramer	,117	,000
		Contingency ratio	,199	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000
		V for Cramer	,185	,000
		Contingency ratio	,305	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

As before, in the case of ethnic minority groups, too, we do not see a marked relationship.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,239	,012
		V for Cramer	,138	,012
		Contingency ratio	,233	,012
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,206	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,202	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,425	,000
		V for Cramer	,245	,000
		Contingency ratio	,391	,000
	N of valid cases		443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,646	,000
		V for Cramer	,373	,000
		Contingency ratio	,543	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	V for Cramer	,185	,000
	Contingency ratio	,305	,000
N of valid cases		7507	

Something similar happens in the case of religious minority groups.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,307	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,293	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,200	,000
		V for Cramer	,115	,000
		Contingency ratio	,196	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,466	,000
		V for Cramer	,269	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,422	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,708	,000
		V for Cramer	,409	,000
		Contingency ratio	,578	,000
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000
		V for Cramer	,185	,000
		Contingency ratio	,305	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

Finally, in the case of responses by income level, we also see that the trend of no marked relationship is repeated.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,275	,000

		V for Cramer	,159	,000
		Contingency ratio	,265	,000
		N of valid cases	1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,200	,000
		V for Cramer	,115	,000
		Contingency ratio	,196	,000
		N of valid cases	1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,231	,000
		V for Cramer	,133	,000
		Contingency ratio	,225	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,290	,000
		V for Cramer	,168	,000
		Contingency ratio	,279	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,443	,000
		V for Cramer	,256	,000
		Contingency ratio	,405	,000
		N of valid cases	363	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,475	,000
		V for Cramer	,274	,000
		Contingency ratio	,429	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,320	,000
		V for Cramer	,185	,000
		Contingency ratio	,305	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

In the case of interactions through social networks, the data suggest the same results as in the case of interactions in the family environment. This question does not seem to be a type of question where we can find certain regularities that indicate the existence of a relationship between the variables. It seems rather that each person has answered as he or she believed, because the phi values are always low (in no case do we reach 0.5).

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,304	,000
		V for Cramer	,176	,000
		Contingency ratio	,291	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		N of valid cases	3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,284	,000
		V for Cramer	,164	,000
		Contingency ratio	,273	,000
		N of valid cases	3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,816	,323
		V for Cramer	,577	,323
		Contingency ratio	,632	,323
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,906	,276
		V for Cramer	,640	,276
		Contingency ratio	,671	,276
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,014	,187
		V for Cramer	,717	,187
		Contingency ratio	,712	,187
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,511	,561
		V for Cramer	,361	,561
		Contingency ratio	,455	,561

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,029	,003
		V for Cramer	,594	,003
		Contingency ratio	,717	,003
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In the case of the younger respondents to the survey, we see that there is some influence of social media interactions on their responses (phi of 0.483).

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,483	,000
		V for Cramer	,279	,000
		Contingency ratio	,435	,000
N of valid cases			582	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,415	,000
		V for Cramer	,239	,000
		Contingency ratio	,383	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,309	,000
		V for Cramer	,179	,000
		Contingency ratio	,295	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,336	,000
		V for Cramer	,194	,000
		Contingency ratio	,319	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

On the other hand, when we look at the results according to the ethnic minority group, the phi value is practically negligible (0.178). This indicates that it is not related to their answers to the question.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,178	,349
		V for Cramer	,103	,349
		Contingency ratio	,175	,349
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,220	,000
		V for Cramer	,127	,000
		Contingency ratio	,215	,000
	N of valid cases		6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,405	,000
		V for Cramer	,234	,000
		Contingency ratio	,375	,000
	N of valid cases		443	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,645	,000
		V for Cramer	,372	,000
		Contingency ratio	,542	,000
	N of valid cases		102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

The same is true for people who claim to belong to religious minority groups.

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,235	,002
		V for Cramer	,136	,002
		Contingency ratio	,229	,002
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,221	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,128	,000
		Contingency ratio	,216	,000
		N of valid cases	6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,447	,000
		V for Cramer	,258	,000
		Contingency ratio	,408	,000
		N of valid cases	328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,659	,000
		V for Cramer	,380	,000
		Contingency ratio	,550	,000
		N of valid cases	92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

To what extent do you agree that the European Union should increase its investment in scientific research * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,290	,000
		V for Cramer	,167	,000
		Contingency ratio	,278	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,176	,004
		V for Cramer	,102	,004
		Contingency ratio	,173	,004
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,215	,000
		V for Cramer	,124	,000
		Contingency ratio	,210	,000
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,216	,000
		V for Cramer	,124	,000
		Contingency ratio	,211	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,464	,000
		V for Cramer	,268	,000
		Contingency ratio	,421	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,498	,000
		V for Cramer	,287	,000
		Contingency ratio	,446	,000
N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,306	,000
		V for Cramer	,177	,000
		Contingency ratio	,292	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

On the perception of citizens' knowledge of scientific evidence on education in their country, compared to other EU countries, we find that having interactions with people interested in science in the home environment does not have much impact (phi of 0.238 for women, compared to 0.267 for men).

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,238	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,137	,000
		Contingency ratio	,231	,000
		N of valid cases	3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,267	,000
		V for Cramer	,154	,000
		Contingency ratio	,258	,000
		N of valid cases	3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,354	,350
		V for Cramer	,354	,350
		Contingency ratio	,333	,350
		N of valid cases		
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,742	,159
		V for Cramer	,524	,159
		Contingency ratio	,596	,159
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,707	,558
		V for Cramer	,500	,558
		Contingency ratio	,577	,558
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,867	,076

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,501	,076
		Contingency ratio	,655	,076
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,618	,400
		V for Cramer	,357	,400
		Contingency ratio	,525	,400
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,243	,000
		N of valid cases		7507

When we look at the data by age of respondents, we see that the youngest respondents (16-24) do show some influence of family interactions with someone interested in science (phi of 0.379). However, as age increases, this relationship disappears.

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
 * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age	Value	Approximate significance
-------------	-------	--------------------------

16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,379	,000
		V for Cramer	,219	,000
		Contingency ratio	,355	,000
		N of valid cases	582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,241	,000
		V for Cramer	,139	,000
		Contingency ratio	,234	,000
		N of valid cases	1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,287	,000
		V for Cramer	,166	,000
		Contingency ratio	,276	,000
		N of valid cases	2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,244	,000
		V for Cramer	,141	,000
		Contingency ratio	,237	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,182	,000
		V for Cramer	,105	,000
		Contingency ratio	,179	,000
		N of valid cases	1362	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,243	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In the case of those who say they belong to an ethnic minority group, the result of the phi value (0.134) suggests that there is no relationship between what they think about the comparison between the knowledge of scientific evidence in their country and that in other EU countries.

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,134	,667
		V for Cramer	,077	,667
		Contingency ratio	,133	,667
	N of valid cases		523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,168	,000
		V for Cramer	,097	,000
		Contingency ratio	,166	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,348	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,329	,000
N of valid cases			443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,551	,002
		V for Cramer	,318	,002
		Contingency ratio	,482	,002
N of valid cases			102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,243	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

Something similar happens when we analyse the data according to the religious minority group.

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,217	,002
		V for Cramer	,125	,002
		Contingency ratio	,212	,002
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,174	,000
		V for Cramer	,101	,000
		Contingency ratio	,172	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,347	,000
		V for Cramer	,200	,000
		Contingency ratio	,328	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,629	,000
		V for Cramer	,363	,000
		Contingency ratio	,533	,000
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,243	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases	7507
------------------	------

In the data by income level (SES), we cannot find any strong relationships either (we have for example a phi of 0.193 for people at the lowest SES level).

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,193	,000
		V for Cramer	,111	,000
		Contingency ratio	,189	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,206	,000
		V for Cramer	,119	,000
		Contingency ratio	,202	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,187	,000
		V for Cramer	,108	,000
		Contingency ratio	,184	,000

N of valid cases			1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,211	,000
		V for Cramer	,122	,000
		Contingency ratio	,206	,000
N of valid cases			2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,417	,000
		V for Cramer	,241	,000
		Contingency ratio	,385	,000
N of valid cases			363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,378	,000
		V for Cramer	,218	,000
		Contingency ratio	,354	,000
N of valid cases			1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,243	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

In the case of perceived knowledge of scientific evidence on education in the country, compared to other EU countries, the data suggest that the results are similar to the question on scientific evidence in education. We do not seem to find a marked relationship between this question and the contexts of interaction (neither in the family, nor in social networks), nor by vulnerable groups.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,297	,000
		V for Cramer	,171	,000
		Contingency ratio	,284	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,471	,459
		V for Cramer	,471	,459
		Contingency ratio	,426	,459
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,671	,249
		V for Cramer	,474	,249
		Contingency ratio	,557	,249

N of valid cases				
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,000	,199
		V for Cramer	,707	,199
		Contingency ratio	,707	,199
N of valid cases				
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,649	,205
		V for Cramer	,459	,205
		Contingency ratio	,544	,205
N of valid cases			26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,811	,041
		V for Cramer	,468	,041
		Contingency ratio	,630	,041
N of valid cases				
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

The only exception is, once again, in the case of younger people (16-24 years old), who do seem to be more influenced by the interactions they have on social networks, as can be seen in the table below.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,409	,000
		V for Cramer	,236	,000
		Contingency ratio	,379	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,303	,000
		V for Cramer	,175	,000
		Contingency ratio	,290	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,251	,000
		V for Cramer	,145	,000
		Contingency ratio	,244	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,355	,000
		V for Cramer	,205	,000
		Contingency ratio	,335	,000
	N of valid cases		1917	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,213	,000
		V for Cramer	,123	,000
		Contingency ratio	,208	,000
	N of valid cases		1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

In the case of those who say they belong to ethnic minority groups, the data suggest that there is no strong relationship (phi of 0.250).

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,250	,001
		V for Cramer	,144	,001
		Contingency ratio	,242	,001
	N of valid cases		523	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,223	,000
		V for Cramer	,128	,000
		Contingency ratio	,217	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,318	,000
		V for Cramer	,184	,000
		Contingency ratio	,303	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,638	,000
		V for Cramer	,368	,000
		Contingency ratio	,538	,000
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

The same is true for those who say they belong to a religious minority group.

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,200	,011
		V for Cramer	,116	,011
		Contingency ratio	,196	,011
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,225	,000
		V for Cramer	,130	,000
		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,368	,000
		V for Cramer	,212	,000
		Contingency ratio	,345	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,615	,000
		V for Cramer	,355	,000
		Contingency ratio	,524	,000
	N of valid cases		92	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

Finally, in the case of the SES level, we also found no evidence of an influence of social media interactions on their perception of knowledge of scientific evidence in education in their country, compared to other EU countries.

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on education in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,281	,000
		V for Cramer	,162	,000
		Contingency ratio	,271	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	,000
		V for Cramer	,149	,000
		Contingency ratio	,249	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,196	,000
		V for Cramer	,113	,000
		Contingency ratio	,193	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,176	,000
		V for Cramer	,102	,000
		Contingency ratio	,174	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,380	,000
		V for Cramer	,219	,000
		Contingency ratio	,355	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,455	,000
		V for Cramer	,263	,000
		Contingency ratio	,414	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of the same questions, but for gender, we find very similar results to those discussed for the case of the evidence on education. All the tables are attached below:

**What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
* What is your gender**

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,262	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,254	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,263	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,254	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,258	,792
		V for Cramer	,258	,792
		Contingency ratio	,250	,792
	N of valid cases			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,581	,669
		V for Cramer	,411	,669
		Contingency ratio	,502	,669
	N of valid cases			
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,500	,827
		V for Cramer	,354	,827
		Contingency ratio	,447	,827
	N of valid cases			
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,882	,063
		V for Cramer	,509	,063
		Contingency ratio	,661	,063
	N of valid cases		26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,624	,381
		V for Cramer	,360	,381
		Contingency ratio	,529	,381
	N of valid cases			
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
 * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,348	,000
		V for Cramer	,201	,000
		Contingency ratio	,329	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,246	,000
		V for Cramer	,142	,000
		Contingency ratio	,238	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,340	,000
		V for Cramer	,196	,000
		Contingency ratio	,322	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,256	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		V for Cramer	,148	,000
		Contingency ratio	,248	,000
		N of valid cases	1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,127	,038
		V for Cramer	,073	,038
		Contingency ratio	,126	,038
		N of valid cases	1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,174	,201
		V for Cramer	,100	,201

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,171	,201
		N of valid cases	523	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,198	,000
		V for Cramer	,114	,000
		Contingency ratio	,194	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,341	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000
		Contingency ratio	,323	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,575	,001
		V for Cramer	,332	,001
		Contingency ratio	,498	,001
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science
 * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,238	,000
		V for Cramer	,137	,000
		Contingency ratio	,231	,000
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,194	,000
		V for Cramer	,112	,000
		Contingency ratio	,190	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,330	,000
		V for Cramer	,190	,000
		Contingency ratio	,313	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,714	,000
		V for Cramer	,412	,000
		Contingency ratio	,581	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

N of valid cases			92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
N of valid cases			7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,259	,000
		V for Cramer	,150	,000
		Contingency ratio	,251	,000
N of valid cases			1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,186	,000
		V for Cramer	,108	,000
		Contingency ratio	,183	,000
N of valid cases			1069	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,144	,018
		V for Cramer	,083	,018
		Contingency ratio	,142	,018
	N of valid cases		1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,240	,000
		V for Cramer	,138	,000
		Contingency ratio	,233	,000
	N of valid cases		2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,375	,000
		V for Cramer	,217	,000
		Contingency ratio	,352	,000
	N of valid cases		363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,381	,000
		V for Cramer	,220	,000
		Contingency ratio	,356	,000
	N of valid cases		1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * What is your gender

Symmetrical measurements

What is your gender			Value	Approximate significance
Woman	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,301	,000
		V for Cramer	,174	,000
		Contingency ratio	,289	,000
	N of valid cases		3815	
Man	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,264	,000
		V for Cramer	,152	,000
		Contingency ratio	,255	,000
	N of valid cases		3608	
Trans	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,730	,443
		V for Cramer	,516	,443
		Contingency ratio	,590	,443
	N of valid cases			
Non binary	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1,039	,044
		V for Cramer	,735	,044

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,721	,044
		N of valid cases		
Fluid	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,707	,558
		V for Cramer	,500	,558
		Contingency ratio	,577	,558
		N of valid cases		
Others	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,600	,312
		V for Cramer	,425	,312
		Contingency ratio	,515	,312
		N of valid cases	26	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,889	,010
		V for Cramer	,514	,010
		Contingency ratio	,665	,010
		N of valid cases		
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Recoded age

Symmetrical measurements

Recoded age			Value	Approximate significance
16-24	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,373	,000
		V for Cramer	,215	,000
		Contingency ratio	,349	,000
	N of valid cases		582	
25-34	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,317	,000
		V for Cramer	,183	,000
		Contingency ratio	,302	,000
	N of valid cases		1261	
35-49	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,268	,000
		V for Cramer	,155	,000
		Contingency ratio	,259	,000
	N of valid cases		2385	
50-64	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,341	,000
		V for Cramer	,197	,000
		Contingency ratio	,323	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	N of valid cases		1917	
+65	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,231	,000
		V for Cramer	,134	,000
		Contingency ratio	,225	,000
	N of valid cases		1362	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
	N of valid cases		7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,230	,006
		V for Cramer	,133	,006
		Contingency ratio	,224	,006
	N of valid cases		523	

No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,229	,000
		V for Cramer	,132	,000
		Contingency ratio	,223	,000
		N of valid cases	6439	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,300	,000
		V for Cramer	,173	,000
		Contingency ratio	,288	,000
		N of valid cases	443	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,548	,002
		V for Cramer	,316	,002
		Contingency ratio	,481	,002
		N of valid cases	102	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Symmetrical measurements

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group			Value	Approximate significance
Yes	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,208	,006
		V for Cramer	,120	,006
		Contingency ratio	,203	,006
	N of valid cases		645	
No	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,221	,000
		V for Cramer	,127	,000
		Contingency ratio	,216	,000
	N of valid cases		6442	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,360	,000
		V for Cramer	,208	,000
		Contingency ratio	,339	,000
	N of valid cases		328	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,674	,000
		V for Cramer	,389	,000
		Contingency ratio	,559	,000
	N of valid cases		92	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	V for Cramer	,169	,000
	Contingency ratio	,281	,000
N of valid cases		7507	

What is your perception of the public's knowledge of scientific evidence on gender in your country, compared to other EU countries * Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science * Household Annual Income in Euros

Symmetrical measurements

Household Annual Income in Euros			Value	Approximate significance
Item 1	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,253	,000
		V for Cramer	,146	,000
		Contingency ratio	,245	,000
	N of valid cases		1202	
Item 2	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,235	,000
		V for Cramer	,136	,000
		Contingency ratio	,229	,000
	N of valid cases		1069	
Item 3	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,224	,000
		V for Cramer	,129	,000

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		Contingency ratio	,219	,000
		N of valid cases	1180	
Item 4	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,201	,000
		V for Cramer	,116	,000
		Contingency ratio	,197	,000
		N of valid cases	2654	
I do not know	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,335	,000
		V for Cramer	,193	,000
		Contingency ratio	,317	,000
		N of valid cases	363	
Prefer not to answer	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,436	,000
		V for Cramer	,252	,000
		Contingency ratio	,399	,000
		N of valid cases	1039	
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,293	,000
		V for Cramer	,169	,000
		Contingency ratio	,281	,000
		N of valid cases	7507	

5.7. Conclusion

<p><i>Knowledge of actions for the recruitment in science</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most known initiatives are those that target women in science (33.01%), while the least known are those that target LGBTI+ individuals (20.70%).
<p><i>Participation in actions for the recruitment of new talent in science</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only 9.7% of the total of respondents has participated in actions for the recruitment of new talent in science
<p><i>Benefits of scientific research</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More than three-quarter parts of the participants (76.3%) think that scientific research benefits citizens' lives.
<p><i>Investment in scientific research</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Almost eight of ten respondents agree to some extent with an increase of investment in scientific research in their country (78.94%) and the EU (78.75%)
<p><i>Citizens' knowledge of scientific evidence on gender and education</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In both cases, approximately one third of the respondents think that in their country, citizens have lower levels of scientific knowledge on gender and education, compared with other EU countries. A similar proportion thinks that in their country, citizens have intermediate levels of knowledge.
<p><i>Vulnerable groups</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People from vulnerable groups are more likely to know initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science compared with the total of respondents - Participants from vulnerable groups participate in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science in a higher proportion than the total of respondents - No differences across vulnerable groups are observed in the perception of the benefits of scientific research.
<p><i>The role of interactions</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Both analysed interactions (living a situation that changed their mind about science and following a scientist on social media), boost citizens' knowledge of actions to recruit new talent in science; however, the impact of interaction 2 is greater across vulnerable groups. - Both interactions increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who participate in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science. The increase in most cases is approximately 100%, in comparison with the total of respondents. - Interactions have a notable impact on the perception of the benefits of science, increasing the proportion of respondents from all vulnerable groups who perceive science as beneficial for society. The impact is more remarkable in the case of interaction 2 (following a scientific person on social networks). - Interactions with science have an effect in increasing the responses "totally agree"

and “totally disagree”. One underlying hypothesis that may explain this result is that interactions with science provide citizens with tools and knowledge to base their opinions on scientific arguments and therefore, they feel more confident to respond based on arguments and not personal opinions.

Associations

- On whether or not initiatives to increase participation in science by vulnerable groups, people with low SES, ethnic or religious minorities, women or the LGBTBI+ community are known, what we see is that in general the relationships are low. Having interactions with people interested in science does not seem to have a very marked impact on awareness of initiatives to increase participation in science. In any case, according to the results, social network interactions have a greater impact than those that occur in the family, from the point of view of knowing about initiatives to increase the participation of vulnerable groups in science.
- Gender, ethnic minority group or religious minority group variables do not tend to have much impact on awareness of initiatives to increase participation in science. In contrast, both SES level and age are much more strongly related.
- In the case of knowing about any initiative that promotes the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science, interactions with people in the family environment, who are interested in science, have more impact than interactions through social networks, for example when following a scientist or a person interested in science. This is especially true for women (gender), young people (age groups) and people with a low income. On the other hand, if you have a higher income, if you are in the 50+ age group, or if you belong to an ethnic group or religious minority, this seems to have less impact on finding out about initiatives that promote the participation of new talent, especially young people, in science.
- On participation in initiatives aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science, including vulnerable groups, we do see marked relationships here. In this case, interactions in the family tend to have the most weight on the decisions one makes to participate or not in initiatives aimed at increasing participation in science-related initiatives. We also found a greater impact for men than for women, or for groups of people younger than 49 years old. For people with lower incomes (low SES), having interactions (especially from someone in the family who is interested in science) tends to have a greater impact on promoting their participation in initiatives aimed at increasing the participation of new talent in science. For ethnic minorities or religious minorities, on the other hand, this relationship is much weaker. In either case, interactions with family members are more important than those through social networks.
- Interestingly, when asked whether they believe that scientific results can benefit the lives of citizens, people from ethnic minorities who have interactions with someone in the family who has an interest in science have a greater impact (even

more so than in terms of gender, or age group). But this is the only case where this happens, out of all the questions in Block 4.

- Questions such as the survey respondents' perception of whether the country should invest more in scientific research, or whether the EU should invest more in scientific research, do not give a pattern in which we can find regularities. It seems that people respond more individually, and their answers do not allow us to establish that there is a relationship of impact or influence of interactions.
- The same is true for the question on citizens' perceived knowledge of the evidence on both education and gender (and the comparison with other EU countries). We cannot establish that interactions (both those in the family context and those in social networks) are related in any way (whichever vulnerable group we are referring to). It does seem that younger people are more likely to be influenced by interactions either in the family or on social media.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

6. Online workshop with KAPIs members

On April 29th, a workshop was held to discuss the results for topic (d) with KAPIs members. They showed interest in the results and in the idea of using multiple approaches to generate awareness in the target-groups. In brief, they underlined and appreciated the following points:

- The relevance of the Scientific Dialogic Gathering as method that can transferable and applicable in other contexts/situations and with different targets (e.g., children).
- The centrality of the educational system and in particular the importance of the role of teachers and social/health workers in fostering the participation of students/young people, especially in marginal contexts. The necessity to use a more inclusive approach by teachers and educators, who have to be trained and supported.
- The importance of the intergenerational learning, including the role of the family to create a positive environment for children/young people.
- The necessity to increase the scientific literacy and the knowledge capital of citizens as a pre-condition for them to fully participate in a democratic society.
- The relevance of the bottom-up initiatives to fill the gap between science ad society and the necessity to integrate this approach with the top-down approach, that is today the prevalent one in formal institutions.

KAPIs members' comments and suggestions can be found in an extensively form (including their specific recommendations) in the document "D4.1 Minutes from Workshop 1". They will be used as stimuli for the next steps of ALLINTERACT project.

7. Conclusions

The Report WP4 contributes both to understand more deeply the factors that hinder or facilitate the participation of new talents in science and to illustrate the awareness-raising actions for the recruitment of them.

Barriers but also actions emerge to foster the recruitment of new talent in science

Existing literature review shows that social (e.g. inequalities), technological (e.g. digital divide), organizational (e.g. discrimination in the workplace and the lack of policies and accountable procedures) and cultural barriers (stereotypes, cultural beliefs, values) hinder the participation of vulnerable groups in science (especially women, but also ethnic/religious minorities, people with a low socio-economic status, young people *etc.*). To overcome these barriers, studies underline, among others, **the importance of families, parents, and peers** in fostering and supporting young people/girls' interests, aspirations and priorities, especially in marginal contexts; **avoiding bias** in recruitment, selection, evaluation and career processes or the role of technology as a central factor to favor **horizontal, participative, and transversal learning**. SMA reinforce this finding, showing that messages frequently (between 73% and 100%) include examples of **transformative initiatives, which foster the recruitment of new talent in science**. Actions mentioned concern: awareness-messages or campaigns, calls for action, corporate and academic initiatives, training, courses and other educational projects.

Figure 7.1. Proportion of transformative initiatives on social media

Additionally, in FG participants proposed different actions to foster the participation but they also underlined barriers that hinder it. For instance, vulnerable women agreed that

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

people who participated in science initiatives were often the “same type of people” (i.e., people with the same socio-cultural characteristics or the same biographical paths).

Most of the actions target women and young people

Quantitative results from the survey and SMA conclude that most actions are addressed to women and youth. On the one hand, the results from the survey point out that the **best-known initiatives are those that target women in science** (33,33% to 49,14%), while the least known are those that target LGBTQI+ individuals (20.70%).

Figure 7.2. Knowledge of initiatives for the promotion of women in science across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

In **social networks** messages, especially Twitter and Instagram, there are examples of initiatives targeting **women and kids/young people, but also migrants and low-income students**. On the other hand, FG participants acknowledged the importance of awareness-raising actions. Women were able to provide only a limited number of examples, while parents, teachers and students were more inclined to talk about them.

Interactions with science foster citizen participation in science

A common characteristic of the identified initiatives is that when citizens interact with science, they are more likely to participate in science. In this line, parents who participated in the FG acknowledged that participating in “**Scientific Dialogic Gatherings**” (see “Work Package 1” for details) increase the awareness and the interest about science results. It **encouraged them to attend and to promote other scientific events** (talks or conferences) in associations or schools. Teachers valued interactions with role models (e.g., women scientists, young scientists etc.) and diverse science contents as important ways to recruit new talent. Survey shows that **interactions with science increase** the proportion of people from **vulnerable groups who participate in initiatives** for the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

recruitment of new talent in science. **Women** and people from **low SES** are the two groups that benefit more.

Figure 7.3. Impact of interactions with science in the promotion of participation of women and people from low SES in science

People from vulnerable groups value scientific research and recognize its benefits

Survey indicates that, in **most vulnerable groups**, the proportion of participants who think that **scientific research benefits citizens' lives** ranges from 74.50% (young people) to 76.90% (religious minorities). The only exception is the LGBTQI+ individuals (with 58.82%). **Interactions with science improves the perception of the benefits of science in vulnerable groups.** The impact is more remarkable when participants follow a scientific person on social networks. People with low SES are the group with a higher increase in their perception of the benefits of science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 7.4. Perception of benefits of science across vulnerable groups and interactions

In FG, **students expressed the importance of organizing different activities to improve scientific literacy** and satisfy aspirations. They expressed the need for further communication campaigns, the inclusion of science-related topics in curricula and equal opportunities for all students.

If science is linked to real life, people show more involvement, interest and curiosity in science

Literature review shows that there is clearly a strong interest for engagement-events and learning activation when these events are related to daily life issues. In FG participants expressed that their **relationship with science derive from both their daily life experiences** and their curiosity towards science. Participation in the discussion of everyday topics with scientific evidence increases self-confidence in people who are not used to getting involved in science. This result has gained much relevance during the pandemic, during which individual and public health concerns have affected all citizens, but **in particular women** because of their familiar responsibilities (children, parents, people with disabilities etc.) or their professional roles (e.g., they work more in the public or social sectors and so on). In this new context, science has become unexpectedly part of their daily lives. Finally, quantitative results from the international survey show that **changing their mind because something happened to them or their families (e.g. daily life issues) promotes knowledge of and participation in initiatives** for the recruitment of new talent in science.

Figure 7.5. Increases in the participation of vulnerable groups in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science due to changing their mind because something happened to them or their families

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Social media provides opportunities to interact with science that foster initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science

Across vulnerable groups, **following a person who publishes about science** on social media is associated with higher knowledge and with **participation in initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science**. Additionally, SMA shows that diverse initiatives emerge across all social networks, including **scholarships, competitions, fairs, exhibitions and projects, among others**.

Figure 7.6. Examples of initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science identified on SMA

One of the initiatives found in the literature review is the creation of a digital learning resource for citizens to learn how they can participate in the co-creation of smart cities. The literature review concludes that initiatives should take advantage of ICT to bridge the digital divide and facilitate new ways of learning, especially for young people.

Initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science are promoted by diverse agents

SMA points out that initiatives designed with a **top-down approach prevail** because of the presence of representatives of institutional actors (NGO, government, enterprises, universities). **Bottom-up initiatives are less frequent, but more emotionally involved**. In the literature review and in the FG, schools, universities and national institutions emerged as the main promoters of the initiatives for the recruitment of new talent in science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 7.7. Distribution of Top-Down and Bottom-up initiatives in gender across strategies (top-down and bottom-up)

In conclusion, this piece of research shows that barriers to participation in science are still present, especially cultural ones; however, awareness-raising initiatives for the recruitment of new talent are numerous and replicable in different contexts. These initiatives are sufficiently known by vulnerable groups, even if not at the same level, but citizens' use of scientific evidence is still limited, their participation is low, and the activities, even if numerous, are targeted often to specific groups (women, in particular). Results suggest that actions could be designed for different targets, involving actors in a circular top-down/bottom-up process, without undervaluing non-traditional forms of social and political engagement, and in a more inclusive way: this means that the new challenge is using different frameworks, languages and technologies, and referring more to citizens' daily life issues to improve the participation and the co-creation of knowledge.